

GAPS

Decentring the Study of Migrant
Returns and Return Policies

Country Dossier Turkey

Return Migration from Turkey to Syria and Afghanistan

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List of Abbreviations

AFAD	Disaster and Emergency Management Authority
AI	Amnesty International
AIDA	Asylum Information Database
AKP	Justice and Development Party
ASAM	Association for Social Development and Aid Mobilization
AVRR	Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration
EU	European Union
EUTRA	EU-Turkey Readmission Agreement
EUTRS	EU-Turkey Statement
FRIT	Facility for Refugees in Turkey
FRONTEX	European Border and Coast Guard Agency
FSA	Free Syrian Army
GDMM	General Directorate of Migration Management
GÖKSEM	Removal Centres and Irregular Migrant Reception and Referral Centres
HRW	Human Rights Watch
HTS	Hay'at Tahrir al-Sham
IBM	Integrated Border Management
ICMPD	International Centre for Migration Policy Development
IGO	Intergovernmental Organization
IHH	Foundation for Human Rights and Freedoms and Humanitarian Relief
IOM	International Organization for Migration
IP	International Protection
IPA	Instrument for Pre-Accession Assistance
LEUs	Law Enforcement Units
LFIP	Law on Foreigners and International Protection
MMP	Mobile Migration Points
MoFA	Ministry of Foreign Affairs
MoI	Ministry of Interior

Mülteci-Der	Association for Solidarity with Refugees
NACORAC	National Coordination & Joint Risk Analysis CentreCenter
N-AVRR	National Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
OES	Operation Euphrates Shield
OOB	Operation Olive Branch
PDMM	Provincial Directorate of Migration Management
PMM	Presidency of Migration Management
RRT	Refugee Rights Turkey
RSD	Refugee Status Determination
SACD	Syrian Association for Citizens' Dignity
SNC	Syrian National Council
SOHR	Syrian Observatory for Human Rights
TCN	Third-Country Nationals
TAC	Temporary Accommodation Centre
TİKA	Turkish Cooperation and Coordination Agency
TP	Temporary Protection
TRC	Turkish Red Crescent
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees
US	United States
USSR	Union of Soviet Socialist Republics
UKRI	UK Research and Innovation

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Executive Summary

This dossier/report critically analyses Turkey's return migration governance system, particularly focusing on the return of Syrians and Afghans. Turkey has become a key player in managing migration flows due to its geographic position and its role as a host country for the largest refugee population globally, largely composed of Syrians under temporary protection and Afghans. The selected country case emphasises decentring the analysis of return migration governance from the dominant Eurocentric focus that pervades much of the existing literature. By placing Turkey at the core of the study, the report highlights the complexities and nuances of migration management beyond the traditional frameworks that focus on the EU as the central actor. Regarding decentring, the report also focuses on local contexts and actors, provides an understanding of regional and global implications, and highlights stratified legal frameworks.

The main research questions of the report are: "How does Turkey's return migration policy toward Syrians and Afghans, as part of South-to-South migration and a decentring approach, function within its legal frameworks and external influences such as the EU? What legal, social, and geopolitical dynamics shape these return processes, and how do these policies manifest in practice based on fieldwork evidence?" The report explores the complex dynamics of voluntary and coerced returns for Syrians and Afghans while investigating the broader consequences of legal stratification and the externalization of the EU migration control.

This report utilizes a qualitative research methodology, combining comprehensive desk and fieldwork with macro-level interviews, focus groups, and participatory observation to examine Turkey's return migration system in-depth. The desk research component of the report analyses the legal, policy, and geopolitical frameworks that shape Turkey's return migration governance. It focuses on critical legal documents, official statistics and documents, NGO reports, and academic publications. The qualitative data were collected through 36 semi-structured interviews with state and non-state actors, with a wide range of stakeholders in selected critical cities (Ankara, Gaziantep, Iğdir, Istanbul, and Van), particularly for Syrians and Afghans. These areas were chosen due to their importance as hubs for migration governance and return logistics. The fieldwork was conducted from January 2023 to May 2024. Thus, the research only briefly provides an overview (Chapter 5) regarding the development after December 8, 2024, when Syria witnessed a transformative moment leading to President Bashar al-Assad's departure from the country and a significant period started regarding Syria's returns.

Key Findings

1. **Legal Stratification and Differentiation of Returns:** One of the report's key findings is the stratified legal system governing Syrians and Afghans' return. Syrians benefit from the temporary protection system, which offers them certain legal safeguards against deportation. However, their temporary status also contributes to a sense of legal limbo and precarity for returns. For Afghans, the situation is significantly more precarious. Mainly classified as irregular migrants with difficult access to international protection, Afghans face the risk of forced deportations and pushbacks without the same legal recourse as Syrians. The lack of formal protection mechanisms for Afghans exposes them to rapid deportation processes, often with little to no access to legal aid or asylum claims.
2. **Voluntary vs. Coerced Returns:** While presented as humanitarian solutions, the meso-level interviews reveal the coercive aspects of voluntary returns. Syrians living under temporary protection experience economic hardship, social exclusion, and legal uncertainty, which pushes them toward accepting return agreements, even when the conditions in Syria remain unsafe or uncertain. The creation of safe zones in northern

Syria has been a key strategy for Turkey in encouraging Syrian returns. However, the safety and sustainability of these zones remain in question. The research found that overcrowding and a lack of adequate infrastructure in these areas may make it difficult for returnees to reintegrate.

3. **The EU's Role and Externalization of Migration Control:** The EU has played a significant role in Turkey's return migration governance, primarily through the EU-Turkey Statement (2016). The agreement formalized Turkey's role as a buffer zone, tasked with preventing irregular migration to Europe in exchange for financial support. The EU's financial backing has enabled Turkey to develop its national return infrastructure, but it has also placed immense pressure on Turkey to facilitate returns, often risking coercive practices. The report highlights how the EU-funded programmes, particularly through the Facility for Refugees in Turkey (FRIT), have been instrumental in establishing voluntary return programmes for Syrians. However, these programmes have been critiqued for creating an environment where returns are indirectly coerced by poor living conditions in Turkey and the lack of long-term integration prospects. For Afghans, the EU's influence is less direct but still significant. The externalization of migration control has resulted in the deterrence and deportation of Afghans, with Turkey acting as a frontline state in managing irregular migration flows from Afghanistan. The research shows that pushbacks and forced deportations of Afghans at Turkey's eastern borders seem to be common, reflecting a broader security-driven approach to return migration governance.
4. **Operational Infrastructure and Capacity Building:** The research also highlights the operational infrastructure supporting return migration and establishing a national return mechanism in Turkey, much of which has been financed by the EU. This includes removal centres, registration systems, Mobile Migration Points, Irregular Migrant Reception and Referral Centres, and cross-border operations aimed at facilitating the return of refugees to Syria and Afghanistan. The report found that while this infrastructure has improved Turkey's capacity to manage returns, it has also contributed to the irregularization of certain migrant populations, particularly not only Afghans but also Syrians. There are claims that border control measures have led to increased pushbacks of irregular migrants, particularly along Turkey's eastern borders with Iran. These pushbacks often occur without due process, further complicating return migration's legal and humanitarian landscape.

In conclusion, this report provides a detailed and critical analysis of the effects of return migration governance in Turkey, offering valuable insights into the coercive mechanisms, legal frameworks, and international influences that shape the experiences of Syrians and Afghans under Turkey's return policies. The report also underscores the significant role of the EU in shaping these return policies, particularly through financial incentives and the externalization of migration control.

Keywords: Return Policy Turkey, Return Migration Governance, Voluntary Return, Coerced Return, Pushbacks, Syrians, Afghans, EU

The GAPs Project

GAPs is a Horizon Europe project that aims to conduct a comprehensive multidisciplinary study on the drivers of return policies and the barriers and enablers of international cooperation on return migration. The project aims to examine the disconnects and discrepancies between expectations of return policies and their actual outcomes by decentring the dominant, one-sided understanding of “return policy-making”. To this end, GAPs:

- Examines the shortcomings of the EU’s return governance;
- Analyses enablers and barriers to international cooperation and;
- Explores the perspectives of migrants themselves to understand their knowledge, aspirations and experiences with return policies.

GAPs combines its decentring approach with three innovative concepts:

- A focus on return migration infrastructures, which allows the project to analyse governance fissures;
- An analysis of return migration diplomacy to understand how relations between EU MSs and third countries hinder cooperation on return and;
- A trajectory approach that uses a socio-spatial and temporal lens to understand migrant agency.

GAPs is a three-year interdisciplinary project (2023–2026) coordinated by Uppsala University and the Bonn International Centre for Conflict Studies with 17 partners in 12 countries on four continents. The 12 countries in which fieldwork has been conducted are Sweden, Nigeria, Germany, Morocco, the Netherlands, Afghanistan, Poland, Georgia, Turkey, Tunisia, Greece and Iraq.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Explaining the GAPS Project and WP4

This dossier/report has been compiled in the context of the Horizon Europe GAPs project on 'Decentring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond,' more specifically, its 4th Work Package (WP4) on 'Return Migration Governance in the African and Middle Eastern Regions and the Role of the EU.'

Since the vast majority of migrants and refugees move and reside in and among countries in the immediate region of their origin countries, return migration will also predominantly take place within the region of countries in crisis. Yet, scholarly concerns have overwhelmingly focused on the minority of migrants who travelled further afield, particularly to the European Union (EU), and returned to their regions of origin. Relatively little attention has been given to the return policies of neighbouring receiving states in the Global South.

Studying this regional dimension can remedy the Eurocentric bias in studying return migration governance. At the same time, the European dimension needs to be considered when looking at return governance within the African and Middle Eastern regions, as it is shaped by the EU's externalization and return migration policies. On the one hand, the EU's deterrence and externalization 'partnerships' fundamentally affect return diplomacies, infrastructures, and trajectories in its neighbouring regions. On the other hand, the governance of regional returns has repercussions for the migration dynamics the EU seeks to control, its engagement with 'third countries,' and the international norms it claims to uphold. To address this knowledge gap, this work package (WP4) aims to better understand the intersections between (i) return migration governance within the African and Middle Eastern regions and (ii) the role of the EU and its external migration policy. To this end, it asks three core research questions: (i) What characterizes return migration governance within African and Middle Eastern regions? Specifically, how does the EU's external migration policy shape these modalities? (ii) What are the driving forces behind these types of return migration governance? Specifically, how has the EU's external migration policy affected these drivers? and (iii) What are the effects of these drivers and modalities of regional migration governance for both people and policy? Specifically, what are specific regional return migration governance implications for the EU's external migration policy? The Work Package answers these questions for eight 'host countries' (Iraq, Jordan, Lebanon, Turkey, Iran, Morocco, Tunisia, Libya) focused on three 'origin countries' (Syria, Afghanistan, Nigeria).

In this framework and as parallel to the WP4's common research questions, this country report dossier critically analyses Turkey's return migration governance, focusing on the return of Syrians and Afghans within the context of South-to-South migration and a decentring approach. By emphasizing Turkey's role as a key actor in managing migration flows, the report shifts the analytical focus away from traditional Eurocentric perspectives, instead highlighting Turkey's legal frameworks and agency in migration management. The research explores the legal stratification that distinguishes the return processes for Syrians under temporary protection and Afghans under international protection but also those who are extensively classified as irregular migrants, exposing them to forced deportations and pushbacks without sufficient legal recourse. The dossier investigates the different types of returns (pushbacks, forced returns and voluntary returns) and analyses the coercive nature of some return mechanisms and implementations while also analysing the EU's influence through the EU-Turkey Statement of 2016 and subsequent financial backing, which has shaped Turkey's return infrastructure. The study utilizes a comprehensive desk research qualitative research, including 36 interviews conducted across key migration hubs to offer insights into Turkey's return migration policy.

1.2. Introducing the Country-Case

Turkey, historically a crossroads between continents, has long served as a destination, source and transit country for migrants and refugees. Its geopolitical position, bordering the EU to the west and conflict zones to the south and east, has placed it at the centre of migration flows, particularly following the Syrian Civil War in 2011. In August 2021, the Taliban's return to power in Afghanistan led to widespread fear and instability, causing a significant exodus of Afghans seeking refuge. Many fled to neighbouring countries or attempted to reach Europe, often passing through Turkey.

The country case for Turkey reflects a complex migration management system where legal stratification, coercion, and external pressures converge. Turkey's role as a host country and buffer zone for Europe complicates the nature of returns, especially for Syrians and Afghans, who face significantly different return processes. The EU's financial and political influence remains pivotal in shaping Turkey's return policies, although internal challenges, such as the aftermath of the earthquakes, economic crises, and rising anti-migrant sentiment, continue to affect the implementation of these policies.

There are more than 3 million refugees and migrants in Turkey, all of whom are seeking international protection. As of 23 January 2025, 2,870,226 Syrians have been granted temporary protection (TP) status. Another group of foreigners are international protection (IP) holders. According to the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR), there were 219,000 refugees and asylum seekers in Turkey as of 2025.¹ According to the latest news interview with Minister of Interior Ali Yerlikaya, 215,579 IP holders from countries including Iraq, Afghanistan, Iran and Ukraine constitute another group of foreign nationals.² In 2024, 9,009 asylum seekers applied for IP, corresponding to a 52% decrease compared to the previous year, when 19,007 asylum seekers applied for IP.³

The following **Figure 1** shows the trend of Syrian refugees under TP and IP applicants and status holders in Turkey over time. The number of Syrians increased steadily until 2021 but has since declined, reflecting returns, resettlements, or changing policies. Similarly, IP applicants peaked in 2018 but have been decreasing. These trends indicate shifts in Turkey's migration management, with a gradual reduction in protected populations likely influenced by return policies and geopolitical factors. The figures illustrate Turkey's evolving role as a key host country for refugees, particularly Syrians under TP. While the number of Syrian refugees increased until 2021, the recent decline suggests a shift in migration governance, possibly driven by intensified return policies, border controls, and changing domestic and geopolitical dynamics. Similarly, the drop in IP applicants indicates stricter asylum policies or fewer new arrivals. For a country like Turkey, which has positioned itself as both a transit and destination country, these trends reflect the challenges of long-term refugee management. The decline in protected populations suggests a policy shift toward return, resettlement, or reduced protection space, which aligns with Turkey's broader approach of balancing migration control with its international commitments.

Figure 1: Number of Syrians Under Temporary Protection and International Protection Applicants/Status Holders (2015-2024)

¹ UNHCR, "Türkiye", 2025. Available at: <https://reporting.unhcr.org/operational/operations/t%C3%BCrkiye#:~:text=T%C3%BCrkiye%20has%20been%20the%20largest,protection%20applicants%20and%20status%2Dholders>. (Accessed 2 February 2025).

² Ibid.

³ PMM, "International Protection". 31 December 2024. Available at: <https://en.goc.gov.tr/international-protection17> (Accessed 31 December 2024).

Source: Prepared by the authors based on PMM, “Temporary Protection”, 12 December 2024, Available at: <https://www.goc.gov.tr/gecici-koruma5638> (Accessed 12 December 2024); UNHCR, “Refugee Data Finder”, 2024a2024, Available at: <https://www.unhcr.org/refugee-statistics/download/?url=1M1Dak> (Accessed 3 December 2024).

Turkey's approach to return migration is shaped by a complex interplay of legal, political, and socio-economic factors, resulting in differential treatment of specific nationalities. This stratified approach is evident not only in entry procedures and legal statuses but also in return policies, particularly for Syrian and Afghan migrants, who are the major subject of this country report. The differentiated approach of Turkey's migration policies is immediately apparent in their reception and the legal statuses granted to Syrian and Afghan migrants. Turkey's territory access policies have also evolved differently for these two groups. For Syrians, Turkey implemented an open-door policy from 2011-2016, shifted to non-arrival (with limited access to territory) from 2016-19, and has focused on returns since 2019. Afghans, however, have faced a non-arrival policy since 1979, indicating a long-standing restrictive approach. Syrians are granted temporary protection (TP) based on the TP Regulation (2014, #6883)⁴. In contrast, Afghans are eligible for International Protection (IP) based on the Law of Foreigners and International Protection (LFIP, 2013, #6458)⁵ but are mainly approached as irregular migrants. Indeed, the figures also reflect that Afghans are the top nationality of persons apprehended after an irregular border crossing, representing 27% of the total apprehension⁶; however, Syrians were the second highest nationality among the irregular arrivals, with 58,621⁷. This fundamental difference in legal status significantly impacts their rights, access

⁴ PMM, “Temporary Protection Regulation”, 2014. Available at: <https://www.goc.gov.tr/kurumlar/goc.gov.tr/Gecici-Koruma-Yonetmeligi-Ingilizce.pdf> (Accessed 22 September 2024).

⁵ PMM, “Law on Foreigners and International Protection”, 2013. Available at <https://en.goc.gov.tr/lfip> (Accessed 22 September 2024).

⁶ The apparent contradiction—Afghans being both the largest group of IP applicants and irregular migrants—stems from two factors: irregular entry (many Afghans arrive irregularly due to limited legal pathways) and rejections and status loss (while some apply for IP to regularize their status, high rejection rates push many backs into irregularity). Thus, Afghan irregularity results both from initial unauthorized entry and failed asylum claims, reflecting structural barriers in Turkey's asylum system.

⁷ Asylum Information Database (AIDA), “Cessation of Temporary Protection”, 2024. Available at: <https://asylumineurope.org/reports/country/turkiye/temporary-protection-regime/qualification-temporary-protection/cessation-temporary-protection/> (23 September 2024).

to services, and potential for return. The differentiation is visible from their entrain to the country to reception, protection, integration and, in particular, returns.

Regarding the legal framework, return types and practices also differ significantly between the two groups. Syrians fall under the TP regime, which does not allow specific and explicit safeguards against deportation. However, the effect of the non-refoulement principle is evident in individuals under TP in terms of deportation to their country of origin (Syria), as the very reason for these individuals to be protected under the TP is closely related to this principle. However, Syrians face pressures to return voluntarily, exacerbated by socio-economic difficulties and uncertainty surrounding their status. Afghans, on the other hand, are typically classified as irregular migrants, facing forced deportations and pushbacks, particularly at Turkey's eastern border with Iran. Afghans often do not have the same legal protections as Syrians, resulting in a precarious status and swift deportations.

For Syrians, there is a blurred line between voluntary and forced return. The “voluntary” returns of Syrians reached 792,624 by January 2025.⁸ These returns, however, raise concerns about their voluntariness due to economic pressures and the lack of long-term integration options in Turkey. On the other hand, Afghans face a much different scenario, with increased deportations in 2023, reaching a 146% increase compared to 2022.⁹ The deportation process is swift and often conducted without sufficient legal procedures.¹⁰ Afghans face pushbacks, forced returns, and assisted voluntary returns, with a significant increase in pushbacks since 2022.¹¹

This stratified approach results in differential treatment throughout the migration process, from entry to return, highlighting the complex interplay of factors shaping Turkey's migration policies. Turkey's return policy for Syrians and Afghans, framed by security concerns, domestic political pressures, and international obligations, has become increasingly focused on managing irregular migration through voluntary return and deportation. While Turkey has facilitated the return of hundreds of thousands of Syrians, concerns remain about the voluntariness of these returns and the human rights implications of deportations, especially for Afghans. The lack of transparency in return procedures, combined with anti-migrant sentiment and economic pressures, makes it challenging to ensure that returns are conducted under international standards of safety and dignity.

2. Methods

Research in this Work Package is carried out in an embedded-multiple case study design, in which cases are selected for diversity (encompassing variation in return types) and representativeness (including main host countries in return systems that are salient to Europe, i.e., Africa, the broader Middle East). This research adopts a qualitative approach to analyse Turkey's return and readmission policies for Syrians and Afghans, with a specific focus on pushbacks, forced removals, and assisted voluntary returns. Combining desk research with document analysis and in-depth fieldwork provides a comprehensive understanding. By integrating multiple data sources and perspectives, the methodology ensures a robust analysis that captures the return processes' legal and practical dimensions reflected by macro- and

⁸ PMM, “Statement from Minister of Interior, Ali Yerlikaya”, 10 January 2025a. Available at <https://x.com/Gocidaresi/status/1877677083066818701> (Accessed 4 October 2024).

⁹ TRT Haber, “Sınır dışı edilen düzensiz göçmen sayısı 21 bin 211'e ulaştı”, 13 March 2023. Available at: <https://www.trthaber.com/haber/gundem/sinir-disi-edilen-duzensiz-gocmen-sayisi-21-bin-211e-ulasti-752711.html> (Accessed 4 October 2024).

¹⁰ AIDA, Ibid. 2024.

¹¹ Ibid.

meso-level analyses. The methodology integrates comprehensive desk research with multi-sited fieldwork across several key locations in Turkey.

For the desk research component, data are generated through document analysis. The desk research component involved an extensive review of relevant documents, policies, and literature. A total of 117 documents covers three types of return in Turkey in general and in particular, returns of Syrians& Afghans) were selected for analysis, including government reports, legal documents, non-governmental organizations (NGO) reports, academic articles, and media publications. These documents were analysed using a code book specifically designed for the desk research component, ensuring systematic and consistent coding of information relevant to the return and readmission policies.

The fieldwork was conducted between January and May 2024 as a multi-sited with the meso-level analysis to capture the diversity and complexity of return migration governance in Turkey, which is shaped by legal, socio-political, and geographic factors. This methodology prioritizes a localized understanding of migration dynamics, focusing on key cities¹² such as Ankara, Gaziantep, Iğdir, Istanbul, and Van, which serve as critical hubs for migration governance and return logistics. This choice enables a nuanced examination of different return processes for Syrians and Afghans, highlighting variations in governance, infrastructure, and experiences across regions. On the other hand, city-level insights provide a granular understanding of migration practices and challenges, which enriches the national analysis. The role of border cities like Van and Iğdir illustrates the practical implementation of return policies, while larger urban centres like Istanbul highlight integration challenges and policy enforcement. This multi-site approach ensures a holistic understanding of Turkey's return migration governance, linking localized realities to broader national and international contexts. These locations were chosen due to their strategic importance in the context of migration and return practices in Turkey. Ankara and Istanbul host the headquarters or important offices of key institutional actors, and Istanbul is also a significant transit hub. On the other hand, Gaziantep, Van, and Iğdir are important border cities for Syrians and Afghans, and return policies related to these groups are located on the borders between Syria and Iran. As of 9 January 2025, the number of Syrians under TP in Gaziantep is 404,661, ranking the second city with a population of Syrians, while Istanbul is the first, with 501,578.¹³

In total, 36 semi-structured meso-level interviews (Ankara/6, İstanbul/ 3, Gaziantep/ 10, Van/ 13 and Iğdir/ 4) were conducted with key informants with state and non-state actors, including government officials, NGO representatives, legal experts, and community leaders. In addition to the interviews, observation visits were made to five temporary sites established following the 2023 earthquakes and currently hosting refugees. These sites are located in Gaziantep, Hatay, and Adiyaman provinces. The observation visits provided a first-hand look at the living conditions, facilities, and overall situation in these temporary shelters, offering valuable context to complement the interview data. Similarly, the physical conditions at the Turkey-Iran border were observed through the border village visits. Also, two focused group meetings were held in January 2024 with over 20 participants, including legal experts, practitioners, and scholars from the selected cities and in May 2024 with the Syrian and Afghan NGOs. These focus groups facilitated a detailed discussion on returns, administrative detention issues, and appeal processes and provided the perspectives of the concerned populations. The insights gained from this meeting were instrumental in understanding the broader legal and practical challenges associated with return policies.

¹² Some relevant meso level interviews from Izmir, in particular for the operations and practices are also benefited for the report.

¹³ PMM, "Temporary Protection", 9 January 2025. Available at: <https://en.goc.gov.tr/temporary-protection27> (Accessed 10 January 2025).

The data analysis employed two code books to capture Turkey's full complexity of return migration governance. The first codebook, derived from the WP4 guidelines and initial literature review, was used for desk research. As the fieldwork progressed, a second codebook was developed tailored to the meso-level interviews due to the field's context-specific themes and operational realities. Both codebooks were applied using Nvivo 14 software, ensuring systematic and rigorous analysis.

Research has been subject to ethical review of the host institutions of the individual researchers conducting the country-specific research. The ethics committee approval for the research was granted by Özyeğin University, which conducted the Turkey-based studies of the GAPs Project in collaboration with the Swedish Research Institute.¹⁴ The Ethics Committee Decision was obtained on 26.04.2023 with the approval code "2023/07/07." Regarding the interviews, the oral consent of respondents is obtained, and the anonymity and untraceability of respondents are ensured.

3. Context

3.1. Initial drivers of outmigration from Turkey

The initial drivers of outmigration from Turkey, particularly for Syrians and Afghans, are multifaceted and rooted in various socio-economic, legal, political, and security-related factors. For both Syrians and Afghans, political instability and ongoing conflict in their home countries have been primary drivers of migration to Turkey and subsequent attempts to migrate onward to Europe and other destinations. The Syrian Civil War, which began in 2011, resulted in widespread violence, destruction of infrastructure, and severe humanitarian crises, forcing millions to flee their homes in search of safety and stability. This has exacerbated an already dire situation marked by insecurity, economic instability, and human rights abuses. According to the Gallup survey conducted in 2022, 53% of Afghans want to leave their country, and Turkey is their top favourite destination for Afghan potential migrants (25%), followed by Germany (12%) and Canada (7%).¹⁵ According to another research conducted in Istanbul, Trabzon and Konya provinces of Turkey, where large numbers of Afghan migrants are living, 94% of Afghan migrants entering Turkey illegally through Iran's border due to security (48%), economic (36%), political (12%) and religious (3%) reasons.¹⁶

Economic factors play a significant role in driving outmigration from Turkey. Both Syrian and Afghan refugees face substantial economic challenges, which prompt them to seek better opportunities elsewhere. Despite efforts by the Turkish government and international organizations to integrate refugees into the labour market, many Syrians and Afghans find it difficult to secure stable and sufficient employment. Based on the meso-level and micro-level interviews (can be seen from the WP7 Report of the GAPs Project¹⁷), informal employment,

¹⁴ Since the Swedish Research Institute is headquartered in Stockholm, it was jointly decided that the ethics committee approval from the said university would be necessary and sufficient for the research to be conducted in Turkey.

¹⁵ Gallup News, "Taliban Returns, Majority of Afghans Seek an Exit", 4 April 2022. Available at: <https://news.gallup.com/poll/391499/taliban-returns-majority-afghans-seek-exit.aspx> (Accessed 30 September 2024).

¹⁶ Jafar Pouya, "The Causes of Afghan Immigration to Türkiye", *Journal of Middle East and Migration Studies*, 30 December 2022. Available at: <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/download/article-file/2594323> (Accessed 30 September 2024)

¹⁷ Susan B. Rottman vd., "Return Aspirations and Trajectories of Migrants: WP7 Country Dossier Turkey" in *GAPs: Decentring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond*, 2024. DOI:10.5281/zenodo.14606405. Available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/14606405> (Accessed 12 February 2025).

low wages, and poor working conditions are common, leading to economic instability and further migration.

Social integration challenges significantly contribute to refugee outmigration from Turkey. Refugees frequently encounter difficulties integrating into Turkish society due to cultural, linguistic, and social barriers.

In addition, legal and residency issues are critical. Uncertainties related to legal status and residency rights can also drive outmigration. While Turkey has provided TP status to Syrians, the long-term prospects of permanent residency or citizenship remain uncertain for many. Similarly, Afghan refugees often face precarious legal statuses, making their stay in Turkey insecure and prompting onward migration.

Turkey's evolving return and readmission policies, aimed at managing the large refugee population and addressing irregular migration, create an environment of uncertainty for many refugees. Policies that include voluntary and involuntary returns to countries of origin or third countries can act as a push factor, encouraging refugees to move to countries where they perceive more stability and security.¹⁸

3.2. Arrival and Reception in Turkey

3.2.1. Arrival and Reception in Turkey for Syrian Migrants

The Syrian Civil War, which started in 2011, has caused one of the largest displacement crises globally, with more than 12 million Syrians forcibly displaced.¹⁹ Within this dire situation, approximately six million Syrians have sought asylum in neighbouring countries. Turkey, sharing a border with Syria, became a primary destination for many of these Syrians. This section outlines the key phases and policies in Turkey's approach to managing the influx of Syrians, marked by an evolving response influenced by humanitarian, political, and security considerations. As illustrated in **Table 1**, the authors divided Turkey's policies towards Syrians into four phases to ease the reflection of general trends and policy developments.

Table 1: General Trend and Policy Developments in Turkey's Migration Management

Period	Securitization	Economization	Registration Policy	Policy Acts
2011-2013	No	No	Yes, under temporary protection	Open door policy
2014-2016	Yes/No	Yes	Yes, under temporary protection	Partial open-door policy

¹⁸ Kathleen Newland and Brian Salant, "Balancing Acts: Policy Framework for Migration Return and Reintegration", *Migration Policy Institute*, 2018, Available at: https://www.migrationpolicy.org/sites/default/files/publications/GlobalCompact-Returning%20Migrants_FinalWeb.pdf; Zeynep Sahin-Mencütek and Anna Triandafyllidou, "Coerced return: formal policies, informal practices and migrants' navigation", *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 51(2), 2024; IOM, "Return Migration". 10 September 2024, Available at: [https://www.migrationdataportal.org/themes/return-migration?](https://www.migrationdataportal.org/themes/return-migration?https://www.migrationdataportal.org/themes/return-migration?)

¹⁹ UNDP and UNHCR, "3RP Regional Strategic Overview 2024", 2024. Available at: <https://data.unhcr.org/en/documents/details/107046> (Accessed 17 May 2024).

2016-2019	Yes	Yes	Yes, with measures to regularize the province of registration	Non-arrival policy
2019-2023	Yes	Yes	Yes/No, closure of registration in 16 provinces and registration at the Temporary Accommodation Centres (TACs ²⁰)	Non-arrival and return policy

Source: Prepared by the authors based on the process of tracing and evolution of policy developments and the following sources²¹

The first period, between 2011 and 2013, started when the Turkish government pursued an open-door policy with the massive cross-border displacement of Syrians since mid-2011²², which was highly praised by the international community.²³ By October 2013, The UNHCR estimated that the number of Syrians seeking asylum in Turkey surpassed half a million. In late 2013 and early 2014, increased conflict and encroaching of the Islamic State in Iraq and Syria (ISIS) control saw a large wave of additional displacement to Turkey, primarily from Ar-Raqqa, as well as continued movements from Aleppo and Idlib provinces. During this time, Turkey instituted a partial tightening of border procedures as President Erdoğan confirmed that Turkey had reached one million Syrians in April of 2014. Due to proximity, most Syrians in Turkey came and still come from the northern governorates of Syria that border Turkey. With continued unrest and displacement, by the end of 2015, the PMM estimated there to be almost 2.75 million Syrians in the country. In 2016, Turkey began tightening its open-door policy for Syrians and implemented stricter border security.

Turkey's initially welcoming approach (*open-door policy*), when the first Syrians began arriving in 2011 was justified by the government as a temporary emergency response to a humanitarian crisis. In response to the arrival of people from Syria, and at considerable expense, Turkey enacted the LFIP in 2013, addressing the legal status and rights of foreigners in the country through asylum procedures and principles. The LFIP also set up a new civilian

²⁰ TACs initially were established as refugee camps or temporary accommodation facilities to host them, however, over the time government decided to decongest or close them due to the economic cost and also to support refugees' integration into the society; however then they become de-facto removal centers, because TACs were never dismantled, rather decongested.

²¹ N. Ela Gökalp Aras and Zeynep Şahin Mencütek, "The International Migration and Foreign Policy Nexus: The Case of Syrian Refugee Crisis and Turkey", *Migration Letters Syria Special Issue*, Migration Letters, Vol. 12, No. 3, 2015. Available at: <https://journal.tplondon.com/index.php/ml/article/view/502/404>; N. Ela Gökalp Aras and Zeynep Şahin Mencütek, "From Assertive to Opportunist Usage of Mass Migration: Turkey's Respond for the Syria Refugee Crisis", in *Turkish Migration Policy Book*, Ibrahim Sirkeci and Barbara Pusch (eds), London: Transnational Press London, 91-127, 2015; Ayhan Kaya, et. Al, *Türkiye'de Mültecilik: Koruma, Kabul ve Entegrasyon (Refugees in Turkey: Protection, Reception and Integration)*, Bilgi University Press, Istanbul, 2021. Available at: <https://bilgiyay.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/korumakabulveentegrasyon.pdf>; Zeynep Şahin Mencütek, et. al, *Syrian Refugees in Turkey: Between Reception and Integration*, Springer, IMISCOE Research Series, 2021; Available at: <https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-3-031-27366-7>

²² N. Ela Gökalp Aras and Zeynep Şahin Mencütek, Ibid, 2015; N. Ela Gökalp Aras and Zeynep Şahin Mencütek, "From Assertive to Opportunist Usage of Mass Migration: Turkey's Respond for the Syria Refugee Crisis", in *Turkish Migration Policy Book*, Ibrahim Sirkeci and Barbara Pusch (eds), London: Transnational Press London, 2016, 91-127; Zeynep Şahin Mencütek, "The Institutionalization of Voluntary Returns in Turkey", *Migration and Society*, 2023, Available at: <https://www.berghahnjournals.com/view/journals/migration-and-society/5/1/arms050105.xml> (Accessed 17 May 2024).

²³ Seçil E. Ertorer, "Asylum Regimes and Refugee Experiences of Precarity: The Case of Syrian Refugees in Turkey", *Journal of Refugee Studies*, 2021, Available at: <https://academic.oup.com/jrs/article/34/3/2568/6135664> (Accessed 17 May 2024).

agency, the Directorate General of Migration Management (DGMM, later the Presidency of Migration Management, PMM).

The second period, between 2014 and 2016, saw the Turkish government adopt a more restrictive policy. Turkish government enacted the TPR in 2014 to protect Syrians against refoulement, safeguarding their right to stay and access to education, health, social services, and work permits. The same period also witnessed revisiting the unconditional open-door policy to slow down access to the territory. However, it must also be underlined that there was no change in the narratives of Turkish officials regarding the open-door policy from 2014 through 2016, as evidenced by the Ministry of Foreign Affairs (MFA)'s April 2016 statement²⁴, the shift to the closed-door policy was observed in practice through a stricter border security strategy. In 2015, Turkey also started building a 911-km length border wall with Syria to combat smuggling and illegal migration.

The third period, between 2016 and 2019, has seen another shift from a *partial open-door policy* to a *non-arrival policy*, where the Turkish policymakers lined towards finding solutions within Syria, such as delivering aid shipments to a border crossing, establishing cross-border camps and working on safe zone alternatives to reduce the mass displacement of Syrians into Turkey.²⁵ Thus, the return of Syrians appeared visible on the agenda of the Turkish authorities at that time. In 2016, after years of an open-door policy and after having introduced integration policies, officials increasingly began to talk about the return. This constituted a U-turn that possibly matched Turkey's changing public opinion, the tensions between native populations and Syrians, the country's degrading economy and the highly tense election period. It seemed that the government realized that the stay of Syrians in Turkey would have a political and social cost and consequently changed its rhetoric.²⁶ The period of non-arrival policy was also significantly influenced by the coup attempt on 15 July 2016, when the political context of Turkey changed dramatically. A state of emergency was declared in July 2018, and Turkey tightened its border controls due to national security concerns, in particular, to prevent irregular escapes from the country.²⁷

Cross-border military operations in Northern Syria were another characteristic of this period. Turkey implemented three major military operations (in 2016, 2018, and 2019) that specifically aimed to prevent the formation of politically autonomous regions along the Turkish border controlled by the Kurdish-dominated YPG militants. The military operations, rooted in two geopolitical objectives - preventing a Kurdistan Workers' Party (PKK) -affiliated contiguous land corridor in Syria and mitigating mass migration by addressing in-country humanitarian needs - have stirred discussions about their legality under international humanitarian law.²⁸ Turkey's military operations in Northern Syria had implications for

²⁴ Ministry of Foreign Affairs, "No: 83, 3 Nisan 2016, Türkiye'nin Bazı Suriyelileri Zorla Ülkelerine Geri Gönderdiği İddiaları Hk.", 2016, Available at: https://www.MoFA.gov.tr/no_-83_-3-nisan-2016_-turkiye_nin-bazi-suriyelileri-zorla-ulkelerine-geri-gonderdigi-iddialari-hk_.tr.MoFA (Accessed 17 May 2024).

²⁵ Souad Ahmadoun, "Turkey's Policy toward Syrian Refugees: Domestic Repercussions and the Need for International Support", *German Institute for International and Security Affairs*, 2014, Available at: https://www.swp-berlin.org/publications/products/comments/2014C47_ahmadoun.pdf (Accessed 17 May 2024).

²⁶ Ahmet İçduygu and Maissam Nimer, "The politics of return: Exploring the future of Syrian refugees in Jordan, Lebanon, and Turkey", *Third World Quarterly*, 2019, Available at: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/01436597.2019.1675503> (Accessed 17 May 2024).

²⁷ N. Ela Gökalp Aras and Zeynep Şahin Mencütek, "Border Management and Migration Controls in Turkey", *RESPOND Project*, 2019, Available at: <https://respondmigration.com/wp-blog/border-management-migration-controls-turkey-report> (Accessed 17 May 2024).

²⁸ Umutcan Yüksel, "The Role of Infrastructure Investments in the Return of Syrian Refugees: The Case of Turkish Military Operations in Northern Syria", *GAPs: Decentring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond*, 9 January 2024, Available at: <https://www.returnmigration.eu/gapsblog/infrastructure-investments-return-syrian-refugees-turkish-military-operations-northern-syria> (Accessed 17 January 2025).

return. The official statements explicitly linked the operations to the repatriation of the over three million Syrians currently in Turkey back to Syria²⁹. Thus, these operations can be seen as the practices of the shift in Turkey's approach to Syrians and the increasing emphasis on "return policy".

The fourth period, between 2019 and 2023, is characterized by implementing security-focused migration practices and a significant shift of policy priorities to fight against irregular migration and return. The TPR has already required Syrians to stay in their province of registration to access rights and services, meaning that if a Syrian refugee were to leave their registered province without travel permission, they would lose access to TP services and rights and face the risk of detention. Since 2017, the EU has provided 92 million EUR in funding to UNHCR to support PMM through interpreters, supplementary staff, equipment, training and technical assistance for registering and verifying Syrians.³⁰ While until 2019, flexibility was in place in implementing the requirement of residence in the registration province, following the ruling party's (Justice and Development Party, AKP) defeat in the 2019 local elections, an emphasis on combatting irregular migration had become more evident when the government started stricter implementation of existing regulations. The presence of Syrians in major cities played a pivotal role in shaping the voting patterns of Turkish citizens, with the political losses being directly associated with the presence of migrants. Additionally, the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020 further restricted borders, severely limiting refugee mobility and access to essential livelihood opportunities.

In July 2019, the Istanbul Governorate issued a statement requiring all Syrians living in Istanbul without the required documents to return to their registered provinces. An extensive campaign of police surveillance led to the detention and return to registered provinces or refugee camps for thousands of Syrians in Istanbul³¹ and Bursa³². In November 2019, Minister of Interior Suleyman Soylu indicated that 190,000 Syrians and irregular migrants left Istanbul following the end of the grace period on 30 October.³³ In the same year, a set of amendments were made to the LFIP, which governs Turkey's migration and asylum regime. The amendments covered a wide range of issues, such as administrative detention, access to healthcare services, removal procedures, and using of ID documents for IP applicants. These changes in the LFIP aimed at diminishing Turkey's attractiveness for potential irregular migrations by tightening asylum procedures, limiting access to healthcare and punishing facilitators of irregular residence.³⁴ Considering the stricter implementation of the existing legislation since the Istanbul measure, this amendment indicates the Turkish government's migration policy shift.

²⁹ Hürriyet Daily News, "Afrin operation close to 'victory': Erdoğan", 2018, Available at: <https://www.hurriyetdailynews.com/afrin-operation-close-to-victory-erdogan-127475> (Accessed 17 May 2024).

³⁰ Directorate-General for Neighbourhood and Enlargement Negotiations, "Strategic Mid-Term Evaluation of the Facility for Refugees in Turkey (2016-2019/20)", *European Commission*, 2021, Available at: https://neighbourhood-enlargement.ec.europa.eu/strategic-mid-term-evaluation-facility-refugees-turkey-2016-201920_en (Accessed 17 May 2024).

³¹ Istanbul Governorate, "Düzensiz Göçle Mücadele İle İlgili Basın Açıklaması", 2019, Available at: <http://www.istanbul.gov.tr/duzensiz-gocle-mucadele-ile-ilgili-basin-aciklamasi> (Accessed 18 May 2024).

³² Bursa Governorate, "Basın Açıklaması", 2019, Available at: http://www.bursa.gov.tr/kurumlar/bursa.gov.tr/Duyuru/2019/_GOC/Son-guncellenmis-hali- Il-Goc-Mudurlugu_nden-gelen_.pdf (Accessed 18 May 2024).

³³ Karar, "İçişleri Bakanı Soylu: İstanbul'dan 190 bin mülteci ayrıldı", 2019, Available at: <https://www.karar.com/icisleri-bakani-soylu-istanbuldan-190-bin-multeci-ayrildi-1375374> (Accessed 18 May 2024).

³⁴ Mülteci-Der, "Ortak Değerlendirme: Yabancılar ve Uluslararası Koruma Kanunu'nda Yapılması Öngörülen Değişiklikler", 2019. Available at: <https://multeci.org.tr/2019/12/04/ortak-degerlendirme-yabancilar-ve-uluslararasi-koruma-kanununda-yapilmasi-ongorulen-degisiklikler/> (Accessed 10 January 2025).

In 2022, the registration procedure for Syrians also changed, and they have been referred to temporary accommodation centres since 6 June 2022. Turkey changed its registration procedure for Syrians under TP by requiring new applicants to be referred to Temporary Accommodation Centres (TACs) instead of registering directly in urban areas. This marked a shift from the previous system, restricting mobility and increasing state control over new arrivals. Accordingly, Syrians seeking TP had to stay in designated TACs (e.g., Elbeyli, Harran, Nizip) before registration. Major cities like Istanbul, Ankara, and Gaziantep were closed to new registrations; thus, a restriction on urban registration started. Also, stricter verification was adopted, which enhanced biometric screening and introduced security checks. This policy shift made it harder for Syrians to register and settle, reinforcing Turkey's strategy of migration control and return facilitation. Turkey gradually reactivated previously closed temporary accommodation centres as a result of this policy shift. Specific TACs, such as Elbeyli in Kilis, Harran in Sanliurfa, and Nizip in Gaziantep, were designated as reception centres. In addition, stakeholders pointed out that "sweeping" operations take place in some of the country's main cities, in addition to the application of the "deconcentration³⁵" policy; these often result in mass arrests and deportations of Syrians. In the same year, the number of Syrians detained almost equalled that of Afghans for the first time in recent years. Stakeholders kept reporting that people who had been persuaded to sign a voluntary return form from removal centres came back to Turkey in 2022. The TPR provides a legal opportunity for re-arrivals, as the law stipulates that re-application will reactivate IDs. TPR provides this legal opportunity based on the discretion of the administration. Actually, the Regulation does not guarantee the activation of IDs. In practice, especially after the policy change on 6 June, people either cannot access registration or their applications are rejected, and they have to appeal against the decision.³⁶

Between 2019 and 2023, there has been an increase in anti-migrant discourse and some attacks against foreigners, notably against Syrians. On August 11, 2021, groups of Turkish residents attacked the workplaces and homes of Syrians in a neighbourhood in Ankara a day after a Syrian youth stabbed and killed a Turkish youth in a fight.³⁷ In the lead-up to general elections in spring 2023, opposition politicians have made speeches that fuel anti-refugee sentiment and suggest that Syrians should be returned to war-torn Syria³⁸. As a reaction to rising anti-refugee sentiment stroked by opposition parties and the society calling for the return of Syrians to war-torn Syria, President Erdoğan has promised to relocate at least 1 million Syrians in Turkish-controlled regions of northern Syria.³⁹ The TP scheme came under

³⁵ The deconcentration policy in Turkey refers to measures aimed at reducing the visible presence of certain migrant groups, particularly Syrians under TP (Temporary Protection), in specific urban areas. This policy operates through a combination of relocation efforts, enforcement operations, and restrictions on residence registrations, particularly in cities with high concentrations of Syrians. One of the primary mechanisms of deconcentration is the relocation of migrants from densely populated areas to less visible or less politically sensitive locations, often through enforcement measures. As the excerpt suggests, "sweeping" operations—often conducted in major urban centres—serve to detain and deport irregular migrants or those deemed in violation of residency rules. This practice is particularly evident in the lead-up to elections when anti-migrant sentiment rises, and political pressures intensify. The policy is thus closely tied to migration governance and securitization strategies, ensuring that large groups of migrants do not become politically salient or visibly concentrated in key cities, especially in contexts where their presence might fuel public discontent or political opposition. In the broader migration governance framework, deconcentration can be seen as an instrument of spatial and demographic management, shaping not only the legal status of migrants but also their physical visibility in the urban landscape.

³⁶ AIDA, "2022 Update AIDA Country Report: Türkiye", 14 July 2023, Available at: <https://ecre.org/2022-update-aida-country-report-turkiye/> (Accessed 18 May 2024).

³⁷ BBC, "Turkish capital reels from violent protests against Syrians", 2021, Available at: <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-europe-58185612> (Accessed 18 May 2024).

³⁸ Soner Cagaptay, "Growing Anti-Syrian Sentiment in Turkey", *The Washington Institute for Near East Policy*, 2019, Available at: <https://www.washingtoninstitute.org/policy-analysis/growing-anti-syrian-sentiment-turkey> (Accessed 18 May 2024).

³⁹ Presidency of Turkey Republic, "Cumhurbaşkanı Erdoğan'ın, İdlib Briket Evleri açılışına gönderdiği video mesaj", 2022, Available at: <https://x.com/tcbestepe/status/1521429496355819520> (Accessed 18 May 2024).

scrutiny as anti-refugee rhetoric increased. Turkey announced in August 2022 that 517,000 Syrians had safely and voluntarily returned to Syria, and at least 70% of the TP beneficiaries are ready to return.⁴⁰ However, UNHCR stated that mass returns to Syria are unlikely to happen in the near future.⁴¹

The year 2023 was marked by the devastating earthquakes in southern Turkey, which left 3.3 million homeless across 11 provinces with a territory of 110,000 sq. km and a population of 15.6 million, where 1.7 million Syrians were registered in the affected.⁴² 339,931 Syrians moved to other provinces or Syria with temporary travel permits. Again, in 2023, the introduction of mobile migration points equipped with access to the GöçNet (Migration Management Database in Turkey) and advanced fingerprinting technologies marked a further evolution in managing migrants. Initially piloted in Istanbul with 100 MMPs and later expanded to 81 cities, this initiative aimed to streamline identifying and referring migrants with irregular status to Removal centres and Irregular Migrant Reception and Referral Centres (*Düzensiz Göçmen Kabul ve Sevk Merkezi-GÖKSEM*) for deportation processes. According to official reports, between 19 July 2023 and 20 September 2024, 1,581,027 migrants underwent these security checks, out of which 138,356 were reportedly irregular migrants.⁴³ In 2024, another round of address verification was applied, wherein law enforcement units conducted residence checks to verify the accuracy of addresses declared by migrants during their PDMM registration. Non-compliance due to absence, often because migrants were at work, triggered SMS notifications mandating a visit to Verification CentresCenters. Failure to comply resulted in deactivating their IDs, cutting off access to crucial social services. This practice has raised concerns about the practical implications of such stringent measures on the daily lives of migrants, as meso-level actors frequently mentioned them during fieldwork.

The following timeline (**Figure 2**) provides the most important developments regarding Syrians and their returns. The timeline highlights Turkey's shifting migration policies and the increasing external influences shaping its approach. The establishment of mobile migration units increased pressure on refugees, reinforcing Turkey's transition from a protection-oriented approach to a return-focused migration governance model. This evolution reflects a broader pattern shaped by domestic political shifts, EU agreements, and regional security concerns.

⁴⁰ NTV, "İçişleri Bakanı Süleyman Soylu NTV'de: Sığınmacıların yüzde 70'i dönmek istiyor", 2022, Available at: https://www.ntv.com.tr/turkiye/icisleri-bakani-suleyman-soylu-ntvde-siginmacilarin-yuzde-70i-donmek-istiyor.fG2dm_UEZEmxK9u5LDipSA (Accessed 10 January 2025)

⁴¹ AIDA, Ibid., 14 July 2023.

⁴² UNDP, "One year after Türkiye's earthquakes, recovery takes many forms", 5 February 2024, Available at: <https://reliefweb.int/report/turkiye/one-year-after-turkiyes-earthquakes-recovery-takes-many-forms> (Accessed 18 May 2024).

⁴³ AHaber, "İçişleri Bakanı Ali Yerlikaya'dan A Haber'e Özel Açıklamalar", 26 September 2024, Available at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vvCTLIDWJxQ> (Accessed 30 Sep 2024).

Figure 2: Timeline of Syrian Return Migration

Source: Prepared and designed by the authors

3.2.2. Arrival and Reception in Turkey for Afghan Migrants

Unlike Syrians, the arrival of Afghans to Turkey has a longer history. This situation progressed in parallel with the developments, especially in Afghanistan. It is possible to discuss Afghan migration in 5 periods: i) 1979-1989, ii) 1989-1996, iii) 1996-2001, iv) 2001-2021, and v) after 2021 to the present day.⁴⁴ However, this report focuses on the period after 2015. Because 2015 was a severe breaking point that shaped states' migration policies. As of December 2015, more than 911,000 refugees and migrants had arrived on European shores since the year began, and some 3,550 lives had been lost during the journey, while over 75 per cent of those arriving in Europe had fled conflict and persecution in Syria, Afghanistan or Iraq.⁴⁵ A record 1.3 million migrants applied for asylum in the 28 member states of the EU, Norway and Switzerland in 2015 – nearly double the previous high water mark of roughly 700,000 that was set in 1992 after the fall of the Iron Curtain and the collapse of the Soviet Union, according to a Pew Research Centre analysis of data from Eurostat, the EU's statistical agency.⁴⁶ According to Eurostat data, 406,025 Afghans were found to be illegally presented in 27 EU countries in 2015, while this number dropped to 148,640 in 2016. Between 2017 and 2020, the average number of Afghan migrants found to be illegally presented in 27 EU countries was 39,980, while another increase was observed in 2021, with 60,475 Afghan migrants and 114,475 in 2022. Similarly, according to the UNHCR's refugee data finder, number of Afghan asylum seekers in Turkey was 33,108 in 2014, while a drastic increase to 90,156 was observed in 2015. As of 2023, 106,241 Afghan asylum seekers are recorded in the country.⁴⁷ According to the official statistics, at the end of 2023, 13,068 applications were registered for Afghans.⁴⁸

The 2015 crisis, especially in 2018, is an important breaking point regarding Turkey's Afghan return policies. That year, there was a radical increase in the number of irregular Afghan immigrants, an increase of more than 100% compared to the previous year. That year, for the first time, Afghans outnumbered Syrians in the number of irregular migrants apprehended.⁴⁹ The new approach and implementations were introduced in light of the above-mentioned dramatic change/significant increase in numbers. At this point, according to Talwasa,⁵⁰ the easiest solution for the government was to send the asylum seekers back to their homes without investigating whether their conditions required close IP as refugees. Between January and June 2018, Turkey sent 17,000 Afghans to Afghanistan through “voluntary return”; however, the voluntary character of these returns is highly criticized. According to Amnesty International (AI), Afghan refugees were misled or coerced into signing documents they could not understand and were sent back.⁵¹

⁴⁴ Ahmad Walid Barlas, “Population Movements in Afghanistan: A Historical Overview, Migration Trends under the Taliban Regime, and Future Outlooks”, 2022, *MPRA Paper*, No. 114179, University Library of Munich, Germany.

⁴⁵ William Spindler, “2015: The year of Europe's refugee crisis”, 8 December 2015, UNHCR Stories, available at: <https://www.unhcr.org/news/stories/2015-year-europes-refugee-crisis> (Accessed 29 May 2024).

⁴⁶ Pew Research Center, “Number of Refugees to Europe Surges to Record 1.3 Million in 2015”, 2 August 2016, available at: <https://www.pewresearch.org/global-migration-and-demography/2016/08/02/number-of-refugees-to-europe-surges-to-record-1-3-million-in-2015/> (Accessed 29 May 2024).

⁴⁷ UNHCR, “Number of Afghan asylum seekers in Turkey”, 31 December 2023, Available at: <https://www.unhcr.org/refugee-statistics/download/?url=Jm4gfG> (Accessed 30 September 2024)

⁴⁸ PMM, “Temporary Protection”, 10 October 2024. Available at: <https://en.goc.gov.tr/temporary-protection27> (Accessed 17 October 2024).

⁴⁹ PMM, “Yakalananan Düzensiz Göçmenlerin Uyruk Dağılımı”, 2024a, Available at: <https://www.goc.gov.tr/duzensiz-goc-istatistikler> (Accessed 24 May 2024).

⁵⁰ Sanaa Talwasa, “Seeking a “Better Life” in Turkey: Afghan Refugees’ International Human Rights Condition in Turkey,” *Üsküdar Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, sayı: 11, Kasım 2020.

⁵¹ Amnesty International (AI), “Turkey: Thousands of Afghans swept up in ruthless deportation drive”, 24 April 2018, available at: <https://www.amnesty.org/en/latest/news/2018/04/turkey-thousands-of-afghans-swept-up-in-ruthless-deportation-drive/> (Accessed 22 May 2024).

In this process, the Ministry of Interior (MoI) began to increase security measures at the border. Between 2019 and 2023, Turkey built 230 km of security walls and patrol roads, and a total of 1,160 km of security walls were completed.⁵² In addition, 341 electro-optical towers, 284 thermal cameras (dragon-eyes), and 139 armoured border surveillance vehicles were procured with EU funds and delivered to the relevant border forces.⁵³

During the same period parallel to the construction of border walls at the Turkey -Iran border, Turkey started constructing a wall on its Iranian border in 2019. The wall was extended along the southern and eastern borders, and in 2021, trenches and wire fences were added. The number of watchtowers and police stations also increased, and the border was controlled with technological devices, including surveillance by uncrewed aerial vehicles (UAVs). Turkey's borders with Iran were announced to be protected by integrated border systems such as security walls, patrol roads, surveillance vehicles and optical towers.⁵⁴ These measures on the Iranian border have turned the border into a shield against migrants. "Blocking" on the Turkish-Iranian border made entering and exiting the region often deadly. The irregular border crossings along the Iranian border continued to spark public outcries.⁵⁵

In 2020, one of the critical turning points in Turkey's migration management was experienced. On the night of February 28, 2020, 33 of the Turkish soldiers who were in operation in Idlib, Syria, lost their lives in the attacks. Such a high loss pushed Turkey to take a sudden reaction, and after the diplomatic traffic that lasted throughout the night, news emerged that 'Turkey will no longer prevent immigrants who want to cross to Europe'.⁵⁶ Hearing the news, thousands of migrants flocked to the Pazarkule border gate on the Turkey-Greece border and especially to the border villages of Edirne. At that time, the number of migrants crossing the border was regularly announced by the Minister of Internal Affairs, Süleyman Soylu. While it was announced that 36,776 immigrants crossed the border on the evening of February 29, 2020, it was announced that 130,469 immigrants crossed the border on the morning of March 3, 2020.⁵⁷ As seen in the field studies carried out by many local NGOs at that time, most of the migrants in the region were Afghans.⁵⁸ While some of the immigrants, mostly Afghans, crossed the border, the majority of them remained determinedly in the buffer zone where the Pazarkule border gate is located for about a month, despite the pushback and acts of violence implemented by Greece at the border.

⁵² PMM, "İçişleri Bakanı Ali Yerlikaya: "Düzensiz Göçmenlere ve Göçmen Kaçakçılığı Organizatörlerine Asla Geçit Vermiyoruz", 17 December 2023, Available at: <https://www.goc.gov.tr/icisleri-bakani-ali-yerlikaya-duzensiz-gocmenlere-ve-gocmen-kacakligi-organizatorlerine-asla-gecit-vermiyoruz> (Accessed 3 February 2025).

⁵³ PMM, Ibid., 17 December 2023; Republic of Türkiye Ministry of Interior, "2024-2028 Stratejik Planı", 2024, Available at: https://www.icisleri.gov.tr/kurumlar/icisleri.gov.tr/lcSite/strateji/raporlar/stratejik-planlar/ICISLERI_BAKANLIGI_2024_2028_STRATEJIK_PLANI.pdf (Accessed 22 May 2024).

⁵⁴ PMM, "Yılbaşından Bu Yana 8 Bin 571 Düzensiz Göçmen Sınır Dışı Edildi", 30 January 2023; available at: <https://www.goc.gov.tr/yilbasindan-bu-yana-8-bin-571-duzensiz-gocmen-sinir-disi-edildi> (Accessed 22 May 2024).

⁵⁵ AIDA, Ibid., 2024.

⁵⁶ Orhan Coşkun and Ezgi Erkoyun, "Turkey says will not stop Syrian refugees reaching Europe after troops killed", 28 February 2020, *Reuters*, available at: <https://www.reuters.com/article/idUSKCN2oMoHo/> (Accessed 28 May 2024).

⁵⁷ Süleyman Soylu (@suleymansoylu), "Saat 21.02 itibarıyla Edirne üzerinden ülkemizden ayrılan göçmen sayısı; 36.776", 29 February 2020. Available at: <https://x.com/suleymansoylu/status/1233819814428389376> (Accessed 29 May 2024); Süleyman Soylu (@suleymansoylu), "Saat 09.15 itibarıyla Türkiye topraklarından ayrılıp Edirne'den Yunanistan'a geçen göçmen sayısı; 130.469", 3 March 2020. Available at: <https://x.com/suleymansoylu/status/1234730037326336003> (Accessed 29 May 2024).

⁵⁸ Hakan Ünay, "Düzensiz Göçmenlerin Sınırı Geçme Deneyimleri ve Kararlılıklarının Analizi: Pazarkule Sınır Kapısı Örneği", *Göç Araştırmaları Vakfı*, October 2020, available at: <https://gocvakfi.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/GAV-RAPOR-Hakan-Ünay-1.pdf> (Accessed 29 May 2024); SGDD-ASAM, "Edirne-Pazarkule Müdahalesi Raporu", 2020, available at: <https://sgdd.org.tr/yayinlar/sgdd-asam-edirne-rapor-tr.pdf> (Accessed 29 May 2024).

According to the report of the Hak İnisiyatifi, as of March 17, the authorities made announcements stating that they would evacuate the area by March 18 due to the suspicion of COVID-19 and that tonight would be the last day and migrants with a residence permit or an official document replacing it came to the cities with free buses, while those have been stated that there are rumours that those without papers will be sent to Kilis.⁵⁹ A month later, due to the spread of COVID-19 in Turkey, migrants in the region were sent to various cities in Turkey. This process led Turkey to centre and instrumentalize migrants in its diplomacy with the EU.⁶⁰ As a diplomatic blackmail for Europe, Turkey announced it would no longer prevent migrants from crossing into Europe, using migration as leverage against the EU. This move was a response to Europe's lack of support for Turkey's military operations in Idlib, where Ankara had sought stronger backing against the Syrian regime. By opening its borders, Turkey signalled frustration with the EU-Turkey Statement, which had placed the burden of migration control on Ankara in exchange for financial aid. Turkish authorities facilitated migrant movement to the Pazarkule border, creating political and humanitarian pressure on Greece and the EU. This calculated action aimed to force Europe to provide greater financial aid, diplomatic support, and recognition of Turkey's strategic role in migration governance.

Especially after 2018, Turkey started working on the return programme and border security. The ICMPD has become one of the critical actors in Turkey's return policies. ICMPD Turkey has been working with the PMM to establish a National Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration System (N-AVRR) mechanism in 2021. On 5 March 2021, Turkey's NAVRR reached a milestone with the assisted voluntary return of 44 Afghan irregular migrants from Istanbul to Kabul through a pilot implementation of the national mechanism.⁶¹

The main factor that caused Turkey to prioritize return policies is the increase in Afghan migration to Turkey. Seven years after Barack Obama announced withdrawal from Afghanistan in 2014, the US has completely withdrawn from Afghanistan.⁶² By August 2021, the Taliban had swept back into power. Their swift offensive came as the US withdrew its remaining troops from Afghanistan as outlined in a 2020 peace agreement with the group.⁶³ On August 30, 2021, the US announced that the withdrawal of US forces from Afghanistan was completed. During the 18-day withdrawal period, 123,000 people were evacuated.⁶⁴

Following the Taliban takeover of Afghanistan, the Turkish authorities declared their opposition to admitting potential large numbers of Afghans to Turkey, with President Recep Tayyip Erdoğan reportedly warning that the country would not become "Europe's migrant storage unit". Elections for June 2023 have increased pressure on the government to adopt a stricter policy on immigration, and the government has been putting tougher border control measures in place. In April 2022, Turkish authorities announced that a 191 km-long wall at the border with Iran had been completed and that it would be extended to 295 km by 2023.

⁵⁹ Hak İnisiyatifi, "Türkiye-Yunanistan Sınırı Göçmen Krizi Raporu", 19 March 2020, available at: https://hakinisiyatifi.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/edirneraporv3_2-min.pdf (Accessed 29 May 2024).

⁶⁰ N. Ela Gökalp Aras, "The European Union's Externalisation Policy in the Field of Migration and Asylum: Turkey as a Case Study", *Report Multilevel Governance of Mass Migration in Europe and Beyond Project (#770564, Horizon2020) Working Paper Series*, 2021, Available at <https://www.respondmigration.com/wp-blog/> (Accessed 29 May 2024).

⁶¹ ICMPD, "Factsheet: Supporting the Development of Return Counselling Capacities in Turkey (ReConnect)", 11 June 2021, https://www.icmpd.org/file/download/53505/file/EN_ReConnect_Factsheet.pdf (Accessed 29 May 2024).

⁶² The White House, "U.S. Withdrawal from Afghanistan", 2021, <https://www.whitehouse.gov/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/US-Withdrawal-from-Afghanistan.pdf> (Accessed 29 May 2024).

⁶³ Lindsay Maizland, "The Taliban in Afghanistan", Council on Foreign Relations, 19 January 2023, <https://www.cfr.org/backgrounder/taliban-afghanistan> (Accessed 29 May 2024).

⁶⁴ Fatih Yumuşakbaş, "ABD askerleri 2 yıl önce Afganistan'dan çekildi", *TRT Haber*, 30 August 2023, Available at: <https://www.trthaber.com/haber/dunya/abd-askerleri-2-yil-once-afganistandan-cekildi-791942.html> (Accessed 29 May 2024).

According to Turkey's Minister of Interior, the EU is providing financial support of 110 million EUR for the construction of the wall.⁶⁵

Turkey continues to increase its capacity regarding return policies. The capacity of the removal centres affiliated with the Ministry is 22,140 as of 2023.⁶⁶ While the increase rate in voluntary and safe returns was 15% planned in 2022 compared to the previous year, it was 40%. While there was a 30% increase in 2023 compared to last year, the 2024 and 2025 targets are a 20% increase compared to the previous year. While the 2022 target for the number of foreigners deported is 53,000, 90,000 were deported in 2022. It plans to deport 50,000 foreigners annually in 2023, 2024 and 2025.⁶⁷

The following timeline (**Figure 3**) provides the significant developments regarding Turkey's policy towards Afghans and their returns. It reflects how conflict, geopolitical shifts, and migration governance have shaped displacement. Repeated cycles of war and regime changes have driven Afghan migration, with Turkey emerging as a key transit and host country. Initially allowing movement, Turkey has increasingly prioritized securitization, border control, and deportations, aligning with regional and EU externalization policies. Recent policies focus on containment rather than protection, with intensified security measures and deportation practices, particularly along the Iranian border. As Afghanistan's conditions deteriorate, the pressure on Afghans to return raises concerns about the voluntariness of return and the broader consequences of restrictive migration policies.

⁶⁵ AI, Ibid., 24 April 2018.

⁶⁶ PMM, Göç İdaresi Başkanlığı 2023 Performans Programı, 2023, available in Turkish at: <https://www.goc.gov.tr/kurumlar/goc.gov.tr/Kurumsal/Strateji/2023-Mayis-/Performans-Raporu-29032023.pdf> (Accessed 2 May 2024).

⁶⁷ PMM, Ibid., 2023.

Figure 3: Timeline of Afghan Return Migration

Source: Prepared and designed by the authors; thus, the report needs to be cited.

3.3. Social, Economic and Political Conditions

Turkey has faced significant social, economic, and political challenges in managing the high number of migrant presences, leading to a complex landscape that affects return migration. Public sentiment towards migrants has increasingly soured, driven by perceptions that they burden the economy and public services. Integration challenges, including language barriers, cultural differences, and restricted access to social services, further exacerbate social tensions. Government policies requiring refugees to remain in their province of registration, alongside address verification exercises and neighbourhood closures, have compounded these issues.

Economically, the presence of Syrian refugees is seen as a strain on Turkey's resources, intensifying competition for jobs, housing, and social services in an already struggling economy. The Turkish government has invested heavily in infrastructure, including a border wall and temporary accommodation centres, to manage the refugee population, but the financial burden remains substantial despite international aid. Employment opportunities for migrants are mostly in the informal sector, limiting their ability to achieve economic stability. The COVID-19 pandemic has worsened their economic situation, with many refugees losing jobs and facing increased financial insecurity.

Politically, Turkey's migration policies have evolved from an open-door approach to more restrictive measures. Initially praised for its humanitarian response, Turkey later implemented the TPR and tightened border security, influenced by the 2016 EU-Turkey Statement that sought to stem refugee flows to Europe in exchange for financial support. Turkey's military operations in northern Syria aimed to prevent the formation of Kurdish autonomous regions and address humanitarian needs within Syria, aligning with broader geopolitical goals and facilitating refugee returns. Political rhetoric, especially before the 2023 general elections, has increasingly focused on return, with opposition parties pushing for stricter policies.

In recent years, Turkey has hosted a significant number of Afghan irregular migrants, especially from 2018 to following the Taliban's takeover of Afghanistan in 2021. This increased rate since 2021 has brought about notable social dynamics and reactions within the country. Initially, humanitarian acceptance experienced by Syrians did not happen to Afghans, especially due to cultural differences, society's feeling of insecurity, and social tension, which increased with the influence of media news about Afghan migration. The cultural differences and integration issues between Afghan immigrants and the local population have caused friction, particularly in economically disadvantaged areas. These tensions have sometimes escalated into xenophobic sentiments and violence. The arrival of Syrians in 2011 significantly shaped Turkey's migration governance, initially prompting the establishment of the TP regime, which granted Syrians access to legal stay, healthcare, and education. However, this focus on Syrians led to a differentiation in how Afghans were treated, as they were categorized under the international protection framework, which provided fewer rights and a more precarious status. The preference for the TP model for Syrians highlighted a stratified approach, where non-Syrian groups, including Afghans, faced greater difficulties in obtaining protection and legal stability. Since 2015, the increasing arrival of Afghan migrants has further influenced the governance of Syrian refugees by reinforcing restrictive migration policies. The growing Afghan population coincided with Turkey's shift toward return-oriented policies, which affected both groups but particularly intensified measures against Afghans. The securitization of migration and border control, coupled with the pressure to manage large-scale migration flows, led to a more stringent asylum system. This shift has also fueled public debates and policy discussions about migration fatigue, impacting social acceptance and integration prospects for both Syrians and Afghans. In essence, while the Syrian mass migration initially shaped Turkey's migration policies, the subsequent rise in Afghan arrivals

has reinforced a more restrictive and security-driven approach, affecting the governance of all refugee groups in the country.

Social media has played a significant role in spreading misinformation and negative stereotypes about Afghan immigrants, further inflaming anti-migrant sentiments. Especially spreading rapidly on social media, videos of Afghans running in groups and crossing the Turkish border, with only young male Afghans, increased anti-migrant sentiment in society. According to the surveys, the most important issue on the agenda of the Turkish people is the problems in the economy, followed by the "refugee problem".⁶⁸ With the economic crisis in Turkey in recent years, inflation has become a factor that affects people's daily lives. Economic difficulties often accelerate the perception of immigrants as a threat to the public, and immigrants are almost seen as the cause of crises.⁶⁹ On the other hand, it is known that in times of economic crisis, immigrants mostly lose their jobs and experience difficulties in daily life due to the crisis.⁷⁰ While public pressure has indeed compelled the Turkish political elites to develop policies aimed at return, it is crucial to examine the role of politicians in shaping this public sentiment. Therefore, the relationship between political rhetoric and public opinion on migration in Turkey demonstrates a complex and multifaceted interplay.

After the 2019 municipal elections and during the 2023 general elections, the issue of migrant presence became a prominent topic in politicians' speeches and commitments. This focus was partly due to the mediatization of Afghan arrivals in Turkey, especially after the Taliban's takeover in 2021, and the growing negative public sentiment toward migrants. However, while politicians' language was responsive to public demand, their commitments regarding the return of migrants as an unwanted population also significantly influenced and reinforced public sentiment. This dynamic created a feedback loop: politicians used rhetoric that appealed to certain voter bases, convincing more of the public to adopt anti-migrant stances. Politicians then justified more restrictive policies as public opinion shifted, claiming they responded to public demand. This cycle has led to an escalation of anti-migrant sentiment and increasingly harsh policies.

Politically, similar to European countries, Afghan migrants have become one of the main focuses of politics in Turkey. While this situation brought about the political instrumentalization of Afghan migrants, it also caused a rapid increase in social anti-immigration attitudes. As a result, immigrants began to experience social and economic difficulties, which became an important factor in the return of migrants.

The legal and institutional frameworks established by the LFIP and the restructuring of the DGMM into the PMM have been crucial in implementing these policies. These measures, while aimed at regulating refugee stay and movement, have also led to increased social tensions and challenges in integration.

The 2023 earthquakes further exacerbated these challenges, displacing 1.7 million Syrians within the affected areas and straining temporary accommodations.⁷¹ Living conditions in these temporary sites are severe, with issues related to hygiene, safety, and access to services. These factors collectively create a challenging environment for both the integration and

⁶⁸ M. Aydın, et. al, "Kantitatif Araştırma Raporu: Türkiye Siyasal Sosyal Eğilimler Araştırması 2022", *Kadir Has Üniversitesi*, ss.134, İstanbul, 2023, Global Akademi ve Akademetre.

⁶⁹ Boris Heizmann and Nora Huth, "Economic conditions and perceptions of immigrants as an economic threat in Europe: Temporal dynamics and mediating processes", 2021, *International Journal of Comparative Sociology*, 62(1), 56-82.

⁷¹ Umutcan Yüksel, "Impact of 2023 Earthquakes on Return Dynamics of Syrian Migrants in Türkiye: Observations from the Field", 10 June 2024, Available at: <https://www.returnmigration.eu/gapsblog/impact-of-2023-earthquakes-on-return-dynamics-of-syrian-migrants-turkiye> (Accessed 4 January 2025).

potential return of Syrian refugees, with significant implications for Turkey's social and political landscape.

4. Findings

4.1. Characteristics of return migration governance from Turkey to Syria and Afghanistan: Types and Scale of Returns

4.1.1. Types of Return

Based on Turkey's legal framework and practical applications, as well as the desk research and the fieldwork, three types of returns are observed concerning Syrians and Afghans: pushbacks, forced returns, and voluntary returns. Regarding the pushbacks, Turkey-Iran land borders in the east have seen significant interceptions and denial of access to territory, particularly since 2021, when the Taliban took over the power in Afghanistan and an increased flow of migrants was observed at the Turkey-Iran land borders. In terms of forced returns, administrative detention for returning and deportation exists, particularly targeting migrants who are in violation of LFIP (including irregular migrants, unregistered, involved in criminal activities, etc.). Turkey also has two main assisted voluntary return and integration programmes supported by IOM and ICPMD (the national programme is supported), particularly for non-Syrians. Finally, there are also "voluntary returns of Syrians" that are not spontaneous and are based on individual decisions. However, the legal framework exists for forced returns and voluntary returns, not pushbacks. Due to regularization deprivation and increased intimidation policies, criminalization practices have become increasingly more observable since 2019. Notably, in 2023, it has been claimed that the fine line between forced and voluntary return migration is becoming blurred, as reflected by the desk research and initial fieldwork findings.

4.1.1.1. *Types of Returns for Syrians*

The research reflected that among the three main return types, voluntary returns are the official policy for many refugees, particularly for Syrians. The meso-level respondents' statements underline coercion through poor living conditions, insecurity, legal pressure or intimidation in particular, particularly during administrative detention. The pushbacks were not reported by respondents did not report any pushback regarding Syria during the fieldwork. Thus, mainly two types of returns apply to Syrians in Turkey: Forced Removal (Intimidation, Administrative Detention and Deportation,) and Assisted Voluntary Return.

In terms of forced returns, Turkey enforces return migration through a legal and regulatory framework aligned with national laws and international agreements. The Law on Foreigners and International Protection (#6458, 2013, LFIP) is a cornerstone, setting out the procedures and conditions for returning foreigners in Turkey who are found to be staying irregularly or may not qualify for IP. The LFIP outlines procedures for deportation, voluntary return, and the rights and obligations of migrants and refugees within Turkish territory. Additionally, Syrian nationals, as well as stateless persons and refugees from Syria who came to Turkey due to events in Syria after 28 April 2011, are provided with TP by the Temporary Protection

Regulation (#2014/6883, 2014, TPR)⁷². The PMM is the government responsible for all asylum procedures in *Turkey*, including the temporary protection regime.

Under the LFIP, foreigners in Turkey may be subject to deportation (officially referred to as ‘removal’) for various reasons, including posing threats to public order, working without a permit, or violating entry and exit conditions. However, exemptions exist if there are serious indications of potential harm, such as the death penalty, torture, or inhuman treatment in their home country. Such protection from refoulement is also guaranteed under the TPR (Article 6); thus, Syrians under the TP regime are generally exempt from deportation to Syria due to the ongoing conflict therein.

Under the LFIP (No. 6458), Turkey enforces deportation procedures based on several legal grounds. Individuals receive a removal order deportation decision⁷³ under Article 54 of the LFIP when they are found to be staying irregularly, posing threats to public order, or engaging in illegal activities. The deportation decision may be issued when the individual is detained, arrested, or transferred to a removal centre, depending on the specific violation. According to Article 54(1)(b) of the LFIP, individuals who are members, supporters, or financiers of terrorist organizations or criminal groups may be subject to immediate deportation, even during asylum proceedings. Syrians under TP and Afghans under IP are required to reside in their registered province unless they obtain travel permits. If found in another province without authorization, they may be detained and face removal procedures (LFIP Article 54(1)(h)). Working without a permit, overstaying visas, or being convicted of crimes may also result in removal (LFIP Article 54(1) (d-f)). The process differs based on the legal status of the individual.

Article 55 of the LFIP provides an exemption from deportation for individuals who risk facing torture, inhuman treatment, or the death penalty in their home country, have severe health conditions or disabilities, or have family members dependent on them in Turkey. However, an emergency decree (October 2016) expanded deportation powers, allowing authorities to remove individuals before the completion of their asylum procedures if they are considered a threat to public order or national security. Not all detained persons are deported, not necessarily. Article 56 of the LFIP states that individuals detained for removal have the right to challenge their deportation order within seven days at administrative courts. Additionally, some detainees may have their deportation suspended due to the non-refoulement principle (LFIP Article 4; TPR Article 6).

The Amendment to the LFIP introduced significant changes concerning migration management, international protection, and deportation procedures. These amendments were primarily influenced by the EUTRS and aimed to strengthen migration control, particularly in response to increasing irregular migration and asylum applications. Concerning the focus of returns, the amendment expanded the scope of deportation decisions and allowed for faster expulsion of certain groups, such as individuals deemed a security risk, while the appeal period against a deportation decision was reduced from 15 days to 7 days.⁷⁴ Legal remedies became more restricted, making it harder for migrants to challenge their removal.⁷⁵ The Amendment

⁷² No: 2014/6883) dated 13/10/2014 was published in the framework of Article 91 of Law No. 6458 on Foreigners and International Protection (LFIP). Available at: <https://www.goc.gov.tr/kurumlar/goc.gov.tr/Gecici-Koruma-Yonetmeliği-İngilizce.pdf> (Accessed 1 April 2024).

⁷³ In Turkey, under the LFIP, a deportation decision (*Sınır Dışı Etme Kararı*) is issued by the PDMM. A removal order (*Sınır Dışı Etme Talimatı*) refers to the operational steps for implementation. Thus, within this report, ‘deportation decision’ is used.

⁷⁴ UNHCR, “Türkiye: Implementing Regulation No. 29656 of 2016, Law on Foreigners and International Protection”, 17 March 2016. Available at: <https://www.refworld.org/legal/decrees/natlegbod/2016/en/113662> (Accessed 19 February 2024).

⁷⁵ Ibid.

was to waive the automatic suspension effect on the deportation decisions. It made it possible to deport some foreigners (54/b, d, k reasons) even before the court gave its final decision regarding the deportation decision, but this was later amended and repealed due to the pilot decision (Y.T Decision) of the Constitutional Court. According to the LFIP, it is not possible to remove (execute the deportation decision for) applicants of IP before the final decision is given regarding their application (LFIP, art. 80/1/e). Thus, there are two different procedures: A deportation decision can be issued before the completion of refugee status determination (RSD); however, this decision cannot be executed (the person cannot be removed) before the final decision.

It should also be noted that returns occur via two main channels: Through PDMMs and removal centres. Syrians opting for voluntary return typically apply at PDMM offices, which issue travel permits for border crossings. If they are in one of the 12 provinces where UNHCR operates or at one of the five designated border points during working hours, UNHCR can monitor and verify the voluntariness of their return. In contrast, Syrians with irregular status often face a different process. When apprehended, they may be placed in removal centres or directly transferred to border crossings, frequently outside working hours, limiting UNHCR's ability to assess voluntariness. While implementation of the voluntary returns requires that an observer signs a voluntary return forms form in UNHCR's absence—typically a representative from the Turkish Red Crescent, the governorate's human rights committee, or pro-government, faith-based NGOs—this raises concerns about the legitimacy of voluntary consent.⁷⁶ However, the fieldwork reflects that a number of returns occur through removal centres or during non-working hours at border crossings, where UNHCR monitoring is not present. In these cases, there is a need for alternative observers (such as the Turkish Red Crescent or local NGOs) to sign voluntary return forms. There are concerns about the genuine voluntary nature of these returns, particularly when individuals face pressure from authorities and procedural safeguards are not efficiently followed.⁷⁷ This dual system makes it challenging to estimate the proportion of genuinely spontaneous or self-organized returns within the officially declared figures, especially for returns processed through removal centres or during hours when international monitoring is not available.

According to the AIDA report of 2023, Syrians have increasingly received removal orders under these rules since 2018.⁷⁸ This process begins with detention, which can trigger a lack of correct documents or public disorder. Many Syrians choose to leave their registered city without a travel permit, even though this places them further into illegality. This, in turn, increases the risk of detention and, consequently, deportation. Moreover, new legal bases for deportation, such as suspicion of terrorist activity, which can be loosely interpreted, affect not only the refugee's risk of being deported but also the experiences of those who live in fear of detention and deportation. The final step in the process is when Syrians are detained and transported to removal centres, where they are forced to sign a 'voluntary' return decision and are deported to Syria.⁷⁹

⁷⁶ The "Voluntary Return Request Form" is issued by the provincial governorship for Syrians under temporary protection who wish to return voluntarily. The process is monitored by international organizations and NGOs to ensure independent oversight. The form must be signed by a UNHCR representative; if unavailable, by a Red Crescent official. In their absence, it is signed by an NGO representative approved by the governorship or an official from the Human Rights and Equality Board. PMM, "Voluntary, Safe and Dignified Return", Available at: <https://en.goc.gov.tr/voluntary-safe-and-dignified-return> (Accessed 21 February 2024).

⁷⁷ Akkad v. Turkey, App No. 155719 (ECHR), 21.06.2022; Abdulkemim Hammud, App No. 2019/24388 (Turkish Constitutional Court), 2/5/2023; Ali Elhüseyin, App No. 2020/5730 (Turkish Constitutional Court), 12/6/2024.

⁷⁸ AIDA, Ibid., 2024.

⁷⁹ Sevda Tunaboylu, Ibid., 2024.

As the second type of return regarding Syrians, in line with international law, Turkey commits itself to voluntary, safe, and dignified principles for voluntary return.⁸⁰ Those who want to voluntarily return must apply to the PDMM office in their city of registration. They must complete a Voluntary Return Form and take a copy of it along with a travel permission document. In addition to Syrians themselves, there are three signatories of the voluntary return form:

- i. PDMM official,
- ii. Translator,
- iii. UNHCR⁸¹, the Turkish Red Crescent (TRC), and NGOs are deemed feasible by governorates or human rights committee members of the governorates, who have an observatory role concerning the voluntariness of the return of Syrians who wish to voluntarily return to Syria.

The LFIP regulates voluntary return under “support for voluntary return” under Article 87 (1), and beneficiaries of TP have the right to voluntarily return to Syria; “Material and financial support may be provided to those applicants and IP beneficiaries who would wish to voluntarily return”. According to paragraph 2 of the same article, the PMM (former DGMM), under the MoI, as the governmental authority responsible for overall migration and IP affairs in Turkey, is the accountable authority for carrying out voluntary repatriation activities in coordination with international organizations, public institutions, and civil society organizations. In the case of an organized large-scale repatriation operation, the Disaster and Emergency Management Presidency, responsible for emergency management and civil protection nationwide in Turkey (AFAD), takes over the responsibility from DGMM (later PMM) at the border crossings. At the provincial level, PDMM, district governorates, and law enforcement units, such as police, gendarmerie and border control authorities, are central to implementing return policies. NGOs such as the Association for Social Development and Aid Mobilization (ASAM), Cooperative for Assistance and Relief Everywhere (CARE), SENED, and international organizations like the UNHCR provide legal aid and protection services. UNHCR observes the voluntary nature of returns. In the absence of UNHCR, the TRC, the human rights committee of Gaziantep Governorate or NGOs found feasible by the governorate (such as Bulbulzade Foundation, Gaziantep Municipality Migrant Information Centre or INKA) involved in the observation of voluntariness.⁸²

At the time that this report is written since the situation in Syria is not conducive to voluntary return, there are no structured incentives for Syrians who would like to return. However, fieldwork confirms the presence of push (such as family reasons, COVID-19, socio-economic situation in Turkey, declining access to asylum and livelihoods, increased anti-refugee sentiment) and pull factors (such as Turkey’s military interventions in North-West and North-East Syria).⁸³ Additionally, incentive mechanisms such as allowing Syrians to make “go-and-see” visits to Syria during the Islamic holidays occurred between 2017 and 2022. The second incentive practice is the provision of logistical and information assistance to facilitate returns, which occurs at the local level with the coordination between municipalities and PDMM offices, targeting the most densely Syrian populated areas. Lastly, during the post-earthquake period, the migration-related authorities requested NGOs to inform them of those who wished to settle in prefabricated houses in Syria or those who wanted to return with 14,000 TRY

⁸⁰ PMM, “Voluntary, Safe and Dignified Return”, 2024b, Available at: <https://en.goc.gov.tr/voluntary-safe-and-dignified-return#:~:text=Voluntary%20return%20is%20the%20return,must%20be%20safe%20and%20dignified>. (Accessed 4 October 2024).

⁸¹ UNHCR monitors the voluntary return interviews conducted by PDMMs in 16 provinces. PDMMs are responsible for interviewing, counselling, and processing refugees’ applications to voluntarily return to Syria.

⁸² SRII WP4 Meso Level Interview, Gaziantep-07 (with a public representative)

⁸³ SRII WP4 Meso Level Interview, Gaziantep-01 (with an IGO representative)

support. There were also requests for NGOs to inform them of those who wanted this financial support.⁸⁴

With these forms signed, Syrians may freely travel to appropriate border crossing points. A border crossing point for voluntary return is determined upon the list of open and allowed crossing points, travel safety and the choice of the migrants. Once migrants arrive at the desired border crossing point, with their travel permission document and a signed copy of their voluntary return form, they may leave Turkey⁸⁵. Voluntary return means accepting the termination of the TP status⁸⁶ (including a V-87 restriction code to their respective ID card), and all rights afforded to TP-ID holders are consequently forfeited. Authorities thus take away their TP-ID Card at the border.⁸⁷

Re-applying the TP status for V-87 coded migrants who return to Turkey is under the discretion of the PDMs, with the approval of respective governorates. A circular by DGMM was sent to the governorates of Turkey's 81 provinces in January 2019. According to the circular, Syrians under TP who signed a voluntary return form, returned to Syria and consequently had their TP status "deactivated" with a V-87 code can, in fact, reapply to reactivate their TP status even if previously rejected by Governorships; however, this may only apply under certain conditions (e.g. illness, hospital admission, elderly age, marriage purposes, school enrolment, employment, etc.), but there are practical hurdles, including restricted registration access and rejected applications. Stakeholders highlighted that there continue to be cases of people whose TP status has ceased and who were issued a "V87" code, unable to re-access rights upon return to Turkey.⁸⁸

Since 2015, Europe's asylum policy has moved away from inclusionary policies to exclusionary policies with an agenda to focus on return programmes.⁸⁹ This shift has also influenced the migration management policies and practices in Turkey and increased the significant emphasis on the voluntary return of migrants as a means to justify the removal of the 'undesirable' population.⁹⁰ The concealed nature of the extent of coercion and the use of force in the notion of voluntary returns transform them into de facto deportation. Therefore, this study identifies practices, procedures, and actors that facilitate voluntary return but often with elements of coercion, resulting in what can be described as imposed returns. Turkish authorities maintain that they do not forcibly deport Syrians to align with the non-refoulement principle. However, Human Rights Watch (HRW)⁹¹ and the AI⁹² Reports indicate that some Syrians have faced verbal and physical pressure to consent to return, including claims that they were given misleading information about the situation in Syria or felt compelled to

⁸⁴ SRII WP4 Meso Level Interview, Gaziantep-02 (with a legal expert of an IGO)

⁸⁵ If they are using official border crossings, the aforementioned procedures have to be followed. If they are using irregular ways to cross, and they are not identified in the registered addresses, their registration would be also deactivated.

⁸⁶ Article 85 (1/c) of the LFIP states that "the international protection status shall terminate in cases where the beneficiary voluntarily returned to the country from which they have fled or stayed outside of due to fear of persecution"

⁸⁷ PMM, "Gönüllü, Güvenli ve Onurlu Geri Dönüş", 2024c, Available at: <https://www.goc.gov.tr/gonullu-geri-donus> (Accessed 24 May 2024).

⁸⁸ SRII WP4 Meso Level Interview, Gaziantep-02 (with a lawyer in an IGO)

⁸⁹ Jessica Schultz, "The end of protection? Cessation and the 'return turn' in refugee law", *EU Immigration and Asylum Law and Policy Blog*, 2020, Available at: <https://eumigrationlawblog.eu/the-end-of-protection-cessation-and-the-return-turn-in-refugee-law/> (Accessed 25 May 2024).

⁹⁰ Sevda Tunaboğlu, *Ibid.*, 2024.

⁹¹ Human Rights Watch (HRW), "Turkey: Hundreds of Refugees Deported to Syria", 24 October 2022, Available at: <https://www.hrw.org/news/2022/10/24/turkey-hundreds-refugees-deported-syria> (Accessed 25 May 2024).

⁹² AI, "Turkey: Sent to a war zone: Turkey's illegal deportations of Syrian refugees", 2019, Available at: <https://www.amnesty.org/en/documents/eur44/1102/2019/en/#:~:text=This%20report%20reveals%20that%2C%20contrary,the%20world's%20most%20dangerous%20countries> (Accessed 24 May 2024).

provide fingerprints on voluntary return forms. Field interviews and observations from various stakeholders in Gaziantep provide similar claims and reveal a complex situation regarding Syrian returns from Turkey. Interviewees highlighted that a representative number of some returns from Turkey are processed through removal centres. For instance, observations at the Azez (Bab Al Salame) border crossing alone indicate over 100 people returning daily; this includes some voluntary returns and deportations.⁹³ However, while these returns are officially classified as voluntary, interviewees suggest that the circumstances surrounding them may not always align with this classification, highlighting a discrepancy between official records and individual experiences.⁹⁴ Interviewees describe concerning practices in removal centres, such as limited legal protections with individuals having difficulty accessing interpreters or lawyers. If a lawyer doesn't reach the individual within 24 hours, the return process often proceeds regardless. The conditions in removal centres have reportedly worsened, with overcrowding and poor living conditions creating an environment that pushes individuals towards "voluntary" return. For example, the capacity of the Oguzeli Removal Centre in Gaziantep was suddenly doubled from 700 to 1400, severely impacting living conditions.⁹⁵

Interviews claim that the systematic implementation of return practices since 2022 has created an environment of fear and uncertainty among Syrian refugees. This includes converting temporary accommodation centres into reception and referral centres, especially in Southeast Turkey, and implementing mobile migration points that can deactivate TP IDs and enforce reporting duties.⁹⁶ Interviewees also noted a blurred line between voluntary returns and deportations. An interviewer claimed that while individuals may sign voluntary return forms, the actual process often resembles deportation. This makes it difficult to determine how many people are genuinely returning voluntarily versus being deported.⁹⁷

Another interview indicated that the situation is further complicated by limited options for those who manage to avoid deportation. They often find their IDs deactivated if released from removal centres, face bi-weekly reporting requirements, and lose access to healthcare and employment. This leaves many feeling they have no choice but to leave Turkey, either for Syria or to attempt irregular migration to Europe.⁹⁸ These findings raise questions about the voluntary nature of returns and potential violations of the non-refoulement principle. The situation can be evaluated as a part of a broader policy regarding reducing the Syrian population in Turkey, as reflected in official statements.⁹⁹

While focusing on voluntary and forced returns for Syrians, this report excludes the pushbacks since the field interviews confirm that pushbacks are not among the types of returns for Syrian migrants.¹⁰⁰ At the Turkey-Syrian border, the construction of the border wall is completed, fortified with concrete and mobile blocks, patrol routes, lighting systems, optic towers, thermal cameras, land surveillance radars, fibre-optic detection systems, and jammers¹⁰¹,

⁹³ SRII WP4 Meso Level Interview, Gaziantep-08 (with a manager of NGO)

⁹⁴ Ibid.⁹⁵ SRII WP4 Meso Level Interview, Gaziantep-04 (with a lawyer in Bar Association)

⁹⁵ SRII WP4 Meso Level Interview, Gaziantep-04 (with a lawyer in Bar Association)

⁹⁶ SRII WP4 Meso Level Interview, Gaziantep-04 (with a lawyer in Bar Association)

⁹⁷ SRII WP4 Meso Level Interview, Gaziantep-05 (with a manager of NGO)

⁹⁸ SRII WP4 Meso Level Interview, Gaziantep-08 (with a manager of NGO)

⁹⁹ Directorate of Communications, "We are preparing a new project that will enable the voluntary return of 1 million of our Syrian brothers and sisters", 03 May 2022. Available at: <https://www.iletisim.gov.tr/turkce/haberler/detay/cumhurbaskani-erdogan1-milyon-suriyeli-kardesimizin-gonullu-geri-donusunu-saglayacak-yeni-bir-projenin-hazirliklari-icindeviz> (Accessed 17 February 2025).

¹⁰⁰ SRII WP4 Meso Level Interview, Gaziantep-05 (with a manager of NGO)

¹⁰¹ Daily Sabah, "Turkey finishes construction of 764-km security wall on Syria border", 9 June 2018. Available at: https://www.dailysabah.com/war-on-terror/2018/06/09/turkey-finishes-construction-of-764-km-security-wall-on-syria-border?utm_source=chatgpt.com (Accessed 21 February 2025).

which have significantly diminished the possibility of pushbacks. It should also be noted that as the existing legal reality, erecting a physical barrier to prevent irregular crossings does not constitute pushback in legal terms, provided that official, accessible border checkpoints are in place, where individuals seeking asylum have a genuine opportunity to submit their claims in accordance with international protection standards. Interception data from the IOM's Migrant Presence Monitoring illustrates a notable decrease in daily interceptions from approximately 350 individuals¹⁰² to 20-30 individuals post-August 2021¹⁰³, with monthly figures in 2022 further dropping to less than 100. By December 2022, the transparency of interception data ceased, suggesting either a methodological shift in data collection or a significant enhancement in border security.¹⁰⁴ These developments underpin the rationale for omitting pushbacks from the study, arguing for their minimal occurrence or limited data availability.

Briefly, voluntary returns are offered to both Syrians and, in fewer cases, Afghans as part of a broader strategy to manage the refugee population. However, voluntary return programmes for Syrians have faced significant criticism. One interviewee from a Syrian NGO remarked: "People are pressured to return because they have no future here, and the promise of safety in Syria is questionable at best".¹⁰⁵

For Syrians, the TP status allows for some degree of security in Turkey, but legal uncertainties and socio-economic pressures undermine the voluntariness of their return. Local actors, particularly in border regions, have highlighted that many Syrians return because they feel they have no other choice. The national NGO coordinator emphasized, "People come to us for help, but the reality is that if they don't see a future here, they will sign the return papers, even if they don't want to".¹⁰⁶

For Syrians, the respondents stated that many voluntary returns involve a coercive notion due to the lack of opportunities in Turkey and the ongoing uncertainty regarding their legal status. Several interviews suggest that Syrians under TP face a constant state of limbo, where their temporary status creates a sense of insecurity, pushing them toward return, even if it is framed as voluntary. The lawyer noted: "The voluntariness of these returns is very debatable. Syrians are pressured by their situation, and the legal system does not always protect them from making a decision they do not truly want".¹⁰⁷

The flow map given below (**Figure 4**) shows the flow map of those return types for Syrians. The figure illustrates the pathways for both voluntary and forced returns of Syrians from Turkey, highlighting the complex layers of migration control. Syrians are identified by law enforcement through security checks, address verification exercises, and mobile migration points. Depending on their legal and registration status, they may face different outcomes: referral to TACs, deportation procedures, or voluntary return processes.

Unregistered Syrians are referred to TACs in Southeast Turkey, where they must either regularize their status, opt for voluntary return, or face potential deportation. Those who fail to complete documentation requirements risk deportation. Meanwhile, Syrians found violating work permit rules, lacking proper documentation, or residing outside their registered

¹⁰² IOM, "Turkey – Migrant Presence Monitoring - Situation Report (July 2021)", 2021a, Available at: <https://dtm.iom.int/reports/turkey-%E2%80%94-migrant-presence-monitoring-situation-report-july-2021> (Accessed 24 May 2024).

¹⁰³ IOM, "Turkey – Migrant Presence Monitoring - Situation Report (August 2021)", 2021b, available at: <https://dtm.iom.int/reports/turkey-%E2%80%94-migrant-presence-monitoring-situation-report-august-2021> (Accessed 24 May 2024).

¹⁰⁴ SRII WP4 Meso Level Interview, Gaziantep-01 (with an IGO representative)

¹⁰⁵ SRII WP4 Meso-Level Interview, Istanbul-01 (with an IGO representative)

¹⁰⁶ SRII WP4 Meso-Level Interview, Istanbul-02 (with a nation-wide NGO representative)

¹⁰⁷ SRII WP3 Meso-Level Interview, Izmir-01 (with a nation-wide NGO representative)

province may have their TP ID deactivated and face increased pressure to comply with migration laws or return.

The figure also outlines the steps for Syrians opting for voluntary return, which involves filling out a return form, undergoing registration checks, and obtaining travel permits. However, the distinction between voluntary and forced return becomes blurred when considering the pressures created by legal and administrative restrictions, including TPID deactivation, detention, and mobility limitations. Critically, the figure underscores how voluntary return processes may be influenced by coercive conditions, such as loss of legal status, detention threats, or difficult living conditions. This raises concerns about the genuineness of voluntariness, as many Syrians may return under duress rather than by free choice. The securitization of migration management, combined with administrative controls and increased deportation procedures, reflects a broader shift in Turkey's migration policy from protection to containment and return.

Figure 4: Return Migration Infrastructures Flow Map for Syrians in Turkey

Border crossing status

* Developed based on framework paper on the concepts and typologies on return (E.U. 1)
 ** Deportation Process, Presidency of Migration Management, 2024. <https://www.goc.gov.tr/2024/02/2024-02-20>
 *** Voluntary, Safe, Dignified Return, Presidency of Migration Management, 2024. <https://www.goc.gov.tr/2024/02/2024-02-20>
 **** Theoretically, deportation decision can be issued for the third countries, however, PDMM (Article 54) it is not possible to issue deportation decision legally about Syrians due to the conditions in Syria.

Source: Prepared and designed by the authors

4.1.1.2. Types of Returns for Afghan Migrants

When IP status holders in Turkey are examined, it is evident that the majority of these groups are people from Afghanistan, Iraq and Iran.¹⁰⁸ IP applicants whose requests are deemed appropriate are granted refugee, conditional refugee or subsidiary protection in accordance with the LFIP.¹⁰⁹ The authority for RSD belongs to the PMM.¹¹⁰

IP applications made in Turkey, especially by Afghan citizens coming to Turkey from Iran and Pakistan, can be considered inadmissible. If Afghan citizens coming from a country of first asylum or a safe third country benefit from adequate protection in that country, including the principle of non-refoulement to Afghanistan, and it is understood that they are not exposed to any threat in that country, their applications are deemed inadmissible. However, if the person concerned is not accepted by the country of first asylum or the country described as a safe third country, the procedures regarding the IP application will continue.¹¹¹

As different from Syrians, the research showed that returns are more frequently forced or coercive, especially for those caught crossing the eastern border irregularly and with a significantly high rate of pushback. Therefore, three types of turns are focused: Pushback, Forced Removal (Intimidation, Administrative Detention and Deportation), and Assisted Voluntary Return. The main legal framework for forced and voluntary returns is given to Syrians. However, as reflected in reports from many international organizations¹¹² and this research, the most common type of Afghan return is pushback.

According to PMM's irregular migration figures, 254,027 foreigners from various nationalities were apprehended across the country in 2023, representing a decrease of 10% compared to 2022, when 285,027 irregular migrants were apprehended.¹¹³ The majority of them are Afghans, followed by Syrians and Pakistanis. Additionally, according to the number of IP applications in Turkey, nearly 70% of the 19,017 applications will be Afghans by the end of 2023. In 2022, the number of applications from Afghans alone was around 19,000.¹¹⁴ Since the Taliban seized control of Afghanistan in August 2021, hundreds of thousands of Afghans have fled the country. According to the UNHCR, more than 900,000 people were displaced

¹⁰⁸ PMM, *Ibid.*, 2024d.

¹⁰⁹ Refugee (granted to individuals coming from European countries based on the 1951 Convention, LFIP, Article 61(1)); Conditional refugee (For asylum seekers coming from non-European countries. Granted temporarily until resettlement in a third country, LFIP, Article 62(1)); Subsidiary protection (Granted to individuals who do not qualify as refugees or conditional refugees but face serious threats (death penalty, torture, or violence) LFIP, Article 63(1)); Temporary protection (Group-based protection for mass influx situations, currently only for Syrians who arrived directly from Syria after 28 April 2011., LFIP, Article 91(1–2) and the temporary protection regulation (TPR 2014)).

¹¹⁰ PMM, *Law 6458 on Foreigners and International Protection (YUKK)*, 2024e.

¹¹¹ Sema Çörtoğlu Koca, "Türkiye'de Düzensiz Göçmen Olarak Bulunan Afganların Hukuki Statülerine İlişkin Değerlendirmeler", 2022, *Public and Private International Law Bulletin*, 42(2).

¹¹² Stiftung Pro Asyl, "The Situation of Afghan Refugees in Turkey", 2021, available at: <https://www.proasyl.de/en/material/expert-opinion-the-situation-of-afghan-refugees-in-turkey/>; AI, "They Don't Treat Us Like Humans": Unlawful Returns of Afghans from Turkey and Iran", 2022, Available at: <https://www.amnesty.org/en/documents/asa11/5897/2022/en/>; HRW, "No One Asked Me Why I Left Afghanistan" Pushbacks and Deportations of Afghans from Turkey", 2022; Available at: <https://www.hrw.org/report/2022/11/18/no-one-asked-me-why-i-left-afghanistan/pushbacks-and-deportations-afghans-turkey#:~:text=%E2%80%9Ctold%20them%20I%20was,on%20August%2030%2C%202021%2C%20shortly> (Accessed 25 May 2024).

¹¹³ PMM, "Düzensiz Göç İstatistikleri", 2024f. Available at: <https://www.goc.gov.tr/duzensiz-goc-istatistikler> (Accessed 25 May 2024).

¹¹⁴ PMM, "Uluslararası Koruma İstatistikleri", 2024g. Available at: <https://www.goc.gov.tr/uluslararasi-koruma-istatistikler> (Accessed 26 May 2024).

within the country or to neighbouring countries, with many returning during the year.¹¹⁵ More than 180,000 Afghans in need of IP have arrived in neighbouring countries since 1 January 2021, but the overall number of Afghans with IP needs is likely to be much higher.¹¹⁶

In April 2022, Turkish authorities announced that a 191 km-long wall at the border with Iran had been completed and that it would be extended to 295 km by 2023. According to Turkey's Minister of Interior, the EU is providing financial support of 110 million EUR for the construction of the wall.¹¹⁷ Increased security measures on the Iranian border have increased the pushback of Afghans in recent years. There were several official acknowledgements of pushbacks in 2022. A report claimed that the gendarmerie had confirmed the national police had told them to push migrants back on the Turkey-Iran border due to the high cost of feeding, housing, and legally processing their claims.¹¹⁸ In December 2021, Governor from Van admitted to pushbacks against migrants on the Iranian-Turkish border, stating that nearly 120,000 migrants had been blocked from entering via the Van border that year. The same governor admitted to 1,137 irregular migrants being blocked in January 2022.¹¹⁹ In addition, according to the PMM statement, 274,311 irregular migrants were intercepted at the land and sea borders. This brings the total number of intercepted irregular migrants to 2,737,732 between 2016-2022.¹²⁰

The reports published by NGOs operating in the field of migration in Turkey based on field studies reveal findings that Afghans are being pushed back at the Turkey-Iran border.¹²¹ AIDA report claims that irregular migrants who escaped detection and security controls frequently went into hiding in Van and were reluctant to request IP for fear of being pushed back.¹²² Despite being driven back from the border four or five times, people continued to attempt to enter Turkey, and many of them attempted to migrate to the western cities of Turkey once they had arrived.¹²³

Afghan individuals interviewed by the AI were forcibly returned by bus from Iran to Afghanistan and from Turkey to Iran after detention, without being able to apply for IP, without receiving an individual assessment of the reasons for their removal or of the risks they would face upon their return to either Afghanistan, Iran or, in one case, Syria.¹²⁴ The AI documented no case; the Iranian and Turkish authorities examined individual cases and their need for IP, and in some cases, the authorities denied access to asylum procedures to those who explicitly expressed fear for their life or human rights if returned.¹²⁵ The assisted voluntary

¹¹⁵ UNHCR, "Global Trends Report 2021", 2022, Available at: <https://www.unhcr.org/media/global-trends-report-2021> (Accessed 26 May 2024).

¹¹⁶ Ibid.

¹¹⁷ AI, Ibid., 2019.

¹¹⁸ Karolina Augustova, "Afghans fleeing the Taliban face death, deportation and push-backs in Turkey", 15 July 2021, available at: <https://www.opendemocracy.net/en/north-africa-west-asia/afghans-fleeing-taliban-face-death-deportation-and-push-backs-turkey/> (Accessed 27 May 2024).

¹¹⁹ Behçet Dalmaz, "Vali Bilmez: 2021'de Van sınırında 120 bine yakın göçmen engellendi", Milliyet, 31 December 2021, available at: <https://www.milliyet.com.tr/gundem/vali-bilmez-2021de-van-sinirinda-120-bine-yakin-gocmen-engellendi-6672153> (Accessed 26 May 2024).

¹²⁰ PMM, "Sınır Dışı Sayısında Artış Devam Ediyor: 119.817 Düzensiz Göçmen Sınır Dışı Edildi", 25 Aralık 2022, Available at: <https://www.goc.gov.tr/sinir-disi-119817> (Accessed 26 May 2024).

¹²¹ Hakan Ünay, "Türkiye'ye Yönelik Afganistan Göçü'ne Yerelden Bakmak: Van Saha Araştırması Çalışma Raporu", *Göç Araştırmaları Vakfı*, 2021. Available at: <https://gocvakfi.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/RAPOR-5-H.U%CC%88NAY.pdf>; Göç Araştırmaları Derneği, "Actors and Mechanisms of (Non-)reception of the Afghans in Turkey", 2023. Available at: <https://www.gocarastirmalaridernegi.org/en/activities/research/afghan-reception-in-turkey/343-non-reception-of-the-afghans-in-turkey> (Accessed 25 May 2024).

¹²² AIDA, Ibid., 2024.

¹²³ Ibid.

¹²⁴ AI, Ibid., 2019.

¹²⁵ Ibid.

return of Afghans is carried out through "Supporting the Implementation and further Strengthening of Turkey's N-AVRR through ICMPD. The N-AVRR Project, "Supporting the implementation and further strengthening of Turkey's National Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration System", consisting of two pillars, provides comprehensive support for the implementation and further development of Turkey's N-AVRR system, including capacity-building activities and financial assistance provision for conducting voluntary return operations and reintegration assistance.¹²⁶

Especially after 2018, Turkey started working on the return programme and border security. The ICMPD has become one of the critical actors in Turkey's return policies. The ICMPD Turkey has been working with the PMM to establish an N-AVRR mechanism. As a result of long-standing consultations and background work within the ICMPD projects' framework, the N-AVRR programme's national stakeholders were identified as PMM, TRC, Turkish Cooperation and Coordination Agency (TİKA) and the MoFA. Those national stakeholders signed a letter of intent on 18 June 2019 and a Cooperation Protocol on 2 September 2020, laying the foundations for the implementation of the N-AVRR.¹²⁷

Briefly, for Afghans, coerced returns are even more common, often resulting from poor detention conditions or border control measures. Many Afghans do not have the same legal protections as Syrians and are subjected to rapid deportations. As one NGO representative pointed out: "Afghan returns are very different. They are often forced to leave within a matter of days, and there is very little oversight to ensure these are done according to international standards".¹²⁸

Forced returns, particularly for Afghans, are a regular feature of Turkey's migration policy, especially in the eastern regions where many enter the country irregularly. There are claims regarding pushbacks and deportations, with many Afghans facing immediate removal without access to legal protections or asylum procedures. A lawyer in Van discussed the lack of procedural safeguards for Afghan refugees, stating: "Afghans are deported almost immediately; they are pushbacked. There is no time for them to apply for asylum or even understand what is happening. The process is much harsher for them compared to Syrians."¹²⁹

The below-given flow map (**Figure 5**) shows the flow map of those return types for Afghans, which outlines the mechanisms of voluntary and forced returns for Afghans and other irregular migrants in Turkey, illustrating the legal processes, deportation criteria, and available support for returnees. Forced returns primarily target those who violate the LFIP, including individuals with expired permits, false documentation, or security-related concerns. Once apprehended, migrants undergo an evaluation by the PDMs within 48 hours. If a deportation decision is issued, the individual has seven days to appeal in administrative court, with a ruling expected within fifteen days. If the appeal fails, deportation proceeds, either through direct removal or administrative detention in removal centres for up to six months, with the possibility of extension. Some individuals may be placed under alternative measures such as residence restrictions, regular reporting, electronic monitoring, or community service. Certain vulnerable groups, including those facing risks of death, torture, or severe health conditions, may be granted humanitarian residence permits instead of deportation.

For those deemed eligible, voluntary return programs operate in collaboration with international organizations and NGOs, offering Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration

¹²⁶ ICMPD, "NAVRR: Supporting the Implementation and further Strengthening of Türkiye's National Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration System", 6 June 2024, Available at: <https://www.icmpd.org/our-work/projects/supporting-the-implementation-and-further-strengthening-of-tuerkiye-s-national-assisted-voluntary-return-and-reintegration-system-navrr> (Accessed 22 May 2024).

¹²⁷ ICMPD, *Ibid.*, 11 June 2021.

¹²⁸ SRII WP4 Meso-Level Interview, Van-01 (with a border village mukhtar)

¹²⁹ SRII WP4 Meso-Level Interview, Van-02 (with a border village mukhtar)

(AVRR) support. This includes assistance with travel arrangements, documentation, and counselling, as well as financial aid upon departure to help cover basic needs upon return. Many Afghan migrants face additional challenges due to a lack of proper travel documentation, requiring coordination with embassies and consulates to process their return. Vulnerable groups, such as elderly individuals, victims of violence, and single-parent families, receive special consideration to facilitate reintegration. However, the distinction between voluntary and forced return remains highly ambiguous. Many Afghan migrants in Turkey experience significant legal and administrative pressure, including the threat of detention, restrictions on movement and work, and loss of legal status, effectively coercing them into "voluntary" return.

Regarding the pushbacks, creating a flowchart is inherently difficult because pushbacks operate outside legal frameworks and lack transparency. Unlike formal deportation and voluntary return procedures, pushbacks occur extrajudicially, often through informal and ad hoc practices by security forces, making it challenging to standardize the process into a structured diagram. One key difficulty is the lack of official documentation and procedural steps. Unlike deportations, which involve identifiable administrative decisions, appeals, and detention procedures, pushbacks are often immediate, undocumented expulsions at borders, preventing any formal appeal or legal intervention. Instead of a structured decision-making process, pushbacks represent an arbitrary, extra-legal practice shaped by shifting political and security dynamics, making them inherently resistant to standardization. Additionally, pushbacks are highly variable and context-dependent. The methods used vary depending on border locations, security conditions, and political directives. The lack of uniformity in how pushbacks occur makes it difficult to define clear decision points or sequential steps in a flowchart. Another challenge is the involvement of multiple actors, including border guards, military units, and sometimes third-country cooperation agreements, which function in a discretionary rather than a rule-based manner.

Figure 5: Return Migration Infrastructures Flow Map for Afghans in Turkey

** Developed based on framework paper on the context and typologies of returnees (2021)
 ** Deportation Procedures, Presidency of Migration Management, 2024. <https://www.goc.gov.tr/imm/return>

Source: Prepared and designed by the authors.

4.1.2. Scales of Returns

There has been a fluctuation in Syrians' voluntary returns from Turkey between 2017 and 2024, as **Figure 6** shows. Based on the official data and statements, starting with 117,919 returns in 2017, the numbers peaked at 173,124 in 2018, potentially due to the Turkish military interventions in Northwest Syria and relatively improved security conditions.¹³⁰ This was followed by a steady decline to their lowest point of 39,319 in 2020, especially with the effect of COVID-19; however, a gradual increase began in 2021, with returns increasing to 147,765 in 2024.¹³¹ The figure is particularly influenced by the earthquakes in 2023, as well as the fall of the Assad regime on 8 December 2024 (given in Chapter 5). The monthly average returns mirror these trends, ranging from a peak of 14,427 in 2018 to a low of 3,277 in 2020 before rising again to 12,314 in 2024.¹³² In 2020, 48,046 Syrians voluntarily returned, with this number rising to 96,537 by 2024, which represents a doubling of annual returns over a five-year period. The monthly average of returns also saw a significant increase, from 4,004 in 2020 to 11,151 in 2024.¹³³

In 2017, Turkey began encouraging “go and see” visits, under which Syrians with TP status were allowed to return to Syria for up to three months without losing their status in Turkey and retaining the option to return.¹³⁴ Under this policy, the Turkish government reported that in 2017 and 2018, over 183,000 Syrians returned and overstayed for three months, giving up their status in Turkey.¹³⁵ It is worth mentioning that such a mechanism has been in place since before the conflict in Syria and ended in 2022. However, the practice of allowing Syrians to go and visit Syria during religious festivals also provided an opportunity for Syrians to check on their land or properties and to gauge the security situation first-hand. Mediatization of these visits also created an expectation among host community members and sparked debates on whether Syrians could return to Syria permanently. This policy has changed for holiday permits granted to Syrians during religious holidays. The MoI announced in April 2022 that holiday permits are not given, and Syrians can only visit and stay in safe zones, namely, Cobanbey, Azez, El Bab, and Mare. Those who want to go to Syria for the holiday will not be allowed re-entry to Turkey.¹³⁶

On the other hand, according to PMM's irregular migration figures, 254,027 foreigners from various nationalities were apprehended across the country in 2023, representing a decrease of 10% compared to 2022, when 285,027 irregular migrants were apprehended.¹³⁷ The majority of them are Afghans, followed by Syrians and Pakistanis. A significant increase in the number of irregular migrants apprehended was observed in 2019 when the government introduced the stricter implementation of existing regulations and its strategy to combat irregular migration, including provincial relocation measures.

¹³⁰ Anadolu Agency, Ajansı “Interview with Minister of Interior”, 24 December 2024, Available at: <https://www.youtube.com/live/O3fxUCuIFRQ> (Accessed 2 February 2025).

¹³¹ Ibid.

¹³² Ibid.

¹³³ Ibid.

¹³⁴ Zeynep Şahin Mencütek, “Encouraging Syrian return: Turkey's fragmented approach”, *Forced Migration Review*, 2019, Available at: <https://www.fmreview.org/return/sahinmencutek> (Accessed 23 May 2024).

¹³⁵ Overstaying a go-and-see visit is not necessarily sufficient to qualify as a voluntary return.

¹³⁶ Hürriyet, “Bayrama giden kalacak”, 2022, Available at: <https://www.hurriyet.com.tr/gundem/bayrama-giden-kalacak-42049388#:~:text=%C4%B0%C3%A7in%C5%9Fleri%20Bakan%C4%B1%20S%C3%BCleyman%20Soylu,%20bayramlarda%20%C3%BClkelerine%20gidip%20geri,Bayram%20in%C3%A7in%20gidip%20d%C3%B6nmek%20isteyenlere%20izin%20verilmeyecek%E2%80%9D%20dedi> (Accessed 24 May 2024).

¹³⁷ PMM, Ibid., 2024d.

Before 2019, only the IOM's AVRR programme was in place. Some 8,098 migrants, mostly Afghans, were provided AVRR support from 2009 to 2018, mainly via funds to cover charter flights and pocket money upon return.¹³⁸ In 2019, some 2,344 people, mostly Afghans, in addition to Pakistanis and Uzbeks, were returned to their countries of origin through the IOM's AVRR programmes.¹³⁹ Another significant initiative is the National Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration (N-AVRR) project, supported by the ICMPD and national funding. With the help of ICMPD and funding from the national budget, PMM established its own voluntary returns programme in 2021. This process is less transparent, and how many people are returning is unknown. After Kabul, returns to Afghanistan were halted for a short while, but as of the beginning of 2022, Turkey started to send high numbers of Afghans back to Afghanistan under the guise of "voluntary return".¹⁴⁰ The lack of transparency and reports of coercion in the return process, especially in countries like Afghanistan, have raised concerns. In January 2022, the Turkish interior minister announced the resumption of sending 'illegal Afghans' back to Afghanistan via charter flights. In 2022, 44,786 Afghans were returned to Afghanistan through 186 charter flights, often under the guise of voluntary return.¹⁴¹ However, reports suggest that these returns were not entirely voluntary, with many Afghans being deported despite significant risks in their home country.

According to AIDA's report, before the elections in 2022, approximately 320 Afghans were sent back to Afghanistan from Agri, and charter flights were numerous. Some charter flights went to Afghanistan through Ankara. All of these returnees signed a return form voluntarily.¹⁴² From March 2021 to May 2022, the AI documented 155 cases of illegal deportation and 23 pushbacks of Afghans involving gunshots at the border.¹⁴³ According to a source quoted in the Dutch Country Report on Afghanistan of 2023¹⁴⁴, irregular Afghans stopped by Turkish police risk immediate deportation from the country. According to the HRW report, 238.448 illegal migrants, most of them Afghans, were driven back to Iran in this way in 2022. In that same year, 92.583 Afghans were rounded up as irregular migrants by the Turkish police.¹⁴⁵

According to another statement by the PMM in early 2023, 8,571 immigrants were deported in the first month of 2023. In this context, 139 irregular immigrants were deported to their countries, with the 9th charter flight organized to Afghanistan since the beginning of the year.¹⁴⁶ In addition, numerous reports of such deportations of Afghan migrants from Turkey were also published in 2023. In terms of deportations of Afghan migrants by air from Turkey to Afghanistan, there are also reports of Afghans being expelled overland from the border areas of Eastern Turkey to Iran.¹⁴⁷ An aid worker assisting Afghan refugees in Turkey claimed

¹³⁸ IOM, "IOM and the European Union Helping Thousands of Vulnerable Migrants to Get Home from Turkey", 17 April 2019, Available at: <https://turkiye.iom.int/news/iom-and-european-union-helping-thousands-vulnerable-migrants-get-home-turkey> (Accessed 24 May 2024).

¹³⁹ European Commission, "Commission Staff Working Document: Turkey 2020 Report", 2020, Available at: https://neighbourhood-enlargement.ec.europa.eu/document/download/f4b4f445-6f09-4130-95bc-04b1df4e8f46_en?filename=turkey_report_2020.pdf (Accessed 23 May 2024).

¹⁴⁰ Anadolu Ajansı. Ibid., 2024.

¹⁴¹ PMM, 'Yılbaşından Bugüne 72.578 Kaçak Göçmen Sınır Dışı Edildi', 23 August 2022, Available at: <https://www.goc.gov.tr/kacak-gocmen2> (Accessed 25 May 2024).

¹⁴² AIDA, Ibid., 2024.

¹⁴³ AI, "Iran/Turkey: Fleeing Afghans unlawfully returned after coming under fire at borders", 31 August 2022, Available at: <https://www.amnesty.org/en/latest/news/2022/08/iran-turkey-fleeing-afghans-unlawfully-returned-after-coming-under-fire-at-borders/> (Accessed 25 May 2024).

¹⁴⁴ Dutch Ministry of Foreign Affairs, "Algemeen Ambtsbericht Afghanistan", 2023, Available at: <https://open.overheid.nl/documenten/ronl-ddb4f12508d6ab794d05d29826474c969cd5a44b/pdf> (Accessed 25 May 2024).

¹⁴⁵ HRW, Ibid., 2022.

¹⁴⁶ PMM, , Ibid., 30 January 2023.

¹⁴⁷ Office of the Commissioner General for Refugees and Stateless Persons, "Afghanistan: Migration movements of Afghans since the Taliban takeover of power", *COI Focus*, 14 December 2023; Available at:

to Middle East Eye News in November 2022 that these expulsions of Afghan migrants are being carried out intensely: their fingerprints are taken, their biometric data are stored, and they are sent back across the border.¹⁴⁸

According to the AIDA Report¹⁴⁹ (2024 update, p. 29), Afghan migrants facing deportation are often issued notification forms like the "T1" form after administrative detention. These forms, recorded in the Göç-Net system, officially notify individuals of their decision to be deported. While Turkish law (LFIP, Article 79) allows detainees to apply for International Protection (IP), stakeholders cited in the AIDA Report claim that procedural inefficiencies and the speed of deportations often hinder access to IP. According to AIDA's report¹⁵⁰, increasing numbers of arrivals through the Iranian border have led to restrictive measures and arbitrary detention and deportation practices. The Afghanistan Analysts Network (AAN)¹⁵¹, discussing deportations in 2018-2019, suggests that removals were carried out too rapidly for thorough case reviews but does not mention the "T1" form or assert a legal barrier to IP applications. The main concern is not the form itself but the challenges in accessing asylum procedures before deportation.

According to an analysis¹⁵² published by the Afghanistan Analysts Network, mainly single Afghan men are being issued deportation. ("T1") forms. The "T1" forms are usually issued following administrative detention in a Removal Centre or a police station and are stored in the PMM electronic file management system named "Göç-Net". If a "T1" deportation decision has been issued, the person cannot apply for IP, and the decision can only be challenged by a judicial appeal.¹⁵³

A notable recent acceleration in returns occurred between 2023 and 2024. In 2023, 76,346 Syrians voluntarily returned, which jumped to 147,765 in 2024 - an increase of nearly 94% in just one year.¹⁵⁴ This sharp rise could be partially attributed to the potential impact of i) narrative highlighting improved conditions through the military interventions and ii) operations targeting 'irregular migrants' and the shrinking protective environment through detention and forced return practices (e.g. provincial relocation projects, mobile migration points, address verification exercises, etc.), and iii) the fall of Assad regime in December 2024. During the aftermath of the February 2024 earthquakes, the Turkish government also allowed for a temporary return of Syrians. Interviews with stakeholders indicated that 70,000 people carried out temporary returns to Syria for 6 months. The condition for the temporary return was not to return to Turkey within the first 3 months, and the system reportedly worked well. Around 64,000 out of 70,000 returned to Turkey.¹⁵⁵

Turkish officials frequently share the numbers of Syrian returnees. On 24 December 2024, the MoI announced that 763,443 Syrians had returned to their homes since 2017¹⁵⁶. While these

<https://www.cgrr.be/en/country-information/migration-movements-afghans-taliban-takeover-power> (Accessed 27 May 2024).

¹⁴⁸ Ali M. Latifi, "Over 240,000 Afghan refugees deported from Iran and Turkey", *Middle East Eye*, 2023; Available at: [Over 240,000 Afghan refugees deported from Iran and Turkey | Middle East Eye](https://www.middleeasteye.net/news/over-240000-afghan-refugees-deported-from-iran-and-turkey) (Accessed 27 May 2024).

¹⁴⁹ AIDA, Ibid. 2024.

¹⁵⁰ AIDA, Ibid. 2024.

¹⁵¹ Amy Pitonak, "Mass Deportations of Afghans from Turkey: Thousands of migrants sent back in a deportation drive", *Afghanistan Analyst Network*, 21 June 2018, Available at: <https://www.afghanistan-analysts.org/en/reports/migration/mass-deportations-of-afghans-from-turkey/> (Accessed 09 February 2025).

¹⁵² Amy Pitonak, "Mass Deportations of Afghans from Turkey: Thousands of migrants sent back in a deportation drive", *Afghanistan Analyst Network*, 21 June 2018, Available at: <https://www.afghanistan-analysts.org/en/reports/migration/mass-deportations-of-afghans-from-turkey/> (Accessed 09 February 2025).

¹⁵³ AIDA, Ibid., 2024.

¹⁵⁴ Ibid.

¹⁵⁵ SRII WP4 Meso-Level Interview, Gaziantep-01 (with an IGO representative)

¹⁵⁶ Anadolu Agency, "Interview with Minister of Interior", 24 December 2024, <https://www.youtube.com/live/O3fxUCuIFRQ> (Accessed 25 Dec 2024)

figures should be approached cautiously, they also indicate the operationalization of an increasing trend of voluntary return discourse among the Turkish political elites. According to this statement, the average annual return figures are 95,430 between 2017 and 2024.¹⁵⁷

Aside from the above-mentioned official Turkish statements, the UNHCR also observes the voluntary nature of returns. The UNHCR continues to monitor return interviews in 12 PDMMs and at five border crossing points (Cilvegözü/Cilvegözü/ Bab al Hawa, Zeytindalı/ Jinderes, Yayladağı/Yayladağı/ Keseb, Oncupinar/Bab al Salama, Karkamis/Karkamış /Jarablus). Accordingly, it has participated in the voluntary return interviews of 202,574 Syrians since 2016.¹⁵⁸

Figure 6: Annual and Monthly Voluntary Returns of Syrians (2017-2024)

Source: The authors prepared based on the official data from the Minister of Interior's statements¹⁵⁹

Briefly, **Figure 6** shows that the highest number of annual returns occurred in 2018 (173,124), followed by a significant drop in 2019 (93,249) and a sharp decline in 2020 (39,319), likely the number of returns in 2024 (147,765) showing a dramatic increase compared to previous years, suggesting a policy shift or intensified enforcement efforts. The monthly average (12,314) also reflects this sharp rise, indicating that the trend is accelerating. After a low in 2020, returns steadily grew, with an increase every year, suggesting a gradual normalization of return procedures. The fluctuations indicate that external factors (such as the pandemic) and domestic policies (such as increased deportations or voluntary return initiatives) significantly shape return dynamics. The surge in 2024 might suggest intensified return mechanisms or shifting migration governance priorities. The most recent figures after the 8 December 2024 can be found in Chapter 5.

¹⁵⁷ Ibid.

¹⁵⁸ UNHCR, "Operational Data Portal, Syria Regional Refugee Response: Durable Solutions", 2024b, available at: https://data.unhcr.org/en/situations/syria_durable_solutions (Accessed 31 October 2024).

¹⁵⁹ Anadolu Agency, Ibid., 24 December 2024.

Figure 7: Number of Irregular Afghan and Syrian Migrants (2014-2023)

Source: The authors prepared the data for Syrians and Afghans based on the official data from the PMM (<https://en.goc.gov.tr/temporary-protection27>)

Figure 7 reflects the key differences in irregular migration trends between Afghans and Syrians in Turkey. Afghan migration shows sharp fluctuations, peaking in 2019 and 2022, likely influenced by intensified deportations, the Taliban takeover, and shifting border policies. In contrast, Syrian irregular migration remains more stable but has risen recently, suggesting increasing pressures or policy shifts. The overall trends indicate that migration policies, geopolitical crises, and enforcement measures significantly shape irregular migration dynamics in Turkey.

When it comes to Afghan migrants, other sources also state that approximately 92,000 Afghans were deported from Turkey to Afghanistan between the years 2017- and 2019.¹⁶⁰ In 2019, the MoI declared that approximately 200,000 Afghans got caught, and more than one-third of those Afghans were deported.¹⁶¹ According to the United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA), 6000 Afghans were deported from Turkey as of August 2020.¹⁶² According to PMM, a total of 66,534 Afghan citizens were returned to their country in 2022, 44,433 with 234 charter flights and 22,101 with scheduled flights.¹⁶³

It is important to note that neither the AVRR programme implemented by IOM¹⁶⁴ nor the N-AVRR programme implemented with Turkish national resources and with the support of ICMPD¹⁶⁵ share annual data in a structured and disaggregated way. In its April 2019 press

¹⁶⁰ GAR Association Report, “Ghost of Istanbul: Afghans at the Margins of Precarity”, September 2020, Available at: <https://gocarastirmalaridernegi.org/wp-content/uploads/GHOSTS-OF-ISTANBUL-N.pdf> (Accessed 2 February 2025).

¹⁶¹ Ibid.

¹⁶² UNHCR, “Afghanistan: Snapshot of Population Movements (January to July 2020)”, 20 August 2020, Available at: <https://reliefweb.int/report/afghanistan/afghanistan-snapshot-population-movements-january-july-2020-20-august-2020> (Accessed 22.05.2024).

¹⁶³ PMM, Ibid., 25 December 2022.

¹⁶⁴ IOM, Ibid., 17 April 2019.

¹⁶⁵ ICMPD, Ibid., 6 June 2024.

release, the IOM stated that it helped 8,098 stranded (non-Syrian) migrants with assisted voluntary return and 438 with reintegration assistance from 2009-2018.

There is also no publicly accessible data on voluntary, assisted, and forced return in a disaggregated way. Turkish government authorities often provide figures that do not provide relevant breakdowns for proper data analysis. However, figures announced by the Minister of Interior, Ali Yerlikaya, provide time-wise breakdowns on the number of interceptions, apprehensions and deportations.¹⁶⁶ Accordingly, between the period of May 2023 and September 2024, 214,217 individuals were intercepted at the border, while the same period also saw the deportation of 182,980 individuals.¹⁶⁷ It should be noted that the deportation figures do not include Syrian migrants under TP, but non-Syrians who are often labelled as irregular migrants because Syrians cannot be deported in line with the non-refoulement principle. However, as indicated in the previous sections, Syrians' return takes the form of voluntary return, while the notion of voluntariness is often blurred with the coercion elements. On the other hand, deportations of Afghans increased by 146% over 2022¹⁶⁸ and continued during 2023. In the first quarter of 2023, the number of migrants deported from all nationalities was 21,211. 2,319 people were deported to Afghanistan with 15 charter flights, and 4,526 with scheduled flights¹⁶⁹.

Figure 8: Number of Deportations (2020-2024)

Source: The authors prepared the official data from the Minister of Interior's statements.¹⁷⁰

Figure 8 shows a clear upward trend in the numbers from 2020 to 2023, indicating a significant increase over time. The numbers remain relatively low in the first two years, followed by a sharp rise in 2022 and 2023. This suggests an escalation in enforcement

¹⁶⁶ A Haber, "İçişleri Bakanı Ali Yerlikaya'dan A Haber'e Özel Açıklamalar! Şeyda Yılmaz ve Narin Güran Açıklaması", 26 September 2024, Available at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vvCTLLDWJxQ> (Accessed 2 February 2025).

¹⁶⁷ Ibid.

¹⁶⁸ PMM, "Yılbaşından Bugüne 72.578 Kaçak Göçmen Sınır Dışı Edildi", 23 August 2022, Available at: <https://www.goc.gov.tr/kacak-gocmen2> (Accessed 25 May 2024)

¹⁶⁹ Anadolu Agency, "Sınır dışı edilen düzensiz göçmen sayısı 21 bin 211'e ulaştı" 13 March 2023, Available at: <https://www.aa.com.tr/tr/gundem/bu-yil-sinir-disi-edilen-duzensiz-gocmen-sayisi-21-bin-211e-ulasti/> (Accessed 25 May 2024)

¹⁷⁰ A Haber, Ibid., 26 September 2024.

measures, changes in migration policies, or an increased focus on return mechanisms. The peak in 2023 suggests that these measures reached their most intense phase, possibly due to heightened political pressure, increased border security, or policy shifts emphasizing removal. However, the drop in 2024 is notable. While still high, it shows a decline compared to the previous year, suggesting a potential saturation point in enforcement, logistical constraints, or a reduced number of eligible cases for removal. This decrease could also indicate policy adjustments, diplomatic challenges, or shifting migration patterns affecting removals.

4.2. Existing Policies to Enforce Return

Turkey has established comprehensive policies and strategic plans to manage return migration to Afghanistan and Syria. The MoI's 2024-2028 strategic plan¹⁷¹ emphasizes enhancing internal security, migration management, border control, and emergency services coordination within the universal human rights framework. The strategic plan also identifies the increasing external migration to Turkey and the associated social problems and environmental pollution as significant threats. In line with the MoI's 2024-2028 strategic plan, the PMM's 2019-2023 strategic plan¹⁷² highlights potential mass migration movements to Turkey due to regional instabilities and the negative public perception of migration. The PMM's goals include managing regular migration, combating irregular migration, implementing effective IP mechanisms, fighting human trafficking, fostering mutual integration/harmonization and communication, and strengthening institutional capacity.

These two plans can be discussed comparatively under three headings:

- **Evolution of Vision:** The 2019-2023 plan primarily focuses on the logistical aspects of return, aiming to enhance the capacity and coordination of relevant institutions. In contrast, the 2024-2028 plan presents a more holistic vision, incorporating return policies into a broader migration management framework that emphasizes sustainability, reintegration, and international collaboration.
- **Enhanced Capabilities:** The latter plan builds upon the foundations laid by its predecessor, proposing advanced strategies such as monitoring and evaluation mechanisms to ensure the continuous improvement of return operations.
- **Alignment with International Standards:** Both plans demonstrate a commitment to aligning Turkey's return policies with international human rights standards. However, the 2024-2028 plan places greater emphasis on the humane and dignified treatment of returnees, reflecting an increased sensitivity to global best practices.

In summary, the progression from 2019-2023 to the 2024-2028 Strategic Plan indicates a shift towards more comprehensive, sustainable, and internationally coordinated return policies, reflecting Turkey's evolving approach to migration management.

After the May 2023 general elections, the implementation of security-focused migration policies was exemplified by the introduction of mobile migration points and Kalkan (Shield) operations.¹⁷³ In February 2024, Minister of Interior Ali Yerlikaya outlined four-pronged approach to address irregular migration.¹⁷⁴ In particular, regarding the return, neither policy-

¹⁷¹ Ministry of Interior, "Multi-Annual Strategy for 2024-2028", 2024, Available at: https://www.icisleri.gov.tr/kurumlar/icisleri.gov.tr/IcSite/strateji/raporlar/stratejik-planlar/ICISLERI_BAKANLIGI_2024_2028_STRATEJIK_PLANI.pdf (Accessed 26 May 2024).

¹⁷² PMM, "Multi-Annual Strategy for 2019-2023", 2019, Available at: https://www.goc.gov.tr/kurumlar/goc.gov.tr/Mali-Tablolar/STRATEJIK-PLAN-2019-2023/Stratejik_Plan_2019_2023-2.pdf (Accessed 24 May 2024).

¹⁷³ AIDA, "2023 Update AIDA Country Report: Türkiye", 8 August 2024, Available at: <https://ecre.org/aida-country-report-on-turkiye-2023-update/> (Accessed 30 September 2024).

¹⁷⁴ PMM, "İçişleri Bakanımız Sayın Ali Yerlikaya Düzensiz Göçle Mücadelede 4 Strateji Uygulandığını İfade Etti", 2024h, Available at: <https://www.goc.gov.tr/kurumlar/goc.gov.tr/GOC-TV/2024/3-Mart/01-Mart/1Cisleri->

wise nor related to the statistics, the official data is not available; however, the public official statements, particularly the long presentations by the MoI, became an important source for tracing the official policies on return. The below-given policy summary is based on the official statements.

1. **Combating irregular migration at its source:** This involves working with the MoFA to establish readmission agreements and visa policies and increasing returns to safe zones created by Turkey's military interventions in Northern Syria.
2. **Combating irregular migration at the borders:** Enhancing border security through integrated border management and implementing interception measures.
3. **Combating irregular migration internally:** This includes address verification exercises, mobile migration points, data verification projects, registering unregistered Syrians at temporary accommodation centres, enforcing residency in the province of registration, requiring travel permits, closing new registrations in approximately 16 provinces, and restricting address registration in neighbourhoods where the refugee population exceeds 20%.
4. **Increasing deportation of asylum seekers and refugees** who violate the principles and obligations outlined by the LFIP (2013).

According to the 12th Development Plan for 2024-2028 submitted to the Presidency of the Grand National Assembly of Turkey (TBMM), preventive practices will be increased in countries of origin and borders in order to effectively “combat irregular migration”.¹⁷⁵ Because of these policy priorities, integration ceased to be a priority, and funding for projects in this area in particular decreased.¹⁷⁶ To implement such policy priorities and to shift to return over integration, the country utilizes a mix of i) legal frameworks, ii) institutional capacities, iii) proactive cooperation, bilateral agreements and iv) practical measures. Based on the existing framework and the above-mentioned multi-annual plan, LFIP and TPR first provide the legal basis for deportation, voluntary return, and the rights of migrants and refugees. The legal and institutional frameworks underpinning Turkey's return migration policies are designed to balance national security concerns with humanitarian obligations.

Secondly (as a part of the institutional framework), restructuring the Directorate General of Migration Management (DGMM) into the Presidency of Migration Management (PMM) in 2018 marked a significant shift towards a more centralized approach to migration governance. PMM collaborates with international organizations, such as the IOM, the UNHCR, and the ICMPD, to operationalize the return of migrants. These collaborations often include technical assistance programmes that support voluntary return and reintegration into the countries of origin. Operational enforcement involves coordination with international bodies to ensure that returns are conducted in line with international refugee protection standards. PMM has also enhanced its capacity for assisted returns with technical and financial support from the EU and Member States. The ICMPD oversaw the SUPREME Project (“Strengthening Utilization of Additional Policies and Measures for Reinforcing Migration Management in Turkey”) from 2019 to 2021. The SUPREME Project aimed to “provide support to the PMM in strengthening of the policies and procedures, support the functioning of National Assisted Voluntary Return Mechanism, supporting the development of re-integration programme as well as enhancing structured cooperation with countries of origin for effective and sustainable

[Bakanimiz-Sn-Ali-Yerlikaya-Duzensiz-Gocle-Mucadelede-4-Strateji-Uygulandigini-Ifade-Etti.mp4](#) (Accessed 22 May 2024).

¹⁷⁵ Anadolu AgencyAjansı, “Düzensiz göç, kaynak ülkelerde ve sınırlarda önlenecek” 17 October 2023, Available at: <https://www.aa.com.tr/tr/dunya/duzensiz-goc-kaynak-ulkelerde-ve-sinirlarda-onlenecek/3022967> (Accessed 30 September 2024)

¹⁷⁶ AIDA, Ibid., 8 August 2024.

migration management in Turkey”.¹⁷⁷ In 2021, the PMM established its own voluntary return mechanism (N-AVRR) with ICMPD’s technical assistance and national budget financing. While this mechanism allows Afghans to return voluntarily to Afghanistan, it lacks transparency, and the number of returnees is unclear. These returns were temporarily halted following the fall of Kabul but resumed in early 2022 under the banner of ‘voluntary return.’ However, these programmes have faced criticism for potentially blurring the lines between voluntary and coerced returns, particularly given the claims of pressure and intimidation.

Thirdly (as a part of the international cooperation), Turkey has a bilateral agreement-like political document, the EU-Turkey Statement (EUTRS, 2016), with articles related to return and readmission. This country's dossier will further discuss the impact of the EU-Turkey Statement on return migration. Turkey is also a party to the EU-Turkey Readmission Agreement (EUTRA, 2013);), which is important for also playing a significant role in the return of Syrians and Afghans. However, both the EUTRA and EUTRS are currently inactive. The EUTRA had never been implemented for third-country nationals, while the latest readmission as a part of the EUTRS dates back to March 2020.¹⁷⁸

Fourthly (regarding practical measures), the enforcement of return policies includes a range of infrastructural and technological investments. The MoI and the PMM have developed comprehensive systems for migration management, including biometric databases, removal centres, mobile migration points and temporary accommodation centres. These systems are supported by substantial funding from the EU and international organizations. Additionally, Turkey has implemented measures to control the internal movement and registration of migrants. TPR requires Syrians to stay in their province of registration to access rights and services. Address verification exercises and neighbourhood closures have been used to enforce this regulation, although these measures have raised concerns about their impact on refugees’ daily lives, creating an environment of intimidation and limiting access to rights and services. Further practices are discussed under section 5.1.3.2.

In light of the desk research, it was noted that there has been a significant shift from reception, protection, and integration towards return as of 2019. Regarding return policy, interviews conducted during fieldwork indicated another focus on forced returns besides this shift. The fieldwork and interview findings provide a nuanced view of Turkey's return policy, specifically the ways it has handled voluntary and forced returns, including pushbacks, for Syrian and Afghan migrants. There is a strong sense of ambiguity between voluntary and forced returns, with multiple actors acknowledging a growing shift toward forced returns under the guise of "voluntary" programmes.

Interviewees frequently challenge the “voluntary” nature of returns. Many describe a coercive environment in which restrictions on rights and resources indirectly push refugees to leave. For instance, a lawyer highlighted how Turkey’s tightening policies, such as the deactivation of IDs and restricted access to TP status, create situations where Syrians feel they have no choice but to sign voluntary return documents: “They [refugees] sign these forms not because genuinely want to return, but because without an active ID¹⁷⁹, they can’t access basic services like healthcare or education”.¹⁸⁰

¹⁷⁷ ICMPD, “Strengthening Utilization of Additional Policies and Measures for Reinforcing Migration Management in Türkiye” 30 May 2019, Available at: <https://www.icmpd.org/our-work/projects/strengthening-utilization-of-additional-policies-and-measures-for-reinforcing-migration-management-in-tuerkiye-supreme> (Accessed 10 January 2025)

¹⁷⁸ N. Ela Gökcalp Aras, *Ibid.*, 2021.

¹⁷⁹ If they have deactivated ID card, that means they cannot access any basic services and have to live with the fear of apprehension and deportation, so they see signing voluntary return form is only way to get freedom. It is part of the intimidation policy or migrants becoming irregularized, hence no option but return.

¹⁸⁰ SRII WP3 Meso-Level Interview, Izmir-01 (with a nation-wide NGO representative)

For instance, representatives from various organizations reported on the conditions under which Syrians are encouraged or, in some cases, pressured to return. This comment from a field actor underlines the practice where returns are framed as voluntary, though Syrians face implicit pressures, such as ID deactivations and limited movement, which often compel them to opt for return. Moreover, Turkey's use of TACs has increasingly functioned as a form of de facto detention for migrants who are not registered or whose protection status has been revoked. An interviewee explained, "We see the government of Turkey moving on with more insistence on return policy... Ongoing discussions to discuss parameters, reflecting how TACs are used as a policy tool to contain and potentially enforce returns without formalized deportations".¹⁸¹

Indeed, TACs have become a cornerstone of Turkey's strategy to manage and contain the migrant population within its borders. Following the June 2022 policy change, these centres now function as quasi-detention facilities for Syrians who lack TP registration or have revoked their status. An interviewee highlighted that these centres limit refugees' freedom while pressuring them to consider "voluntary" return: "They're detained indefinitely in TACs. Either they sign the voluntary return forms or remain there without any transparent legal process."¹⁸²

Additionally, interviewees mentioned that Syrians face significant pressure to "voluntarily" return due to various administrative hurdles like ID deactivation, limited registration capabilities, and restricted movement. These barriers contribute to a complex interplay between voluntary and forced returns, further compounding challenges for Syrian refugees in Turkey. Thus, Syrians are affected by legal restrictions that indirectly promote return, including the deactivation of IDs, restrictions on movement, and the bureaucratic complications of maintaining legal status. This differentiation appears particularly evident in the experiences shared by legal clinic representatives, where Syrians facing ID deactivation lose access to essential services, which pressures them toward return.¹⁸³

One interviewee from a legal clinic in Gaziantep highlighted that the voluntary return process often intertwines with forced compliance. They explained that "voluntary return forms exist, but the actual action is deportation" and described situations where migrants felt compelled to sign these forms under duress or in poor conditions within removal centres.¹⁸⁴ In parallel, a legal representative explained that the removal centres' poor conditions indirectly encouraged returns. According to this account, removal centres are overcrowded to the point of being "inhumane," pushing individuals to opt for "voluntary" returns as an escape rather than out of genuine willingness; thus, overcrowding is defined as "indirect coercion".¹⁸⁵

The regional dynamics of return are particularly relevant for both Syrians and Afghans. For Syrians, the proximity to the Syrian border allows for voluntary return programmes to the "safe zones" in northern Syria. However, these returns are officially classified as voluntary, but they may be influenced by local conditions, as one NGO representative in Gaziantep remarked: "Many Syrians in this region feel the pressure to return. They are told it's safe, but we know from those who returned back that the situation is still dangerous."¹⁸⁶

The respondents also stated that Turkey's return policy has been shaped by EU pressure and financial incentives. have shaped Turkey's return policy. One interviewee from an intergovernmental organization (IGO) in Istanbul said, "Turkey's national return strategy has

¹⁸¹ SRII WP4 Meso-Level Interview, Ankara-01 (with an IGO representative)

¹⁸² SRII WP3 Meso-Level Interview, İzmir-05 (with a lawyer as a part of an NGO)

¹⁸³ SRII WP4 Meso Level Interview, Gaziantep-03 (with a NGO representative)

¹⁸⁴ SRII WP4 Meso Level Interview, Gaziantep-04 (with a lawyer in Bar Association)

¹⁸⁵ SRII WP4 Meso Level Interview, Gaziantep-04 (with a lawyer in Bar Association)

¹⁸⁶ SRII WP4 Meso-Level Interview, Istanbul-02 (with a nation-wide NGO representative)

evolved significantly since 2016, particularly with the EU-Turkey Statement. The focus has shifted from just containing the refugee population to actually encouraging voluntary returns, especially for Syrians¹⁸⁷ This aligns with broader national migration goals of managing a large refugee population while balancing EU expectations.

It is also stated that implementation heavily depends on the resources available to local authorities and their capacity to manage returns. Local actors, particularly lawyers and NGOs, play a crucial role in assisting refugees during the return process; as a lawyer in Izmir pointed out: “We often deal with cases where refugees, especially Syrians, are pressured into signing voluntary return forms. It’s our job to ensure they know their rights and that they aren’t being forced to return”.¹⁸⁸ This highlights the local scale where individual cases are handled with significant variation depending on the location and access to legal resources.

Pushbacks are another area of concern highlighted by the interviewees. Pushbacks reflect Turkey’s security-focused stance on migration management, designed to prevent irregular entry but criticized for lacking due process and humanitarian considerations. Interviews from the field indicated that Afghans, especially single men, have experienced pushbacks at Turkey’s eastern borders without due assessment of their protection needs, contravening the principle of non-refoulement. One interviewee noted that the “main bulk of our assistance shifted over time to include those also under international protection or the ones that need this protection, yet most of them were being apprehended or pushed back”,¹⁸⁹ indicating the severity of Turkey’s approach to irregular migration and the difficult position of humanitarian actors in this context.

Interviews recount that Afghans, among others, are regularly prevented from entering Turkey or are sent back to Iran without legal assessments for asylum. One field expert described how pushbacks have become an important component of Turkey’s migration policy, often executed with state coordination: “Pushbacks are common now. Local authorities even provide supplies like thermal blankets to keep things organized. It’s not like before; it’s now a mechanism.”¹⁹⁰

For Afghans, the eastern regions bordering Iran also play a crucial role in shaping return practices. An interviewee in Van reflects, “In Van and Iğdir, Afghan returns are frequent. These are not voluntary like with Syrians; many Afghans are deported within days of being apprehended at the border”.¹⁹¹

The political landscape evolved with the Taliban’s takeover of Afghanistan in 2021, intensifying pressures at the Iran border and increasing public scrutiny of the refugee situation in Turkey. In response, starting from December 2021, the PMM’s verification project, together with the UNHCR and the EU funds since 2017,¹⁹² is accelerated, and a new measure called “address verification”¹⁹³ through an internal circular sent by the MoI. Law enforcement units carry out address verification in coordination with PDMMs throughout the country. The objective was to enforce the existing law and legislation limiting Syrians from staying in the

¹⁸⁷ SRII WP4 Meso-Level Interview, İstanbul-03 (with a Syrian-founded NGO representative)

¹⁸⁸ SRII WP3 Meso-Level Interview, Izmir-01 (with a nation-wide NGO representative)

¹⁸⁹ SRII WP4 Meso Level Interviews, Ankara- 04 (with a supranational organization representative/ Eurocrat)

¹⁹⁰ SRII WP4 Meso Level Interview, İstanbul- 03 (with a Syrian-founded NGO representative)

¹⁹¹ SRII WP4 Meso-Level Interview, Van-04 (with a local journalist)

¹⁹² Global Compact on Refugees, “Verification of the personal data of foreigners under international protection and temporary protection”, 2024, Available at: <https://globalcompactrefugees.org/good-practices/verification-personal-data-foreigners-under-international-protection-and-temporary> (Accessed 18 May 2024).

¹⁹³ As per article 50 of Population Services Law (Law no 5490) and article 26 of LFIP (Law no 6458), Turkish citizens and foreigners (including Syrians under Temporary Protection and foreigners with residence permit) are obliged to register their current residence address which is recorded through Göç-Net (Turkey’s Migration Database managed by PMM) and MERNIS databases.

province of registration to access rights and services. Throughout the exercise, law enforcement units (LEUs) visited refugee households under temporary and international protection at their declared addresses to verify information from the Migration Database of Turkey (Göç-Net). The impact was also visible for Syrians, and it is seen that with the deactivation of status, around 600,000 Syrians under TP were deactivated in 2022. While over 160,000 people have had their status reinstated, many have been forced to relocate to their initial province of registration or risk continuing without the legal status that allows them to access public services and formal work.¹⁹⁴ As an early outcome of the address verification exercise and to balance the social tension, 1,200 neighbourhoods where the proportion of all foreigners exceeds 25% of the total neighbourhood population are closed for the new registration¹⁹⁵. According to the announcement, except for new-born, nuclear family reunification, and those who prove their residence in closed neighbourhoods before 3 December 2021, these neighbourhoods are closed for temporary and IP) registration, residence permit, and city change procedures for foreigners under IP, TP, and residence permit holders.

Several interviews implicate that returns may sometimes take place under strict conditions that could be perceived as coercive. One interviewee from Van describes, "...when migrants are caught at the border, they are often immediately sent back to Iran without official documentation, bypassing any formal return process"¹⁹⁶ This approach appears to be shaped by political pressures and public security considerations. However, interviews suggest that its implementation may sometimes pose challenges to the rights and safety of returnees, particularly in border regions. Another interviewee in Van highlights the severity of these pushbacks, noting cases where migrants are "...stripped and forced to cross back into Iran during the winter, with many risking hypothermia."¹⁹⁷

Voluntary return programmes are officially promoted, especially for Syrians. Briefly, Voluntary returns represent the third major type of return migration in Turkey's infrastructure, facilitated through incentives and assistance programmes. Turkey, with support from international organizations such as the International Organization for Migration (IOM), has established a reintegration assistance programme (Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration, AVRR) aimed at promoting voluntary return as an alternative to forced repatriation since 2009¹⁹⁸, then the national AVRR (N-AVRR) with the International Centre for Migration Policy Development (ICMPD) in 2019.¹⁹⁹ However, the fieldwork interviews reflected that certain factors, such as restricted access to services and the deactivation of identification cards, may create indirect pressures that influence individuals' decisions to return. In this context, some returnees may feel they have limited options. As one NGO representative describes, "The reality is that people return because conditions make it almost impossible to stay... they are compelled to sign voluntary return forms to avoid worse consequences."²⁰⁰

Meanwhile, while Syrians generally have more access to structured voluntary return pathways, Afghan migrants often face more challenging conditions and are at higher risk of immediate

¹⁹⁴ UNDP and UNHCR, *Ibid.*, 2024.

¹⁹⁵ PMM, "Mahalle Kapatma Duyurusu Hk.", 30 June 2022, Available at: <https://www.goc.gov.tr/mahalle-kapatma-duyurusu-hk2> (Accessed 18 May 2024).

¹⁹⁶ SRII WP4 Meso-Level Interview, Van-03 (with a journalist)

¹⁹⁷ SRII WP4 Meso-Level Interview, Van-06 (with a NGO representative)

¹⁹⁸ IOM, "Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration", 2024. Available at: <https://turkiye.iom.int/assisted-voluntary-return-and-reintegration#:~:text=The%20AVRR%20programme%20facilitates%20the,return%20and%20rebuild%20their%20lives> (Accessed 2 October 2024).

¹⁹⁹ ICMPD, *Ibid.*, 6 June 2024.

²⁰⁰ SRII WP4 Meso-Level Interview, Van-06 (with a NGO representative)

removal. Political considerations and security concerns associated with Afghan migration contribute to stricter enforcement measures. As one interviewee from Iğdir observed, “For Afghans, there is little choice... if caught, they are immediately sent back without any process.”

²⁰¹

The interviews imply that Turkey’s border enforcement practices, particularly along its eastern and western borders, may at times involve elements resembling pushbacks. The EU representative stated that the EU-funded humanitarian assistance has occasionally intersected with efforts to monitor and mitigate these pushbacks, primarily on the western border through ASAM, which provides legal support to those apprehended. The representative pointed out the limitations and political challenges faced, explaining, “The humanitarian space to operate on the western border was relatively open by the government of Turkey because it touched upon something they were keen on documenting, which is the pushbacks at the western border. When it comes to the eastern borders, it’s a different story.”²⁰²

The interviews further reveal also the EU’s constrained ability to monitor pushbacks along the eastern border with Iran, where irregular migrants, particularly Afghans, are frequently pushed back without due process or legal assessment of protection needs. The lack of reliable data is problematic, as the EU representative admitted, “we have very little data” on the eastern border pushbacks, only partial reports, leaving a gap in comprehensively understanding these forced returns.²⁰³

In conclusion, the interviews suggest that Turkey’s return policy operates in a complex landscape where the distinction between voluntary and forced returns is sometimes unclear. The findings indicate the presence of border enforcement measures and the establishment of TACs, which function with varying degrees of legal oversight. Within this framework, refugees may face challenging conditions that influence their decision to return.

4.3. Operational Infrastructures of Return Migration Governance

4.3.1. Return-Related Actors

Turkey’s institutional structure displays the characteristics of multilevel governance, with central state actors being the most crucial layer of multi-levelness.²⁰⁴ The complex structure of actors, layers, policies and execution capacities at central, local, and inter-regional levels indicates the country’s dynamic nature of migration management. The Presidency holds the political power to order limitations or suspend TP in case of a risk to national security, public order or health (TPR, 2014 Article 15). The MoI serves as the main ministry dealing with IP and TP and has extensive responsibilities through the PMM, which the LFIP established as Directorate General status in 2013, then transformed to Presidency status with enhanced roles and responsibilities in 2018 and renamed in 2021.²⁰⁵ The PMM is responsible for activities to implement policies and strategies related to the field of migration, ensure coordination among

²⁰¹ SRII Meso-Level Interviews, Iğdir-04 (with a border village mukhtar)

²⁰² SRII WP4 Meso-Level Interview, Ankara- 04 (with a supranational organization representative/ Eurocrat)

²⁰³ Ibid.

²⁰⁴ Zeynep Şahin-Mencütek, et. al, Ibid, 2023.

²⁰⁵ Presidential Decree No 85 provides the legal basis of restructuring and re-naming Directorate General on Migration Management, into the Presidency of Migration Management. With this amendment PMM is formed as a central executive institution with the authority over migration and international protection affairs. <https://www.resmigazete.gov.tr/eskiler/2021/10/20211029-35.pdf> (Accessed 23 May 2024).

institutions and organizations related to these issues, and manage the entry and stay of foreigners in Turkey, their departure from Turkey, and their deportation, as well as the processes related to international protection, TP, and the protection of victims of human trafficking.²⁰⁶ The PMM is equipped with various technologies (such as Göç-Net – biometric migration management database), materials and infrastructures (such as TACs, Removal CentresCenters, Verification CentresCenters MMPs, and GÖKSEM), policies and institutional capacities (such as LFIP, TPR, N-AVRR programme) to reach its migration management objectives.

As stipulated in its 2019-2023²⁰⁷ and 2024-2028²⁰⁸ strategic plans, MoI aims to provide effective coordination on domestic security, migration, border management, and disaster management to ensure safety. It includes establishing technologically supported and integrated border management and patrolling roads to improve effective intervention at borders. It has a 1,160 km integrated security and border management system at the Southeast and Eastern borders.²⁰⁹ The MoI and PMM also developed the Migration Strategy Paper and executed these strategies through national and international cooperation and coordination.²¹⁰ In line with these strategies and through the EU funds, the MoI has a functioning National Coordination & Joint Risk Analysis Centre (NACORAC) and Integrated Border Management (IBM) Database to enable inter-agency cooperation and to pave the way for sharing data, combining derived data in a common database. Indeed, these cases illustrate how Turkey's return policies are increasingly influenced by surveillance-driven governance, where migrants are categorized through automated systems rather than direct human assessment. These digital infrastructures raise concerns about the extent to which returns remain voluntary or whether, as migrants flagged and tracked within this system, they find themselves with no real alternative but to accept repatriation. Moreover, it may have limited alternatives.

Furthermore, as these mechanisms are funded by the EU, they reflect broader externalization policies, highlighting Europe's indirect role in shaping return dynamics beyond its borders. This vignette highlights how return policies are not just only legal or political decisions but are also deeply intertwined with technological infrastructures that facilitate control, systems that support migration management through monitoring, and, ultimately, the enforcement of migration management. The Disaster and Emergency Management Authority (AFAD) had a mandate to coordinate their reception needs at the beginning of the Syrian Civil War. In cooperation with the relevant line ministries, public institutions, organizations, and the TRC, AFAD provided or contributed to housing, shelter, health, security, social activities, education, worship, interpreting, communication, banking and similar services in container and tent cities.²¹¹ In 2018, PMM took over managing TACs and providing services from AFAD.

Additionally, Turkey's cross-border operations and intervention in Northern Syria created a need for AFAD's support to the camps that were established to accommodate internally displaced Syrians to prevent their crossing into Turkey, particularly camps or prefabricated housing. In addition to AFAD, Turkey's institutional architecture also has actors governing return migration. The MoFA handles bilateral cooperation and diplomatic dialogues with

²⁰⁶ Ministry of Interior, "Göç İdaresi Başkanlığı", 2024, Available at: <https://www.icisleri.gov.tr/goc-idaresi-baskanligi-hizmet> (Accessed 23 May 2024).

²⁰⁷ Ministry of Interior, "Multi-Annual Strategy for 2019-2023", 2019, Available at: https://www.icisleri.gov.tr/kurumlar/icisleri.gov.tr/IcSite/strateji/%C5%9EEREF/ICISLERI-BAKANLIGI-2019_2023-STRATEJIK-PLANI.pdf (Accessed 25 May 2024).

²⁰⁸ Ministry of Interior, *Ibid.*, 2024.

²⁰⁹ PMM, "İçişleri Bakanımız Sayın Ali Yerlikaya Sınırlarımızdaki Üst Düzey Güvenlik Tedbirlerini Anlattı", 2024, Available at: <https://www.goc.gov.tr/kurumlar/goc.gov.tr/GOC-TV/2024/3-Mart/01-Mart/3Icisleri-Bakanimiz-Sayin-Ali-Yerlikaya-Sinirlarimizdaki-Ust-Duzey-Guvenlik-Onlemlerini-Anlatti.mp4> (Accessed 23 May 2024).

²¹⁰ Yabancılar İletişim Merkezi (YİMER), "Göç Strateji Belgesi", 2024, Available at: <https://yimer.gov.tr/TR/Legis/bb1b8b20-6046-4204-9da8-cbe4985d5ead> (Accessed 25 May 2024).

²¹¹ Zeynep Şahin-Mencütek, *vd.*, *Ibid.*, 2023.

countries of origin, facilitating the preparation of travel documents. The TİKA engages in the reintegration stage by incorporating returnees' needs into community-based development projects in origin countries, such as Afghanistan, Pakistan, and Bangladesh.

The Gendarmerie, Police, and Land/Coast Guard Commands play significant roles in the return migration process within Turkey. As part of the Turkish state architecture, these entities fall under the umbrella of the MoI, which is responsible for maintaining public order and security. The Gendarmerie operates primarily in rural areas, overseeing law enforcement and public safety, and is pivotal in identifying and processing migrants in these areas. The Police handle similar responsibilities within urban settings, ensuring compliance with migration laws, and often execute security checks, address verifications and carry out referrals and transfer to removal centres where migrants may be held before their return. The Land and Coast Guard Commands focus on border security and control, intercepting illegal entries and exits, thus directly impacting the flow of migrants.²¹²

Semi-state associations like the TRC have a "Migration and Refugee Services Department". In response to the Syrian Civil War and mass migration movement, TRC launched the "Syrian Crisis Humanitarian Relief Operation" on 29 April 2011 to contribute to the logistics of the cross-border operations of all humanitarian actors responding from Turkey to Syria. Furthermore, the TRC has an observatory role concerning the voluntary returns of Syrians who want to return to their country voluntarily.²¹³ The TRC also offers pre-return counselling and coordinates with Red Crescent societies in the countries of origin, especially in implementing the N-AVRR programme targeting non-Syrian migrants.

The ICMPD²¹⁴ provides technical and operational assistance to the N-AVRR programme, supporting policy and programme development aimed at promoting voluntary return and reintegration. The UN, primarily through the UNHCR and the IOM, provides critical support for the protection and return of refugees. These organizations work in close coordination with the Turkish government and other international partners to ensure that returns are conducted safely, dignifiedly, and sustainably. The IOM also supports the AVRR programme by providing comprehensive services, including counselling, logistical support, travel arrangements, health assessments, and financial aid. IOM collaborates with local authorities and NGOs to ensure effective and sustainable reintegration. In agreement with the Government of Turkey, the UNHCR²¹⁵ observes voluntary returns to Syria and regularly attends interviews at PDMM Offices, including at three border locations, namely Gaziantep Karkamis, Kilis Oncupinar and Sanliurfa Akcakale²¹⁶ border gates. In Southeast Turkey, the UNHCR is present at three border crossing points 5 days a week: Öncüpinar (Kilis), Karkamis (Gaziantep), and Akcakale (Sanliurfa). Before the earthquakes of 6 February 2023, UNHCR was also present 5 days a week at PDMM offices in Hatay, Gaziantep and Sanliurfa. Since the earthquakes, voluntary return interviews have no longer been conducted by the PDMM in Gaziantep. PDMM Hatay resumed activities, and since October 6, the UNHCR has attended voluntary return interviews at the PDMM Office.

The UNHCR continues to be present twice a week at the PDMM office in Adana and the PDMM in Sanliurfa when requested. UNHCR has not been asked to observe voluntary return

²¹² Ibid.

²¹³ N. Ela Gökalp Aras and Zeynep Şahin Mencütek, *Ibid.*, 2019.

²¹⁴ ICMPD, *Ibid.*, 28 March 2022.

²¹⁵ UNHCR, "Operational Data Portal, Syria Regional Refugee Response: Durable Solutions", 2024c, available at: https://data.unhcr.org/en/situations/syria_durable_solutions (Accessed 24 May 2024).

²¹⁶ As per instruction by the Sub-Governorate on management of Customs areas at border points, UNHCR has not been attending voluntary return interviews at Akcakale border gate since 04 Dec 2023. UNHCR access to Akcakale border gate is in discussion with PDMM Sanliurfa.

interviews by PDMM offices in Kahramanmaraş, Osmaniye, Malatya, Adıyaman or Mardin, reportedly because there were either no or very few applications.²¹⁷ UNHCR was also involved in the RSD procedure, which was transferred to the PMM in 2018.²¹⁸ Concerning these findings, it can be said that the UNHCR was previously involved in the RDS process, which was transferred to the PMM in 2018. In this context, the evolving role of UNHCR in Turkey's return procedures raises significant concerns and questions about its capacity to uphold its protection mandate.

The UNHCR's involvement in voluntary return interviews could lend legitimacy to be seen as contributing to the oversight of state-led return policies rather than ensuring, but concerns remain about the extent to which this ensures true voluntariness. In some provinces, the absence of UNHCR oversight in several provinces, coupled with its restricted and limited capacity to intervene, raises the question of whether it is enabling "forced voluntary returns" by participating in a process shaped by the Turkish government. The questions arise about the nature of return decisions and the level of choice available to returnees. If individuals face increasingly difficult conditions and limited legal protections, their decision to return may be influenced by these challenges rather than being entirely voluntary. Ultimately, the UNHCR appears to be operating within this framework, maintaining some monitoring functions but with limited influence over return policies. This situation risks its role to be symbolic rather than protective. If it cannot meaningfully ensure that returns are voluntary, safe, and dignified, its presence may serve more to legitimize returns than to safeguard refugee rights.

Among the intergovernmental actors, the fieldwork reflected that the UNHCR is seen as a critical "broker" between the EU and Turkey, tasked with advocating for protection standards and safe, voluntary returns for Syrians. The organization emphasizes the necessity for returns to meet three primary criteria—safety, voluntariness, and dignity. However, UNHCR faces significant constraints due to both financial limitations and the political complexities involved in its partnership with Turkish authorities. As noted by one interviewee, "UNHCR remains the most principled broker in town," indicating a preference for UNHCR to mediate the relationship between the EU and Turkish authorities over direct involvement by the EU, as UNHCR maintains a stronger focus on principled, rights-based approaches.²¹⁹ However, the IOM is mentioned more in terms of its operational involvement. The interviewees emphasized that the involvement of IOM aligns with Turkey's operational goals for migration control and EU-funded projects that promote managed returns, though IOM has limitations in directly influencing policy on enforced returns. On the other hand, the ICMPD is mentioned with its technical and policy support but not as collaborating with even the national NGOs, but mainly the high-level bureaucracy.

In addition to central-level state and non-state actors, there are also local actors such as provincial branches of PMM, provincial and district governorates, border management authorities, police stations and removal centre management that facilitate the return programmes at the local level. Even though municipalities have no direct influence on the return migration, few municipalities are involved in the transportation to border gates in coordination with PDMM offices. For instance, Istanbul's Esenyurt municipality has been organizing return campaigns since 2018, including trips to the Syrian border to support the return of around 3,500 Syrians.²²⁰

²¹⁷ SRII WP4 Meso-Level Interview, Gaziantep-01 (with an IGO representative)

²¹⁸ UNHCR, "UNHCR tarafından kayıt ve MSB", 2024d, Available at: <https://help.unhcr.org/turkiye/tr/information-for-non-syrians/registration-rsd-with-unhcr/> (Accessed 24 May 2024).

²¹⁹ SRII WP4 Meso-Level Interview- Ankara-04 (with a supranational organization representative/Eurocrat)

²²⁰ Esenyurt Municipality, "57 Suriyeli Daha Esenyurt'tan Ülkelerine Döndü", 2022, Available at: https://www.esenyurt.bel.tr/home/IcerikDetay?HABERLER=57_Suriyeli_Daha_Esenyurt%E2%80%99tan_%C3%9Clkelerine_D%C3%B6nd%C3%BC&&id=13890 (Accessed 22 May 2024).

In Turkey, various non-state actors play significant roles in the realm of migration, particularly in supporting and advocating for migrants and refugees. Among the most active civil society organizations are the Association for Social Development and Aid Mobilization (ASAM), Foundation for Human Rights and Freedoms and Humanitarian Relief (IHH), and Bar Associations, which are especially involved in matters related to detention, deportations, and other legal issues. Additionally, international organizations like the HRW, the AI, the Syrian Observatory for Human Rights (SOHR) and the Syrian Association for Citizens' Dignity (SACD) are prominent in monitoring and reporting on the conditions faced by migrants and refugees in Turkey. Resistance to Turkey's increasing deportations comes mainly from civil society organizations, bar associations, and international advocacy groups. ASAM and Bar Associations provide legal support to prevent unlawful deportations, while IHH and international actors like HRW, AI, SOHR, and SACD document rights violations and challenge the notion that Syria is safe for return. The Turkish government's securitized migration policies, coupled with EU funding for migration management and return programs, create an environment where deportations are facilitated rather than prevented. While the EU supports humanitarian aid, it does not actively oppose deportations, making resistance fragmented and largely reactive. Civil society efforts focus on case-by-case interventions rather than a unified challenge to the return turn.

State officials working in governorates, police stations, and removal centres interpret signatures on voluntary return forms as indications of consent, though concerns have been raised that some of these signatures may have been obtained under pressure. Non-state actors, including lawyers and rights-based organizations, question the extent to which these returns are truly voluntary. While legal interventions often face significant challenges, they still have an impact—for example, preventing an individual deportation or reactivating the registration of a person facing removal. Unlike in European countries like the UK, Germany, Austria, or the Netherlands, independent civil society organizations have not played any counselling or execution role in assisted voluntary returns due to the general suspicion of the Turkish government toward civil society and sensitivity around return and migration issues.²²¹

4.3.2. The Role of the EU Regarding Return Migration Governance

The EU plays a pivotal role in shaping Turkey's return migration governance, particularly regarding Syrians and Afghans. This influence is primarily exerted through financial support, policy alignment, and externalization strategies that position Turkey as a key buffer state. The EUTRS (2016) and subsequent agreements reflect the EU's focus on curbing irregular migration and reinforcing return mechanisms. While financial assistance has bolstered Turkey's migration management capacity, it has also led to a securitized and often coercive return framework, raising ethical concerns about the balance between migration control and human rights.

Since 2015, Europe's asylum policy has moved away from inclusionary policies to exclusionary policies with an agenda to focus on return programmes. This shift has also influenced the migration management policies and practices in Turkey and increased the significant emphasis on the voluntary return of migrants as a means to justify the removal of the 'undesirable' or 'unwanted' population. The EU has been increasing its focus on return

²²¹ Zeynep Şahin Mencütek, "The Institutionalization of Voluntary Returns in Turkey", *Migration and Society*, 2023, Available at: <https://www.berghahnjournals.com/view/journals/migration-and-society/5/1/arms050105.xml> (Accessed 24 May 2024).

policies, and the New Pact on Migration and Asylum (Pact)²²², proposed by the European Commission in September 2020, represents a comprehensive framework aimed at strengthening EU-wide migration management and cooperation with neighbouring countries, including Turkey. On April 10th 2024, after longstanding negotiations and despite the intense critiques, the European Parliament adopted the Pact, which entered into force on 11 June 2024 and will enter into the application after two years.²²³ Given Turkey's strategic role as a key transit and host country for refugees and migrants, this Pact is expected to shape future collaboration between the EU and Turkey, particularly in the areas of return policies and border management.

One of the central elements of the Pact is its emphasis on more efficient and standardized return procedures, thus enhancing cooperation on returns. This focus aligns with Turkey's objectives of controlling irregular migration at its borders, particularly with Syria and Afghanistan. Since the EUTRS, Turkey has received substantial financial and technical support for migration management, and the Pact could further this by streamlining return mechanisms and promoting Turkey as a "safe third country." The establishment of "return sponsorships" by EU member states under the Pact may facilitate Turkey's role in managing returns from the EU and third countries. The EU-funded projects reflect the externalization of EU migration policies, reinforcing Turkey's role in preventing onward migration to Europe by strengthening return mechanisms and detention capacities. While some projects emphasize voluntary return and human rights compliance, the overarching strategy aligns with EU efforts to enhance migration containment through financial and institutional support to Turkey. Such investments are expected to continue under the Pact, aligning with Turkey's priority of securing its borders and managing migration flows from Syria and Iran.

The Pact's legislative procedures have been ongoing since 2020, and significant progress was marked by the European Parliament's approval of key elements in April 2023. This sets the stage for formal implementation by 2025, with tangible impacts on the EU-Turkey migration cooperation likely to emerge around this timeframe. With Turkey's role as a "buffer zone" for Europe, the Pact's timelines are critical as they align with Turkey's own evolving migration policies, particularly in return practices. However, it would not be wrong to say that the Pact will likely strengthen collaboration between the EU and Turkey, specifically regarding return policies and border security, with continued EU funding shaping Turkey's significant regional role regarding migration.

From a broader perspective, more focused on Turkey in terms of returns, the EU-Turkey Readmission Agreement (EUTRA, 2013) should be mentioned. A readmission agreement between the EU and Turkey has been on Brussels' agenda since the late 1990s, but negotiations continued until 16 December 2013, when the EUTRA was signed pending ratification (in 2014). The EUTRA could not be used for third-country nationals (TCNs) even after the transition period (2017,) due to the administrative measures taken by Turkey based on delays regarding the visa exemption process.²²⁴ On 22 July 2019, the Turkish government publicly announced the suspension of the EUTRA in response to the EU sanctioning Turkey's gas

²²² European Commission, "The Pact on Migration and Asylum", 21 May 2024, Available at: https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies/migration-and-asylum/pact-migration-and-asylum_en (Accessed 08 February 2025).

²²³ Ibid.

²²⁴ N. Ela Gokalp Aras, "A Game Changer in EU-Turkey Relations: The Opportunities and Pitfalls of Migration Policy", *The International Spectator*, Vol. (54)4, 47-61, 2019, Available at: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/03932729.2019.1670481?journalCode=rspe20> (Accessed 4 February 2025).

drilling operations in Cypriot waters²²⁵, but more importantly, due to the delays of the agreed-on visa-free regime for Turkish citizens.²²⁶ Thus, the EUTRA could not be implemented.

Regarding return, the EUTRS of 2016 is a pivotal point in understanding Turkey's approach to return migration. This Statement, aimed at stemming the flow of irregular migration to Europe, essentially positioned Turkey as a gatekeeper, reducing the number of arrivals in Greece, which continued with significantly lower numbers in the subsequent years and ended as of March 2020 with COVID-19. The agreement aimed to decrease irregular migration and included provisions for returning migrants not eligible for asylum in the EU back to Turkey in exchange for financial aid and other political incentives for Turkey. Despite the criticisms regarding its humanitarian implications, the EUTRS has been considered effective in reducing irregular arrivals to Europe and has shaped future European migration diplomacy, including other bilateral agreements to manage migration flows.²²⁷ The renewal of the Statement has been on the table for a long time, with the EU and Turkey having different demands for a new consensus. This political agreement has not been in effect since March 2020. In later periods, debates emerged about the conditions under which the Statement would be renewed, and the expectations of both Turkey and the EU were expressed. However, after 2020, particularly starting in 2019, Turkey's return policy became a more securitized and centralized policy area, so the EU's support shifted significantly towards helping Turkey develop its national return policy by focusing on capacity building. As a result, even though the EU's influence became less visible, fieldwork has shown that its impact still manifests in fragmented ways. The period between 2020-2024, describing the EU's influence as 'silent but significant',²²⁸ would be a fitting analogy to understand its role as the driving force behind Turkey's return policy.

Briefly, the EU's overall impact on Turkey's return policy can be summarized through its emphasis on keeping refugees within Turkey's borders. While the EU's funding has provided Turkey with the capacity to manage a large refugee population, it has also placed Turkey in a position where it must balance EU demands with domestic pressures. The EU significantly shapes Turkey's return policy for Syrians and Afghans through financial assistance, infrastructure support, and strategic policy frameworks. Since the EUTRS, the EU has provided substantial funding to strengthen Turkey's migration management capacity, with investments exceeding €11 billion for border security, asylum processing, and return infrastructure.²²⁹

The role, motivations, and impacts of the EU on Turkey's return governance can be analysed under the following subheadings:

Motivations: Externalization of Migration Control and Political

The EU's primary motivation in influencing Turkey's return policy is migration containment—preventing irregular migration flows into Europe. The 2015 migration crisis prompted a shift from reception and protection towards deterrence and return-based strategies.

The EU exerts political pressure on Turkey to maintain its role as a gatekeeper for Europe. Turkey's return policies, including voluntary and forced returns, are significantly shaped by

²²⁵ Euractiv, "Turkey suspends deal with the EU on migrant readmission", 2019, Available at: <https://www.euractiv.com/section/global-europe/news/turkey-suspends-deal-with-the-eu-on-migrant-readmission/> (Accessed 3 February 2025).

²²⁶ Daily Sabah, "Readmission agreement with EU no longer functional, Ankara says", 23 July, 2021. <https://www.dailysabah.com/eu-affairs/2019/07/23/readmission-agreement-with-eu-no-longer-functional-ankara-says> (Accessed 3 February 2025)

²²⁷N. Ela Gokalp Aras, Ibid, 2021.

²²⁸ This expression has been used specifically to convey the meaning of "sessiz ama derinden (quiet but profound)" as it is understood in Turkish.

²²⁹ Zia Weise, et. al, "The EU is helping Turkey forcibly deport migrants to Syria and Afghanistan", *Politico*, 11 October 2024, Available at: <https://www.politico.eu/article/the-eu-is-helping-turkey-forcibly-deport-migrants-to-syria-and-afghanistan/> (Accessed 17 October 2024).

the EU's externalization approach along with the national needs and policy development. The EU's goal is to prevent migrants from reaching Europe, and this has influenced how Turkey manages its border controls and return processes. By making Turkey responsible for a significant portion of migration management, the EU ensures that returns—whether voluntary or coerced—align with its broader goal of reducing irregular migration into Europe.

Turkey's migration strategy, particularly its focus on returning irregular migrants, has been significantly impacted by the EU's desire to externalize migration control, keeping refugees and migrants in Turkey rather than allowing them to transit through to Europe. The EUTS itself can be seen as a product of this political dynamic, where the EU has sought to limit the number of irregular migrants reaching its borders by securing Turkey's cooperation. This political agreement strengthened the EU's role as one of the key players in defining Turkey's return policy along with the national security concerns (particularly in response to mass refugee inflows from Iraq (1991), Syria (2011), and Afghanistan as well as the increasing number of irregular migrants, thus the growing pressures to develop its legal and administrative frameworks). Through agreements like the EUTRS, the EU effectively outsourced the responsibility of managing migration flows to Turkey. This externalization strategy ensures that Turkey is not only responsible for hosting refugees but also for returning those deemed irregular or whose asylum claims have been rejected.

Syrians and Afghans, as two of the largest refugee groups in Turkey, are central to these efforts. For Syrians, the EU prioritizes preventing secondary movements to Europe by ensuring they remain in Turkey under TP. For Afghans, the EU is motivated by concerns over irregular migration, particularly in light of the Taliban takeover in 2021, which raised fears of increased Afghan arrivals in Europe. However, Afghans do not receive the same level of political or financial attention as Syrians, as their movement remains largely contained within Turkey and Iran.

Main Strategies and Tools

The EU externalizes migration management by delegating return responsibilities to Turkey through financial incentives, political agreements, and legal frameworks. The EU employs financial assistance, capacity-building programs, and policy alignment measures to shape Turkey's return governance. Financially, Turkey has received over €11 billion in migration-related funding, including investments in return mechanisms, border control, and detention infrastructure. Programs like the Facility for Refugees in Turkey (FRIT) and IPA-funded return projects strengthen Turkey's ability to track, detain, and return migrants. Capacity-building efforts focus on integrating Turkey's migration management systems, such as the Göç-Net database, with EU migration control frameworks. The EU also uses diplomatic leverage, conditioning visa liberalization and economic cooperation on Turkey's compliance with return and border management expectations.

One of the primary ways the EU drives Turkey's return policy is through financial incentives and support, which has been and is still mainly used to develop the national return mechanism. However, due to the securitisation and highly centralized structure, seeing the results of this support requires time and searching for secondary sources.

The EU has provided substantial funding to Turkey through FRIT, which has delivered over €6 billion to help Turkey manage its refugee population, which divided into two funding phases: the first covering projects up to mid-2021 and the second financing initiatives until

mid-2025 (nearly €5.4 billion has already been used).²³⁰ Beyond the FRIT, the EU allocated an additional €3.5 billion (2020 and 2023) to sustain ongoing programs that distributed as follows: €1 billion for humanitarian relief, €781 million for essential needs, €595.6 million for education, €260 million for healthcare, €474 million for economic empowerment, and €400 million for migration governance and thus altogether, the EU's financial commitment to supporting refugees and host communities in Turkey from 2011 to 2023 has reached approximately €10 billion.²³¹

This funding is conditional on Turkey implementing policies that align with the EU's migration control objectives, including voluntary return programmes for refugees, particularly Syrians. These financial flows enable Turkey to build the infrastructure necessary for managing returns, including removal centres, border control mechanisms, and integration support for those remaining in the country. Through these funds, voluntary return mechanisms that encourage refugees to return to their countries of origin, especially to Syria, have also been established. Although framed as voluntary, these programmes are supported by EU funds, which have been instrumental in creating a return infrastructure. This makes the EU a financial backer of Turkey's broader migration and return policies, shaping how returns are organized and executed.

The financial backing provided by the EU has had a profound influence on Turkey's ability to manage its sizeable Syrian refugee population. Funds have been directed toward improving refugee integration and voluntary return programmes, which have been criticized as coerced in practice. Interviews with legal practitioners and NGOs in Turkey emphasize that while these returns are officially classified as voluntary, they are often driven by poor living conditions, legal uncertainty, and economic pressure, making them involuntary in practice. An interviewee with the EU representative in Ankara noted, "Syrians are signing voluntary return agreements because they feel trapped. They have no stable future here, and the EU funding is not doing enough to support real integration."²³²

As stipulated in the "IPA Annual Action Programme for Turkey 2019", the intermediate objective of the EU is to strengthen Turkey's legal and administrative framework for managing irregular migration in line with the EU *acquis* and EU standards.²³³ The EU has significantly shaped Turkey's migration management through its externalization policies, primarily using different funding instruments. In particular, concerning return, the EU has supported refurbishing and maintaining existing removal centres and the construction of new ones with the above-mentioned projects.²³⁴ Additionally, liaison offices and guest houses for readmission have been established. Border security was another area to enhance through the modernization of surveillance systems at both eastern and western borders, and the Turkish Coast Guard's capacity for search and rescue operations has been increased. The implementation of integrated border management strategies has complemented these improvements. The asylum and protection systems in Turkey have been strengthened with EU support. This includes the development of high-quality asylum procedures and improved registration and verification systems for refugees and asylum seekers. Alongside these measures, the EU has backed the development of pathways to viable alternatives to administrative detention and the implementation of effective voluntary return programmes.

²³⁰ European Commission, "The EU Facility for Refugees in Turkey", 2023a, Available at: https://enlargement.ec.europa.eu/document/download/3967c96e-e3c5-47fc-8cao-88141d3d0594_en?filename=frit_factsheet.pdf; European Commission, "The Facility for Refugees in Turkey", 2024, Available at: https://www.eca.europa.eu/ECAPublications/SR-2024-06/SR-2024-06_EN.pdf (Accessed 4 February 2025).

²³¹ European Commission, *Ibid.*, 2023a.

²³² SRII WP4 Meso-Level Interview, Ankara-04 (with a supranational organization representative/ Eurocrat).

²³³ European Commission, *Ibid.*, 2024..

²³⁴ PMM, "Ongoing Projects", 2024i, Available at: <https://en.goc.gov.tr/kurumlar/en.goc/I%CC%87ngilizce-devam-eden-projeler.xlsx> (Accessed 3 February 2025).

This encompasses the establishment of the AVRR system through IOM, training of return counsellors, and providing voluntary return and reintegration assistance to irregular migrants. Institutional capacity has also been significantly influenced by EU funding. Staff in migration management, border control, and asylum procedures have received training, while policy frameworks and action plans have been developed. Inter-agency collaboration and international cooperation have also been supported. Data collection and analysis capabilities have been supported with the implementation of projects on biometrical data management and verification systems. This improved data management contributes to more informed decision-making in migration policy.

The EU has played a crucial role in shaping and supporting Turkey's migration management practices through substantial funding and various projects. For a better understanding of the operational structure and the role of the EU, there is a need to systematically analyze the EU-funded projects in Turkey's migration management sector. Through the review of the project descriptions and budgets for 20 projects funded under various instruments related to return migration, including the IPA Home Affairs sector²³⁵, EU Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations²³⁶, Instrument contributing to Stability and Peace (IcSP), and member states' individual support²³⁷ in Turkey. Also, based on the official data, the PMM has completed 74 projects and has 19 ongoing projects, with 48% of these projects funded by EU-related sources: 28 funded by the IPA instrument, 5 by ECHO, and 12 by EU member states.²³⁸ Among those projects, 6 projects were identified directly in relation to return as supporting both Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration (AVRR) and National AVRR programmes. According to the European Commission's "Turkey 2023 Report", 737 irregular migrants were returned through the national voluntary return scheme, while 2,259 were returned with the assistance of IOM and EU financing in 2022.²³⁹ In addition to the IPA instrument, individual member states (Denmark, Netherlands and Norway) provided support for the National Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration System (N-AVRR) project, consisting of two pillars: i) provision of comprehensive support for the implementation and ii) further development of Turkey's N-AVRR system; including capacity building activities and financial assistance provision for conducting voluntary return operations and reintegration assistance.²⁴⁰

For example, the "Support to Registration and Verification of Syrians and Non-Syrians"²⁴¹ project, funded by the EU and implemented with UNHCR, aimed to regularize migrant documentation and combat irregular migration. This project provided the PMM with the necessary resources, including interpreters, supplementary staff, equipment, and training, ensuring accurate and systematic registration of migrants. Such systematic registration is essential for managing migration flows, providing the legal status of migrants, and facilitating their potential return to their home countries or third countries. The "Increasing Technical

²³⁵ European Commission, "Türkiye - financial assistance under IPA", Available at: https://neighbourhood-enlargement.ec.europa.eu/enlargement-policy/overview-instrument-pre-accession-assistance/turkiye-financial-assistance-under-ipa_en (Accessed 09 February 2025).

²³⁶ European Commission, "EU Facility for Refugees in Turkey List of projects committed/decided, contracted, disbursed", 30 September 2024, Available at: https://neighbourhood-enlargement.ec.europa.eu/document/download/49484102-739e-407f-888d-fa7d2dc33879_en?filename=Facility%20for%20Refugees%20in%20Turkey%20-%20List%20of%20Projects.pdf

²³⁷ ICMPD, Ibid., 28 March 2022.

²³⁸ PMM, "Migration Projects", 2022, available at: <https://www.goc.gov.tr/goc-projeleri56> (Accessed 30 September 2024).

²³⁹ European Commission, "Türkiye 2023 Report", 8 November 2023, Available at: https://neighbourhood-enlargement.ec.europa.eu/document/download/eb90aefd-897b-43e9-8373-bf59c239217f_en?filename=SWD_2023_696%20T%C3%BCrkiye%20report.pdf (Accessed 09 February 2025).

²⁴⁰ ICMPD, Ibid., 28 March 2022.

²⁴¹ UNHCR, "Verification of Syrian nationals under temporary protection", 2024e. Available at: https://help.unhcr.org/turkiye/inf2024_ormation-for-syrians/verification-of-syrian-nationals-under-temporary-protection/ (Accessed 09 February 2025).

Capacity for Effective Migration Management" project, funded by the EU, ensured the connection of provincial systems to the central Göç-Net database and provided necessary mobile registration points. The refurbishment and maintenance of removal centres under the EU's support have also been pivotal. "The Increasing Technical Capacity for Effective Migration Management" project aimed to align these centres with international and European standards, enhancing their capacity to detain and process irregular migrants. Based on the analysis of the EU-funded capacity-building projects, it is seen that the EU has also funded the construction of new removal centres and the refurbishment of existing ones to ensure adequate facilities for detention and processing, contributing to the increased capacity and efficiency of Turkey's migration management system.²⁴²

The EU-Turkey cooperation includes capacity-building initiatives, where EU institutions work closely with Turkish authorities to strengthen border management and return procedures. The EU agencies like the European Border and Coast Guard Agency (Frontex) and organizations such as the ICMPD have been involved in providing technical support, training, and resources to help Turkey better manage its borders and ensure effective returns. This institutional collaboration has made the EU an essential actor in the operationalization of Turkey's return policy. Through capacity-building programmes, the EU has facilitated Turkey's ability to enforce return policies and manage refugee populations in a way that meets EU migration control objectives. This cooperation extends to legal frameworks, where the EU's influence on Turkey's migration laws ensures that the country's return policy is designed to reduce irregular migration to Europe.

This financial support has significantly impacted how Turkey handles Syrian returns. While framed and officially categorized as "voluntary," interviews with key stakeholders claim that these returns are often coerced and may be influenced by the precarious conditions in which Syrians live. Although the returns are officially framed as "voluntary," the reality is often much more coercive. As one interviewee from Van noted, "The EU's policy is structured around keeping refugees within Turkey, with funding allocated primarily to support their stay in the country."²⁴³ The EU's financial support has been crucial for Turkey's capacity to house millions of Syrians. However, it also pressures Turkey to manage returns in a way that aligns with the EU's externalization strategy—keeping refugees within Turkish borders rather than facilitating resettlement or genuine voluntary returns.

The EU funding has also bolstered Turkey's border security through projects²⁴⁴ like "Strengthening the Border Control Capacity of Turkey". These initiatives provided advanced surveillance technology, training, and infrastructure to prevent illegal migration and human trafficking. The introduction of electro-optic towers, thermal cameras, and mobile surveillance units has significantly enhanced Turkey's border management capabilities. The construction of a 764 km concrete wall along the Turkish-Syrian border, equipped with advanced surveillance systems, further exemplifies the integration of modern technology into Turkey's border security efforts.

While EU support has undeniably strengthened Turkey's migration management framework, it has also inadvertently supported practices that may undermine migrant rights. The emerging Turkish return regime relies on instruments and discourses that echo those of

²⁴² European Commission, "Türkiye - financial assistance under IPA", 2024, Available at: https://neighbourhood-enlargement.ec.europa.eu/enlargement-policy/overview-instrument-pre-accession-assistance/turkiye-financial-assistance-under-ipa_en (Accessed 09 February 2025).

²⁴³ SRII WP4 Meso-Level Interview, Van-01 (with a border village)

²⁴⁴ Delegation of the European Union to Türkiye, "EU Supports Stronger Border Management in Türkiye", 20 December 2022, Available at: https://www.eeas.europa.eu/delegations/t%C3%BCrkiye/eu-supports-stronger-border-management-t%C3%BCrkiye_en (Accessed 11 February 2025).

European countries due to close cooperation—including substantial financial and technical support from the EU—that has triggered learning processes occurring at the national, local, and international levels.²⁴⁵ However, there are also significant critiques.

As highlighted in the Politico report²⁴⁶, the EU has invested over €11 billion in Turkey to bolster its capacity to house and monitor migrants, with a significant share allocated to border security, asylum processing, and removal centres. The report claims that initially designed to improve living conditions and integration for migrants, the EU-funded facilities like "reception centres" were reoriented toward deportation as political pressures in both Europe and Turkey grew to reduce migrant numbers. In addition, the report states that the EU-funded "Increasing Technical Capacity for Effective Migration Management" project facilitated the linking of Turkey's provincial systems with the Göç-Net database, enhancing the tracking and processing of migrants, including those subjects to deportation orders, often with limited legal recourse. This integration of administrative systems, along with the provision of MMPs, has streamlined Turkey's ability to execute deportations, especially for populations facing precarious circumstances in their home countries, such as Syrians and Afghans.

In more detail, the same report claims that the EU has allocated €213 million to build and maintain around 30 removal centres in Turkey as part of nearly €1 billion in funding for migration control. Some of these funds have supported expanded fingerprinting systems used to track and detain migrants while also reinforcing removal centres with barbed wire and higher walls.²⁴⁷

While the EU insists on its commitment to upholding humanitarian standards, the report²⁴⁸ raised concerns about human rights conditions within these centres, with some deportees stating that they felt pressured to sign "voluntary" return forms due to the risk of detention or mistreatment. This complexity highlights the EU's complex role in migration control—management—on the one hand, and it aims to reduce arrivals to Europe by strengthening and supporting Turkey's capabilities and migration infrastructure, while on the other, it faces criticism for indirectly contributing to returns that may contravene not fully align with international protection obligations. Thus, while standards. However, the EU funding has bolstered Turkey's return infrastructure and strengthened Turkey's capacity to manage migration. It has also raised ethical questions, particularly in Turkey, regarding how these resources to enforce returns and deportations are used in the enforcement of return policies that sometimes conflict with the EU's stated human rights commitments.²⁴⁹

Additionally, some observers suggest that deportations may also serve as a means for Turkey to pressure the EU to negotiate for more increased EU funding to combat irregular migration. The European countries have not shied away from providing Turkey with aid to prevent undocumented migrants from reaching their borders. Projects that were recorded as ongoing at the end of 2017 included 60 million Euros in IPA funds to meet the needs of returnees to Turkey under the EU-Turkey deal and other undocumented migrants apprehended in Turkey. The UK also allotted around 1,3 million pounds for projects relating to voluntary returns, combatting undocumented migration, and maintaining removal centres.²⁵⁰

Consequences: Differentiated Returns of Syrians and Afghans

The EU's approach has reinforced Turkey's securitized and centralized migration governance, particularly in its return policies. The focus on voluntary returns for Syrians is contested, as

²⁴⁵ Zeynep Şahin Mencütek, *Ibid.*, 2023.

²⁴⁶ Zia Weise, *Ibid.*, 11 October 2024.

²⁴⁷ *Ibid.*

²⁴⁸ *Ibid.*

²⁴⁹ *Ibid.*

²⁵⁰ Amy Pitonak, *Ibid.*, 21 June 2018.

restrictive policies, limited access to services, and ID deactivations create conditions that make return the only viable option for many. Meanwhile, Afghans face a harsher reality, with frequent deportations and pushbacks.

Regarding the EU's influence on return policies for different nationalities, its support has contributed to Turkey's voluntary return programs for Syrians. However, some reports suggest that indirect factors—such as limited access to services and the deactivation of identification cards—may create pressures that influence Syrians' decisions to return. This has led to discussions about the extent to which these returns are genuinely voluntary, as some individuals may feel they have limited alternatives.

In contrast, Afghans experience more immediate and forceful returns at the eastern border with Iran. The EU-funded infrastructure, such as the Göç-Net electronic database, has enhanced Turkey's capacity to monitor and swiftly deport Afghan migrants deemed irregular. While the EU emphasizes humanitarian standards, its financial support indirectly strengthens Turkey's enforcement measures, particularly for Afghans with limited access to asylum procedures. However, for Afghans, the EU's role is far less pronounced, leading to unequal treatment and a lack of sufficient legal protections for this group. The coercive nature of returns, whether framed as voluntary or forced, reflects the broader geopolitical strategy of the EU, which seeks to manage migration flows by keeping refugees in Turkey rather than supporting more durable solutions like resettlement or safe returns. Overall, the EU's role in Turkey's return policy has bolstered both voluntary and forced return mechanisms, aligning with a broader strategy of externalizing migration control while raising ethical concerns about the balance between security and human rights protections for refugees and migrants.²⁵¹

Turkey's formulation of return policies is influenced by its strategic geopolitical position, the externalization of EU migration policies, and its own domestic interests. The country transitioned from governmental neglect towards migration in the early 1990s to becoming an active participant in international migration governance, influenced significantly by EU pressure and assistance. This has led to the adoption of various legal and administrative measures aimed at managing and controlling migration, including the policing of unauthorized migration flows. Turkey's migration governance has evolved into a technocratic regime, focusing on the legal infrastructure necessary to manage migration effectively and align with international norms, albeit with continued emphasis on controlling and limiting the influx of migrants and refugees. This approach balances humanitarian considerations and the practical realities of managing large-scale migration flows influenced by external pressures and internal policy goals.

In contrast to the EU's involvement with Syrian refugees, Afghan refugees receive far less attention within the framework of EU-Turkey cooperation. For Afghans, the EU's impact is more indirect but no less significant. The EU's relative lack of concern over Afghan migration in Turkey stems from a combination of externalization policies, geopolitical priorities, and migration control measures already in place. Unlike Syrian migration, which directly impacted Europe during the 2015 crisis, Afghan migration remains largely contained within transit states like Turkey and Iran, reducing its political urgency for the EU. Turkey's strict border enforcement, deportations, and cooperation with the EU ensure that Afghan migrants struggle to move beyond Turkish territory, effectively turning Turkey into a buffer zone that prevents large-scale movement toward Europe.

Additionally, the EUTRS focused on Syrians, leaving Afghans outside the scope of major funding or resettlement programs. While Afghan migration is significant in numbers, it is less

²⁵¹ Suna Gülfer Ihlamur-Öner, "The Global Politics of Refugee Protection and Return: The Case of the Syrian Refugees" in Eva Kasotti ve Narin Idriz (eds), *The Informalisation of the EU's External Action in the Field of Migration and Asylum*, Asser Press, The Hague, ss. 287-315.

visible and politically pressing than Syrian displacement, making it easier for the EU to sideline the issue. The fact that Afghan migrants primarily enter Turkey through Iran, a securitized and difficult-to-cross border, further limits their ability to reach Europe, reducing the EU's need to respond. Moreover, Turkey's proactive deportation of Afghans and restrictive legal policies reinforce the EU's hands-off approach. The EU benefits from Turkey's containment strategies while avoiding direct responsibility for Afghan asylum seekers. The legal and humanitarian complexities of returning Afghans to Taliban-controlled Afghanistan also contribute to EU inaction, as addressing their status would require resettlement efforts or policy shifts that European states are unwilling to pursue. As a result, Afghan migrants in Turkey often find themselves in a state of legal limbo, facing challenges such as deportation, detention, or precarious survival in unstable living conditions. Meanwhile, the EU remains largely indifferent and primarily relies on Turkey to manage the issue without significant intervention.

Several interviews, particularly those conducted in Iğdir and Van, pointed out that the EU's role in supporting Afghan refugees is minimal. One interviewee in Iğdir mentioned, "We don't receive much assistance from the EU for Afghans; the EU is primarily focused on supporting Syrians."²⁵² This highlights the unequal focus of the EU's migration management strategy, which prioritizes Syrians over other refugee populations, leaving Afghans in a far more vulnerable position. Also, others expressed frustration with the EU's one-refugee approach, which primarily benefits Syrians, leaving other nationalities like Afghans at a disadvantage.²⁵³ An NGO representative in Van remarked: "EU focuses its financial support and political dialogue on Syrians, but leaves Afghans without the necessary protection, making them vulnerable to pushbacks and deportations".²⁵⁴ The EU's limited involvement in addressing the root causes of Afghan migration—such as instability and violence in Afghanistan—leaves Turkey with primary responsibility for managing returns, with minimal EU oversight or accountability.²⁵⁵ In parallel, the EU representative in Ankara stated that the EU's role is primarily to provide financial support for integration and voluntary return programmes but admitted that "there are gaps in how we monitor forced returns, particularly in the east where Afghans are most vulnerable."²⁵⁶

The UNHCR representative in Istanbul mentioned, "The EU's funding is directed at managing Syrians, but Afghans are left out of the system. They are deported without any attention from the EU or the international community".²⁵⁷ This highlights a critical gap in the EU's migration management strategy, where the emphasis on externalizing migration has resulted in disparate treatment of refugee populations.

Unlike Syrians, Afghans are often categorized as irregular migrants, making them more vulnerable to deportations and pushbacks, particularly along Turkey's eastern border. The lack of EU attention to Afghans exacerbates this vulnerability, as the EUTRS and broader EU funding mechanisms have largely been centred on Syrians. This has left Afghans in a more precarious position, where their irregular status makes them easy targets for forced returns. While the EU has focused on improving Turkey's capacity to manage migration, it has failed to address the legal vacuum for non-Syrian refugees like Afghans.

²⁵² SRII WP4 Meso-Level Interview, Iğdir-01 (with an academic scholar)

²⁵³ Afghans have been coming to Turkey for many years, but their density has increased from time to time. On the other hand, Syrians reached numbers of up to 4 million in a very short time. This density caused Syrians to move to Europe suddenly and quickly. However, Afghans plan to come to Turkey primarily for economic reasons, work here, save money, and then go to European countries. Therefore, the duration and intensity of influence on Europe are different between the two groups, thus the given policy priorities.

²⁵⁴ SRII WP4 Meso-Level Interview, Van-02 (with a NGO representative)

²⁵⁵ SRII WP4 Meso-Level Interview, Van-03 (with a journalist)

²⁵⁶ SRII WP4 Meso-level Interview, Ankara-04 (with a supranational organization representative/ Eurocrat)

²⁵⁷ SRII WP4 Meso-Level Interview, Ankara-02 (with a nation-wide NGO representative)

The EU's influence also extends to how different refugee groups are treated under Turkish law. Syrians, under TP, enjoy certain legal safeguards against forced return. However, Afghans are often classified as irregular migrants, making them more susceptible to immediate deportation. This legal stratification has been exacerbated by the EU's return policies, which, while focusing on Syrians, often neglect other nationalities like Afghans, who face a far more precarious legal status. For example, the EU-Turkey migration cooperation, particularly the Facility for Refugees in Turkey²⁵⁸, has been instrumental in addressing these challenges. The Facility, established by the European Union in 2015, aims to coordinate resources and support Turkey in managing its substantial refugee population. This initiative was a response to the Syrian refugee crisis but also extended to other nationalities, including Afghans. However, the latest evaluation report by the EC regarding FRIT shows that the EU approaches Syrians and Afghans differently, emphasizing the irregular dimension for Afghans despite the Taliban's take-over mentioned: "The protracted displacement of Syrian refugees and the increasing number of irregular arrivals from Afghanistan in Turkey, following the crisis in Summer 2021"²⁵⁹ The EU's return policy has inadvertently reinforced this stratification, as funding and focus remain disproportionately on Syrians, leaving Afghans more vulnerable to forced returns.

The EU's relative lack of concern over Afghan migration in Turkey stems from a combination of externalization policies, geopolitical priorities, and migration control measures already in place. Unlike Syrian migration, which directly impacted Europe during the 2015 crisis, Afghan migration remains largely contained within transit states like Turkey and Iran, reducing its political urgency for the EU. Turkey's strict border enforcement, deportations, and cooperation with the EU ensure that Afghan migrants struggle to move beyond Turkish territory, effectively turning Turkey into a buffer zone that prevents large-scale movement toward Europe.

The consequences of the EU's externalization policies on Turkey's return policy are far-reaching. By financially and politically incentivizing Turkey to carry out returns, the EU has contributed to the creation of a two-tiered migration system, where Syrians are subject to voluntary returns under duress and Afghans face forced deportations with minimal legal protection. The geopolitical influence of the EU, particularly through the EUTRS, has led to a more centralized and security-driven approach to migration in Turkey, often at the expense of migrant rights. The financial support provided by the EU has enabled Turkey to expand its capacity for returns, but it has also resulted in the irregularization of refugee populations and the erosion of legal protections. As Turkey continues to build its national return policy, the EU's externalization strategy remains a driving force with significant implications for the rights and safety of refugees.

The fieldwork showed that the political cooperation between Turkey and the EU moves towards return rather than integration and maintains the differentiated approach for Syrians and Afghans. The EU's financial involvement further underscores its role in supporting Turkey's structured returns and border management approach, emphasizing containment over integration. The EU representative states, "Our institution initially prioritized social integration of Syrians under temporary protection, providing financial and logistical support to Turkey's migration management, particularly in registration and verification efforts. Later, we expanded our programme to cover Afghans or non-Syrians. However, there has been a shift

²⁵⁸ European Commission. *Ibid.*, 2023a.,

²⁵⁹ European Commission, "Final Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council Seventh Annual Report of the Facility for Refugees in Turkey", 2023b. Available at: https://neighbourhood-enlargement.ec.europa.eu/seventh-annual-report-facility-refugees-turkey_en (Accessed 17 September 2024).),

in recent years, with increased emphasis on return and managing irregular migration, reflecting political pressure within Turkey and the EU to address migration more stringently”.²⁶⁰

The EU representative notes that returns are increasingly framed within "political pressures" to address irregular migration, especially as Turkey has tightened its stance on border enforcement and return mechanisms. As a result, the EU has played a cautious role, often aligning with UNHCR as a "safeguard" to avoid reputational risks associated with forced returns, although some EU states also indirectly press for returns to alleviate domestic migration pressures.²⁶¹ Consequently, the EU has provided substantial funding and resources to Turkey's migration management system, which has gradually included "address verification" exercises and policies that risk irregularizing migrants by restricting movement, a factor indirectly promoting return.²⁶²

The fieldwork shows us that the EU mainly takes a role with financial support, primarily used for migration control, border management and most recently, the establishment of the national return mechanism. It should be noted that the interviews and also the observations as a part of the fieldwork reflect the EU's indirect role, through funding NGOs and legal assistance, in trying to address the issue, albeit with limited effectiveness, given the legal and political restrictions on monitoring and intervention in Turkey's migration management. The EU's influence, particularly through funding, has significantly shaped Turkey's return policies. Interviews suggest that European funding has indirectly encouraged Turkey's strict border control and return systems, as noted by a researcher: "EU funding has built capacities here not just for integration but for controlling borders and ensuring that the 'return' infrastructure works in line with Europe's expectations."²⁶³

The EU's financial support has contributed to Turkey's return infrastructure, indirectly reinforcing practices that lead to both voluntary and forced returns. The EU aims to manage migration flows outside its borders, yet this funding often aligns with Turkey's securitized migration policies. For example, IGO officials describe TACs developed with EU-backed administrative support as "necessary" yet problematic due to the limited legal recourse and rights access for migrants within these centres. The EU's involvement thus adds a layer of complexity, as financial support and capacity-building efforts for return systems align with Turkey's stricter enforcement, even as the EU advocates for voluntary and safe returns.

Finally, while the EU representatives of the different directorate generals (DGs) in Turkey clearly stated that they have no role in cross-border operations, the Turkish state officials mentioned the need for collaboration to expand the safe zone in Northern Syria. According to a senior state official in Gaziantep, the EU's investment in border technology and infrastructure indirectly reinforces Turkey's enforcement capabilities. The official mentioned the EU's role in "funding facilities and technologies for border security," which in practice aligns with Turkey's forced return efforts for migrants classified as irregular.²⁶⁴ On the other hand, there is a lack of sufficient EU resettlement options. The ambiguity in EU policies further complicates the return dynamic. A state official at the important border crossing highlighted that while the EU supports voluntary return mechanisms, its reluctance to expand resettlement quotas "creates a bottleneck," as refugees have fewer safe alternatives beyond return to Syria or transit to Europe under precarious conditions.²⁶⁵ In addition, it is stated by the two officials that the EU's support for Turkey's cross-border operations is not enough, and

²⁶⁰ SRII WP4 Meso Level Interview, Ankara- 04 (with a supranational organization representative/ Eurocrat)

²⁶¹ Ibid.

²⁶² Ibid.

²⁶³ Ibid.

²⁶⁴ SRII WP4 Meso-Level Interview, Gaziantep-07 (with a public officer)

²⁶⁵ SRII WP4 Meso-Level Interview, Gaziantep-06 (with a public officer)

there is a need for expanding the safe zone since the existing safe area is not enough for returns in case of voluntary returns.

Figure 9 shows the general return-related actors and those at the local level in the selected cities where the fieldwork is conducted. The figure presents a mapping of actors involved in return processes in Turkey, illustrating the complex and multi-layered governance of migration returns. It categorizes actors into migrants, state institutions, civil society organizations, international NGOs, intergovernmental organizations, and supranational entities like the EU. This diverse network reflects how migration governance extends beyond state control, involving multiple stakeholders with competing interests and roles.

State actors, particularly the MoI, PMM, PDMs, and law enforcement actors such as police, gendarmerie, and coast guard/cost guards, play a central role in enforcement, border control, and return mechanisms. The inclusion of courts, including the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR), highlights the legal contestation surrounding deportations, suggesting that some cases are subject to judicial review.

The presence of national and local NGOs, civil society organizations, and informal structures demonstrates bottom-up engagement in migration governance, both in support and in the facilitation of returns. While organizations like ASAM, Refugee Rights Turkey (RRT) and Bar Associations provide legal and humanitarian assistance, informal actors such as tribes, local shop owners, and human smugglers reflect the hidden, often extra-legal dimensions of migration management at the local level.

The figure also highlights the role of international and supranational organizations, including the UNHCR, IOM, and the EU, which fund, coordinate, or influence return operations through policies and agreements. The EU's DG HOME, DG NEAR, and DG ECHO indicate a focus on migration control, externalization, and humanitarian assistance, reinforcing Turkey's role as a buffer zone in European migration governance.

Critically, this mapping underscores how migration return is not a singular state-driven process but a complex field of governance shaped by intersecting legal, political, humanitarian, and informal actors. The inclusion of both enforcement and humanitarian organizations raises questions about whether returns are managed as protection-based processes or as securitized mechanisms of migration control. Moreover, the involvement of local actors and informal networks highlights the blurry line between official return processes and irregular pushback dynamics, making it essential to scrutinize how return policies are implemented in practice.

Figure 9: Actors Related to Returns and Readmission of Syrians and Afghans

Source: The authors prepared based on the desk research and the conducted fieldwork

4.3.3. Selected Return-Related Practices

Turkey's return migration practices have evolved significantly and have been influenced by various factors, including but not limited to domestic priorities, securitization, and the EU's externalization policies, which are operationalized through substantial EU funds. However, several practices within Turkey's migration governance have raised concerns about their impact on migrants, particularly regarding the creation of an environment fuelled by intimidation practices and the nature of voluntary returns. Here, the dossier focused on important practices regarding the returns of Syrians and Afghans.

Following a policy change in June 2022, Syrians who enter the country are transferred to TACs in Gaziantep, Kahramanmaraş, Hatay, Kilis and Malatya, based on Article 8 of the TPR. The TACs in Turkey serve as sites for housing and processing certain groups of refugees, particularly newly arriving Syrians under TP. However, admission to the TAC is at the discretion of PDMM. Hence, these camps have become a new form of detention facility for Syrians who are either not registered under the TP regime or have had their TP status revoked.²⁶⁶ Due to this practice, registration is one of the main issues faced by Syrian migrants. This resulted in the registered number of Syrian migrants under TP from 3,535,898 in 2022 to 3,092,536 in 2024, particularly due to individual exits, returns and changes in their status.

Admission to these centres is at the discretion of PDMM, with no formal rejection decision required, and judicial review is largely inaccessible. This structure creates a situation where, if denied access to these TACs, Syrians face "voluntary return" to Syria as their only alternative, blurring the lines between voluntary and forced return. The interviewees shared their concerns regarding that these TACs effectively function as *de facto* detention centres, especially for Syrians who lack registration under the temporary protection regime or whose protection status has been revoked. In particular, lawyers claim that PDMM's discretionary practices have been increasingly used to avoid formal registration and deportation procedures, effectively sidestepping due process. Syrians in these centres have limited access to legal assistance, restricted communication with family, and limited access to legal counsel, even though lawyer visits are technically allowed. The overall outcome is that Syrians are left with no clear, accessible legal recourse, making "voluntary return" feel more like an enforced decision than a choice. With the above-mentioned figures, the decline reflects individual exits, status changes, and returns, though the line between voluntary and forced remains blurred by the constrained options and restricted rights within TACs.

Deportations under the guise of voluntary returns for Syrian migrants have been prevalent, with the HRW reporting that between February and July 2022, there had been incidents of arbitrary arrests, detentions, and deportations of hundreds of Syrian men and boys to Syria^{267, 268} While official statements emphasize that these returns are voluntary, during the fieldwork, some Syrians have reported feeling pressured or misled into signing voluntary return forms, citing experiences of intimidation, threats, or, in some cases, physical force.²⁶⁹ The Minister of Interior, Ali Yerlikaya, announced that between 2016 and 2024, 715,654 Syrians voluntarily and safely returned to their homes in northern Syria.²⁷⁰ However, this narrative is challenged by reports from some Syrians who describe their returns as influenced by difficult circumstances rather than entirely voluntary decisions.²⁷¹ The distinction between

²⁶⁶ AIDA, *Ibid.*, 8 August 2024.

²⁶⁷ HRW, *Ibid.*, 24 October 2022.

²⁶⁸ *Ibid.*

²⁶⁹ Rottmann, S. B. vd., *Ibid.*, 2024.

²⁷⁰ A Haber, *Ibid.*, 26 September 2024.

²⁷¹ HRW, *Ibid.*, 24 October 2022.

voluntary and forced returns remains complex and has led to ongoing discussions about the treatment of migrants within Turkey's migration system. Turkish authorities often associate the voluntary return of Syrians with the "safe zones" established following military operations such as Euphrates Shield and Olive Branch in northern Syria. According to field interviews, Turkey has taken a broad approach to revitalizing these areas, including humanitarian aid, infrastructure investments, the development of industrial and commercial zones, the construction of briquette houses, and the provision of education and healthcare services.²⁷²

Briefly, since 2019, Turkey's migration policy has shifted significantly towards restricting access to urban registration and concentrating migrants within controlled spaces like TACs. Since 2022, Turkey has required new applicants for TP first to be referred to TACs before registration rather than allowing them to register directly in urban areas. This effectively restricts their mobility and increases state control over new arrivals. At the same time, there are claims from the first focus group study suggesting that some Syrians are detained and pressured into signing voluntary return forms in removal centres, which operate separately from TACs., may experience pressure to sign voluntary return forms while in detention.²⁷³ The interviews and the focus group study indicated that some individuals return after being detained and pressured into signing voluntary return forms in removal centres, raising questions about the extent to which these returns are not always as entirely voluntary as they appear.²⁷⁴ While refugees in TACs are not necessarily "forcibly held" in TACs against their will, they are subject to mobility restrictions that can limit their ability to leave freely. At the same time, access to TACs is not always guaranteed, and those individuals without legal status face heightened risks of administrative detention and/or deportation.²⁷⁵ These challenging conditions contribute to a situation where many feel compelled, which may lead some to "opt for voluntary return", even if it is not their preferred choice.

Another important practice that Turkey utilized was the address verification exercise to regularize the documentation of Syrian migrants. As part of the exercise, Syrians who were not found at their declared/registered address were given a 90-day grace period to update their addresses with PDMMs. In the case of missing this period, their registration is deactivated, severely limiting their access to rights and services. While their IDs can be reactivated upon presenting themselves to the PDMM, those who fail to do so lose their IDs, pushing them towards being irregular migrants or faced with forced returns. The MoI reported that in 2023, 731,146 Syrian migrants out of 3,092,536 were found without updated address registration. Among them, 242,853 updated their addresses, 192,812 have a pending appointment to update address registration, and the address status of 291,481 individuals is unknown.²⁷⁶ The implementation of the V71 restriction code (unknown address), which suspends the registration procedure for those who cannot be found, further complicates the situation.²⁷⁷

Another recent practice is the operations to combat irregular migration and realize the policy objectives; Turkey carried out various Kalkan (Shield) Operations targeting migrant smugglers and irregular migrants, employed charter flights, enhanced border security and fences, and deployed mobile migration points. As a result of these practices, between 4 June 2023 and 20 September 2024, 9,863 operations were carried out against migrant smuggling, 214,217 individuals were intercepted at the borders, and 182,980 irregular migrants were

²⁷² WP4 Meso Level Interview, Gaziantep-7 (with a public representative)

²⁷³ The first focus group study held with participation of over 20 legal practitioners from different provinces on 19th January 2024 in Istanbul. This meeting was held under the Chatham House Rules, and there will be no public audience.

²⁷⁴ Ibid.

²⁷⁵ Ibid.

²⁷⁶ A Haber, Ibid., 26 September 2024.

²⁷⁷ AIDA, Ibid., 8 August 2024.

deported. 270 mobile migration points were deployed in 81 provinces, which identified 138,356 irregular migrants and referred them to GÖKSEM for deportation processes. Lastly, between 4 June 2023 and 20 September 2024, 126 charter flights were organized for the deportation of 23,779 irregular migrants, composed of particularly Afghans.²⁷⁸ The mobile migration points are primarily situated in busy squares, streets, and transportation hubs. However, such measures likely instilled a sense of insecurity among refugees, prompting them to exercise self-imposed isolation from social life.²⁷⁹

4.3.4. Capacities of Return Migration Governance

The PMM has developed a comprehensive framework for managing migration, integrating robust technological systems, physical infrastructures, and international cooperation to enhance border security and manage migrant flows effectively. The strategic use of personnel, advanced technology, and detailed policies aims to address the challenges posed by irregular migration and improve the overall management of migration in Turkey.

As outlined in the 2019-2023 strategic plan²⁸⁰ by the PMM, the organization employs a total of 4,051 personnel. This includes 1,621 permanent staff, 119 contracted employees, 162 service procurement workers, 888 temporary staff, and 1,262 permanent workers. The PMM operates through a central organization and provincial units headed by a Director General, Deputy Directors General, 13 service units, and permanent boards and commissions. The provincial organization comprises 81 provincial directorates and district group directorates, removal centres, temporary accommodation centres, reception and accommodation centres, and shelters for victims of human trafficking. The PMM is responsible for managing various physical structures and information technology resources, including²⁸¹:

- PMM international protection bureaus (decision centres) and mobile decision teams
- 30 removal centres with a total detention capacity of 22,140 individuals
- 81 provincial directorates and 35 district directorates
- Voluntary return offices at the border gates
- Coordination and Joint Risk Analysis Centre (NACORAC)
- Temporary accommodation centres
- 270 mobile migration points
- 67 verification centres for data updates of TP/IP holders

GöçNet, the migration database, integrates various inter-agency modules such as fingerprint and picture recording, restriction codes, language detection systems, and enhanced traveller recording systems.²⁸² It includes 26 modules: the e-Residence Module, Visa Module, International Protection Module, and Entry Ban Module. GöçNet provides comprehensive management of residence permit applications, visa processes, and international protection

²⁷⁸ A Haber, *Ibid.*, 26 September 2024.

²⁷⁹ SRII WP4 Meso Level Interview, Gaziantep-1 (with an IGO representative)

²⁸⁰ PMM, *Ibid.*, 2023.

²⁸¹ Ali Yerlikaya (@AliYerlikaya), “81 ilimizde 270 adet mobil göç noktası aracımız hizmet veriyor”, 7 December 2024. Available at: <https://x.com/AliYerlikaya/status/1865277713839165820> (Accessed 28 February 2025); PMM, *Ibid.*, 2024; PMM, *Ibid.*, 25 December 2022.

²⁸² PMM, “2023 Faaliyet Raporu”, 2024. Available at: <https://www.goc.gov.tr/kurumlar/goc.gov.tr/Mali-Tablolar/FAALİYET-RAPORU/2023/2023-Yili-Idare-Faaliyet-Raporu.pdf> (Accessed 28 February 2025); Sayıştay, “2019 Göçnet Projesi Bilisim Sistemleri Denetimi Özeti”. Available at: <https://www.sayistay.gov.tr/reports/download/Xl3g485gKO-gocnet-projesi-bilisim-sistemleri-denetimi-ozeti-2019> (Accessed 28 February 2025).

applications. YİMER 157 (Foreigners Communication Centre) offers 24/7 service in Turkish, English, Russian, German, Arabic, and Persian.²⁸³

The Migration Board, led by the MoI, sets migration strategies, coordination, and implementation, comprising representatives from various ministries and institutions. The PMM, authorized by Article 163 of Presidential Decree No. 4, can establish overseas organizations, including migration advisers in embassies and consulates. These advisers facilitate the deportation or voluntary return of irregular migrants, liaising with relevant countries to ensure smooth operations.

From 2019 to 2023, the MoI enhanced border security to combat terrorism and human smuggling. Key developments include:²⁸⁴

- Constructing 230 km of security walls and patrol roads, totalling 1,160 km
- Installing 227 km of razor wire systems on these walls
- Building 23.5 km of stone-reinforced embankments, patrol roads, and high-security panel fences on the Turkey-Iraq border
- Integrating 294 km of lighting systems and sensor systems along 368 km of the border
- Constructing 1,897 km of security roads, totalling 4,517 km
- Organizing training sessions on integrated border management
- Building 151 elevator tower systems on the eastern and southeastern borders
- Completing 598 km of energy transmission lines
- Procuring 341 electro-optic towers, 284 thermal cameras, and 139 armoured border surveillance vehicles, funded by the EU

According to the Strategic Plan of the MoI²⁸⁵, Turkey's return policies continue to evolve, with the capacity of removal centres reaching 22,140 as of 2023. The ratio of human trafficking victims returning to their source, transit, or third countries through voluntary and safe return programmes is 21%, a target also set for 2024 and 2025. The increase rate in voluntary and safe returns was 40% in 2022, surpassing the planned 15%. A 30% increase was recorded in 2023, with targets set at a 20% increase for 2024 and 2025. The target for deportations in 2022 was 53,000, but 90,000 foreigners were deported. Annual deportation targets for 2023, 2024, and 2025 are set at 50,000.²⁸⁶

The following **Figure 10** highlights Turkey's highly securitized and technology-driven migration governance, emphasizing surveillance, biometric tracking, and militarized border control. The integration of electronic monitoring, removal centres, mobile migration units, and biometric databases suggests a shift from protection-based policies to enforcement-focused migration management. While these measures enhance state control, they risk criminalizing migration and limiting access to asylum, reinforcing a security-first approach over humanitarian considerations.

²⁸³ Sayıştay, Ibid.

²⁸⁴ Republic of Türkiye Ministry of Interior, Ibid., 2024.

²⁸⁵ Ibid.

²⁸⁶ PMM, Ibid., 2023.

Figure 10: Capacities of Return Migration

Sources:
 *PFMM, "Sistem Bakanlık Sayın Ali Yerlikaya İncelemesinde Üst Düzey Güvenlik Tedbirlerini Anlattı", 2024, available at: <https://www.goc.gov.tr/kurumlar/goc.gov.tr/ODC-TV/2024/3-Mart/01-Mart/31/islemler/Bakanlik-Sayin-Ali-Yerlikaya-Incelemesinde-Ust-Duzey-Guvenlik-Olemlerini-Anlatti.mp4> (Accessed 23 May 2024).
 +1908M, "Göç İdaresi Başkanlığı 2019-2023 Strateji Planı", 2023, available in Turkish at: https://www.goc.gov.tr/kurumlar/goc.gov.tr/Mali-Talimat/STRATEJIS-PLANI/2019-2023/strateji_Plan_2019_2023-2.pdf (Accessed 24 May 2024).

Source: The authors prepared based on the desk research citing the publicly open sources mentioned above.

5. Preliminary Reflections on Post-Assad Syria and Returns

On December 8, 2024, Syria witnessed a transformative moment when armed rebels, predominantly led by 'Hay'at Tahrir al-Sham (HTS), gained control of Damascus, leading to President Bashar al-Assad's departure from the country. This development, marking the end of a 14-year civil war, has created a complex mixture of hope and uncertainty among Syrian migrants, including the 2.8 million living under temporary protection in Turkey.²⁸⁷ While the political transition suggests possibilities for a return, the reality on the ground reveals a more nuanced situation where security concerns, infrastructure and housing challenges, and practical considerations heavily influence refugee decision-making.²⁸⁸

The scale of Syria's displacement crisis remains staggering. More than half of the pre-war population has been displaced, with over 13 million Syrians forced from their homes since 2011. Of these, 7 million remain internally displaced within Syria, while more than 6 million have sought refuge in neighbouring countries, Europe and beyond. Recent regional developments have further complicated this landscape, with over half a million people fleeing Syria from Lebanon in late 2024 due to Israeli airstrikes, while simultaneously, over 1.1 million Syrians faced new internal displacement²⁸⁹ between November and December 2024.

Since 2017, 821,579 returns²⁹⁰ have been recorded from Turkey, including 81,576²⁹¹ since the fall of the Assad regime. Turkey has introduced a policy allowing Syrians to make temporary "go-and-see" visits to assess the situation in Syria. Under this "go-and-see visit program" implemented since January 1, 2025, Syrian families can apply through their head of household (or the eldest adult family member if the head is unable) for permission to make up to three visits to Syria within a six-month period. Processing of voluntary returns continues in provinces and at five border crossings, while three border crossings are open for processing go-and-see visits. In the first week of implementation (January 1-8), 1,766 Syrians²⁹² have already utilized this program to make exploratory visits. On 16 January, Turkish Airlines announced²⁹³ the resumption of flights to Damascus as of 23 January, with three flights per week.

According to UNHCR's 11th Regional Flash Update on the Syria Situation Crisis²⁹⁴, voluntary returns from Turkey mostly involve individuals returning alone, often due to the absence of

²⁸⁷ PMM, "Temporary Protection". 23 January 2025, Available at: <https://en.goc.gov.tr/temporary-protection27> (Accessed 1 February 2025).

²⁸⁸ Umutcan Yüksel and N. Ela Gökalg, "Preliminary Reflections on Post-Assad Syria: Emerging Dynamics and the Complex Reality of Refugee Returns from Türkiye", 23 December 2024, Available at: <https://www.returnmigration.eu/gapsblog/preliminary-reflections-on-post-assad-syria> (Accessed 1 February 2025).

²⁸⁹ OCHA, "Syria Flash Update No. 5 - Recent Developments in Syria (As of 12 December 2024) [EN/AR]", 12 December 2024, Available at: <https://www.unocha.org/publications/report/syrian-arab-republic/syria-flash-update-no-5-recent-developments-syria-12-december-2024> (Accessed 1 February 2025).

²⁹⁰ PMM, "İçişleri Bakanı Ali Yerlikaya'nın Başkanlığında 15. Göç Kurulu Toplantısı Gerçekleştirildi", 20 January 2025, Available at: <https://www.goc.gov.tr/icisleri-bakani-ali-yerlikayanin-baskanliginda-15-goc-kurulu-toplantisi-gerceklestirildi> (Accessed 1 February 2025).

²⁹¹ Ali Yerlikaya, "Geri dönüşler", 29 January 2025, Available at: <https://x.com/AliYerlikaya/status/1884575731960701416> (Accessed 1 February 2025).

²⁹² PMM, "İçişleri Bakanı Ali Yerlikaya: "Bir Ayda 52 Bin 622 Suriyeli Gönüllü, Güvenli, Onurlu ve Düzenli Geri Dönüş Yaptı", 10 January 2025, Available at: <https://www.goc.gov.tr/icisleri-bakani-ali-yerlikaya-bir-ayda-52-bin-622-suriyeli-gonullu-guvenli-onurlu-ve-duzenli-geri-donus-yapti> (Accessed 1 February 2025).

²⁹³ AP News, "Turkish Airlines will resume flights to Damascus, officials say after visit by Syria's new rulers", 16 January 2025, Available at: <https://apnews.com/article/turkish-airlines-damascus-flights-3fc385df53d33653d3b0acc7a174ea0e2> (1 February 2025).

²⁹⁴ UNHCR, "Regional Flash Update #11: Syria situation crisis", 23 January 2025, Available at: <https://reporting.unhcr.org/syria-situation-crisis-regional-flash-update-11> (Accessed 1 February 2025).

dependent family members in Turkey or because they intend to assess conditions in Syria before reuniting with their families. The primary reasons for returning include improved security, political changes and family reunification, with some citing homesickness or economic considerations. Most returnees aim to return to their province of origin, with Aleppo, Idleb, Damascus and Hama being the most common destinations. Challenges such as property destruction, family relocation, inadequate infrastructure and security concerns influence their choices of destination. Property ownership remains a critical factor, with many returnees owning homes, though some lack the documents needed to claim them. While most returnees hold Syrian civil documentation, gaps in birth, marriage and divorce records are common.

The average number of daily returns was around 200-300 people in the pre-fall of the Assad period, while it has drastically increased to an average of 1,100-1,150 since the fall of Assad. Despite this drastic increase, it can also be observed that political change alone does not automatically trigger large-scale organized returns. Instead, refugees carefully weigh multiple pull and push factors and conditions in their decision-making process. In fact, factors influencing the decision to return to Syria include assistance status in the host country, ethnicity, gender, marital status, and security, as well as housing conditions in the place of origin.

According to MDM, Turkey's needs assessment on the intentions of Syrian communities in İzmir and Hatay²⁹⁵ is evident in the critical role of security conditions in shaping their intention or pulse to return. In İzmir, 55% of key informants, who are primarily originating from northeast Syria, reported no intention to return at the moment, while in Hatay, only 20% of the community indicated no intention to return. Another intention survey on the future plans and humanitarian needs of the Syrian migrants in Turkey, carried out by Support to Life²⁹⁶, indicates that 53% of the respondents' intend to stay in Turkey, while 18.9% would like to return to Syria and 8.9% hoped to settle in a third country.

The survey²⁹⁷ also reveals geographical and contextual insights. Participants originating from conflict-prone regions like Haseke and Deir ez-Zor are less likely to return due to ongoing instability. Meanwhile, participants from Aleppo and Damascus, where security has improved, are more inclined to consider returning. Housing conditions in Syria remain a critical issue, with many participants reporting that their homes are either destroyed or heavily damaged, further discouraging return. Demographic factors such as gender and marital status also influence decisions. Women-led households and single individuals are less inclined to return, reflecting economic vulnerabilities and safety concerns. In contrast, male-headed and married households show a slightly higher intention to return.

Regardless of complex pull and push factors and the characteristics as well as the priorities of the Syrian community in Turkey, ensuring the territorial integrity of the country with a priority given to an inclusive governance system and improvement of safety and security conditions are the most important elements in determining the return decisions of Syrian migrants. Until the fall of the Assad regime on December 8, 2024, the EU had a position of "no normalization,

²⁹⁵ ReliefWeb, "Rapid needs assessment intentions of Syrian communities in Türkiye to return to their hometowns in Syria", 21 January 2025, Available at: <https://reliefweb.int/report/turkiye/rapid-needs-assessment-intentions-syrian-communities-turkiye-return-their-hometowns-syria-january-2025> (Accessed 1 February 2025).

²⁹⁶ Supporttolife, "Intention Survey Report On The Future Plans And Humanitarian Needs Of Syrian Refugees In Türkiye", 20 January 2025, Available at: <https://www.supporttolife.org/announcements/intention-survey-report-on-the-future-plans-and-humanitarian-needs-of-syrian-refugees-in-turkiye-2/> (Accessed 1 February 2025).

²⁹⁷ Ibid.

lifting of sanctions or reconstruction until a political transition”²⁹⁸. With Bashar al-Assad gone and his autocracy in ruins, the Foreign Affairs Council of the EU reached a political agreement²⁹⁹ to begin easing sanctions on Syria to give a boost to the Syrian economy and help the country get back on its feet on January 27, 2025. Diplomats in Brussels³⁰⁰ believe there is enough consensus to make the decision, but they caution that the sanctions will not be lifted in the sense of being permanently erased. Instead, they will be temporarily "suspended" and coupled with a "fallback mechanism" that can reinstate the penalties if HTS fails to deliver on its promises of inclusive governance.

Even prior to this decision, humanitarian exemptions had already been made to the EU's Syria sanction regime. On January 17, 2025, the EC announced³⁰¹ the provision of new humanitarian support to Syrians, both inside Syria and in neighbouring countries, for an amount of €235 million for 2025. However, despite these exemptions and derogations for humanitarian aid, NGOs face a complex, costly landscape in their operations. A 2023 study by the European Parliament³⁰² highlighted the "widespread refusal" of banks to process any transfers to Syria and the "chilling effect" created by the fear of violating sanctions. Therefore, restoring financial ties between Europe and Syria will be essential to ramp up assistance for reconstruction, infrastructure and public services.

Lastly, considering the persistent volatility on the ground, any returns should be based on achieving protection thresholds and parameters³⁰³, as set by UNHCR in 2018.

6. Conclusion

To analyse the effects of return migration governance from Turkey to Syria and Afghanistan, it is critical to understand the nuanced dynamics of how Turkey manages returns with the EU's support and influence, particularly for Syrians and Afghans. Along with the comprehensive desk research, the meso-level interviews of the multi-sited fieldwork offer rich empirical insights into this governance system, including coercive and voluntary returns and the differentiated treatment of these two national groups.

The report, drawing from the interviews, underscores the critical role of external actors, especially the EU, in shaping Turkey's return policies, revealing the often coercive and inconsistent application of these policies, particularly toward vulnerable populations like Afghans and Syrians. Turkey's approach to Syrian and Afghan returns highlights distinct strategies rooted in legal, social, and political considerations. It reveals that the governance

²⁹⁸ EPRS, "Impact of sanctions on the humanitarian situation in Syria", June 2023, [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2023/749765/EPRS_BRI\(2023\)749765_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2023/749765/EPRS_BRI(2023)749765_EN.pdf) (Accessed 1 February 2025).

²⁹⁹ European Council, "Main results: Russian war of aggression against Ukraine", 2025, Available at: <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/meetings/fac/2025/01/27/> (Accessed 1 February 2025).

³⁰⁰ EuroNews, "EU is about to start suspending sanctions on Syria. How many are in place?", 27 January 2025, Available at: <https://www.euronews.com/my-europe/2025/01/27/eu-is-about-to-start-suspending-sanctions-on-syria-how-many-are-in-place> (1 February 2025).

³⁰¹ European Commission, "EU provides €235 million humanitarian aid to Syrians", 17 January 2025. Available at: https://reliefweb.int/report/syrian-arab-republic/eu-provides-eu235-million-humanitarian-aid-syrians?_gl=1*_1103yqe*_gcl_aw*RONMLjE3MzQxOTk4MDYuQ2p3SoNBaUE5dIM2OmhBOUVpdoFKcG5Yd3d4LXVaSoVJbHROSzhnVVJnWnRKUmXmKracS1YT3h3RjFGUjlxOTNMYVBkekiVUIRLYk1oboNTVkiROXZEXoJ3RO..*_ga*NzU3OTI1Mzc3LjE3MzEyNjg1NjU.*_ga_E6oZNX2F68*MTczODI1NTczNC4yMC4xLjE3MzgyNTU5NDkuNjAuMC4w (Accessed 1 February 2025).

³⁰² EPRS, *Ibid.*, June 2023.

³⁰³ ODP, "Comprehensive Protection and Solutions Strategy: Protection Thresholds and Parameters for Refugee Return to Syria", 2015, Available at: <https://data.unhcr.org/en/documents/details/63223> (Accessed 1 February 2025).

system in place for Syrians focuses heavily on the concept of ‘voluntary returns’ to northern Syria, with substantial EU financial and logistical support. The research highlights that coercive measures are often at play while these returns are officially labelled as voluntary. This reflects a system where returnees are guided toward returning, not solely by choice but because of systemic pressure that leaves them with few options. The safe zone approach in northern Syria, heavily supported by Turkish military and political interests, is a focal point for return migration governance. While Turkey advocates for the establishment of “safe zones” in northern Syria, some reports suggest that these areas may face infrastructure challenges, leading to discussions about the long-term sustainability and safety of returns to these regions. Additionally, TACs in cities like Gaziantep and Kilis have been described as facilities where Syrians without valid protection status may experience detention-like measures and feel pressure to sign voluntary return agreements. This has led to concerns that the distinction between voluntary and forced returns may not always be clear. However, despite investments, including EU funds for infrastructure and services, interviewees express concerns over these safe zones' actual safety and sustainability.

In contrast, Afghans encounter a more structured and expedited return process with limited legal and procedural safeguards. Classified primarily as irregular migrants, many face rapid deportations and pushbacks at Turkey’s eastern border, particularly single men who do not benefit from the legal protections available to Syrians under the TPR. Afghan migrants experience limited access to legal aid or asylum applications and face harsh conditions during deportations, often without due process. This stratification in return policy, grounded in Turkey's prioritization of national security and irregular migration control, underscores these two groups' complex and differentiated treatment. As a result, they are more vulnerable to deportations, pushbacks, and fewer legal protections during the return process. For Afghans, returns are conducted swiftly and with limited oversight, often due to geopolitical pressures on Turkey to manage migration flows from Afghanistan after the Taliban’s takeover in 2021.

The operational infrastructure supporting return migration to Syria and Afghanistan is largely financed by EU mechanisms, though the nature of these returns is contested. The interviewees pointed out that the EU's external migration policy plays a significant role in shaping Turkey's approach, not being interested or monitoring the conditions for the returnees. These claims tie into broader critiques about the EU’s externalization of migration management, which delegates responsibility to countries like Turkey to prevent irregular migrants from reaching Europe while financing infrastructure that facilitates returns. Despite the official rhetoric of humane returns, interviewees frequently pointed out the coercive aspects of Turkey's return migration system, especially regarding pushbacks at borders and the use of detention centres where migrants are often pressured into signing voluntary return forms. These practices are particularly pervasive in the return of Afghans.

The governance of return migration from Turkey to Syria and Afghanistan reveals a complex system deeply influenced by the EU’s external migration policies and Turkey’s domestic priorities. For Syrians, return policies are cloaked in voluntary rhetoric, but coercion is a common theme, driven by legal uncertainty and economic pressures in Turkey. The safe zones in northern Syria, a key element of return policy, remain under-resourced and insecure, complicating long-term sustainability for returnees. For Afghans, the situation is starker, with a focus on forced deportations, reflecting Turkey's broader geopolitical interests and limited legal protections for Afghans.

In conclusion, Turkey's return policy reflects a complex interplay between voluntary and forced returns, with a marked shift toward enforcement. This differentiation and reliance on coercive mechanisms call for ongoing scrutiny to ensure that Turkey’s return policies adhere to international norms and provide adequate protection for both Syrian and Afghan migrants.

Finally, the developments following December 8, 2024, have significantly reshaped the landscape of return migration governance in Turkey, particularly regarding Syrians. The developments after this date mark a critical juncture for Turkey's return policies. The political changes in Syria have provided Turkish authorities with renewed justification for return facilitation, yet the feasibility of large-scale returns remains highly contested. The role of the EU in shaping Turkey's return infrastructure will also be tested as European policymakers weigh the ethical and legal implications of supporting returns under current conditions.

Moving forward, Turkey's return policies are expected to be increasingly influenced by domestic political pressures, economic constraints, and diplomatic negotiations with both the EU and Syrian opposition groups. While the Turkish government may push for greater numbers of returns, the reality on the ground—marked by ongoing instability in Syria and the legal precarity of many refugees—suggests that the process will remain complex and contested. Thus, there is a need for continued monitoring of return policies, particularly in light of emerging geopolitical developments. The intersection of legal, political, and humanitarian concerns will shape the next phase of Turkey's migration governance, with lasting implications for both refugees and broader regional stability.

7. References

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